

Organization:

5TH MEETING OF YOUNG BIOPHYSICISTS

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

BIOPHYSICS FESTIVAL
NOVA FCT | CAPARICA

08-09 MAY 2025

Organizing Committee

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Tatiana João Carneiro CIBB & CNC- Universidade de Coimbra (UC)

Tomás Vieira Gulbenkian Institute for Molecular Medicine (GIMM)

Scientific Committee

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Pedro J. B. Pereira I3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto (UP)

BIOPHYSICS FESTIVAL – 5th Meeting of Young Biophysicists
8th - 9th May 2025
NOVA School of Science and Technology, Caparica, Portugal

Ricardo Franco UCIBIO-i4HB, Nova School of Science and Technology (NOVA FCT)

Rui João Loureiro IIMCB - International Institute for Molecular and Cell Biology in Warsaw

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Sérgio Sousa BioSIM, LAQV/REQUIMTE, Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade do Porto (FMUP)

Tatiana João Carneiro CIBB & CNC- Universidade de Coimbra (UC)

Tomás F. D. Silva Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati (SISSA)

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Welcome Message from the Portuguese Biophysics Society

Fellow Biophysicists,

Welcome to the Biophysics Festival 2025!

The Biophysics Festivals bring together enthusiastic young researchers in the broad field of Biophysics, providing an informal and friendly platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration. Since their inaugural edition, these Festivals have been a prime opportunity to discuss groundbreaking scientific advancements in Biophysics and engage in meaningful social interactions.

The Portuguese Young Biophysicists (PYBphy) group is responsible for organizing these great meetings. This dynamic and resourceful community truly inspires the Portuguese Biophysics community to look forward to these Festivals each year. Thanks to their efforts, the Festival has an exceptional number of sponsors, including the Diamond sponsors IUPAB and BPI – Fundação “la Caixa”.

Nurturing and supporting the next generations of biophysicists has always been a top priority for the Portuguese Biophysical Society (SPBf). Thanks to these festivals, the international visibility of the PYBphy is increasing, inspiring similar initiatives in other countries.

In this fifth edition of the Biophysics Festival, the PYBphy and the local organizing committee have done a fantastic job creating a program of outstanding scientific quality. With 139 registered participants, this year’s program is inspiring for both young and experienced researchers, while offering fantastic opportunities for young biophysicists to share and discuss their exciting research projects.

We expect that the Biophysics Festival will continue to mobilize new scientists to join SPBf and enjoy the many benefits of membership, further promoting Biophysics in Portugal. Don’t miss the chance to be part of this dynamic community!

I wish you a wonderful and productive Biophysics Festival!

Sandra de Macedo Ribeiro

President of the Portuguese Biophysical Society

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Welcome Message from The Organizing Committee

Dear Esteemed Attendees,

On behalf of the Portuguese Young Biophysicists (PYBphy) group, we extend our warmest welcome to you!

We are thrilled to host you at the 5th Meeting of Young Biophysicists – the "Biophysics Festival 2025", taking place at the NOVA School of Science and Technology (NOVA FCT).

The Biophysics Festival aims primarily to promote scientific dissemination in the field of biophysics by providing a platform for knowledge exchange among undergraduate, master's, and PhD students, as well as researchers at various stages of their careers. This conference is designed to foster a professional yet welcoming environment that promotes the exchange of ideas, encourages collaboration, and helps building lasting academic relationships. Beyond research presentations, it is dedicated to strengthening the sense of community within the field of biophysics.

This year, we are pleased to hold the conference at NOVA FCT. We extend our sincere thanks to NOVA FCT for generously providing the venue and for their invaluable support in organizing this event. We are also grateful to UCIBIO for their strong backing, as well as to all our other sponsors whose contributions have made this meeting possible.

A special thanks go to our esteemed speakers and the dedicated Scientific Committee for their commitment and support.

We would also like to thank the Portuguese Biophysics Society, of which PYBphy is proudly a part, for its continued support in promoting biophysics and strengthening our scientific community.

Most of all, thank you to all our participants—your presence brings meaning to this gathering.

We are committed to making this meeting both enriching and memorable for everyone involved.

Warm regards,

The Young Portuguese Biophysicists Group

BIOPHYSICS FESTIVAL – 5th Meeting of Young Biophysicists

8th - 9th May 2025

NOVA School of Science and Technology, Caparica, Portugal

PROGRAM

8th of May

13h00-14h00 – Registration

14h00-14h15 – Opening Session

Dr. Eurico Cabrita, Vice-Dean of Innovation and Research, NOVA FCT

Dr. Pedro Tavares, Representative of the Chemistry Department, NOVA FCT

Dr. Sandra Macedo Ribeiro, President of the Portuguese Biophysical Society, SPBf

M.Sc. Cátia Soares, Representative of the Organizing Committee, PYBphy

Scientific Session 1

Chairs: Dr. Sandra Macedo Ribeiro and Dr. Miguel Castanho

Oral Presentations

14h15-14h35

OP1. UNVEILING THE ROLE OF THE N-TERMINAL AND INTERNAL FUSION PEPTIDES IN SARS-CoV-2 VIRAL ENTRY

Carolina C. Buga - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

OP2. EXPLORING PpcG's DUAL REDOX-BOHR CENTERS: REVOLUTIONIZING ELECTRON TRANSFER IN URANIUM BIOREMEDIATION

Alexandre Almeida - Associate Lab i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, Caparica, Portugal

14h35-14h45 - Q&A Session

Flash Talks

14h45-15h10

FT1. EXPLORING THE MOLECULAR DETERMINANTS INFLUENCING SCAVENGING OF BACTERIAL TOXINS BY EXTRACELLULAR VESICLES

Diogo Gonçalves - iBB-Institute for Bioengineering and Biosciences

FT2. O₂ DAMAGE ON MO/W FORMATE DEHYDROGENASES AND THEIR INNATE PROTECTION MECHANISM

Guilherme Vilela-Alves - UCIBIO, Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit

FT3. MUCIN GLYCODOMAINS RECOGNITION BY IMMUNE-RELATED LECTINS UNVEILED BY NMR SPECTROSCOPY

Cátia O. Soares - UCIBIO, Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit

FT4. UNRAVELING THE MOLECULAR RECOGNITION MECHANISMS OF HUMAN GALECTIN-2 THROUGH NMR

Alejandra Travecedo - CIC bioGUNE, BRTA, Bizkaia Technology Park, 48160, Derio, Spain

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FT5. A HYBRID NMR APPROACH TO STUDY OXIDASE SUBSTRATE BINDING IN DIRECTED EVOLUTION

Maria L. Martins - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

15h10-15h25 - Q&A Session

Plenary Lecture 1

Chair: Dr. Maria João Romão

15h25-16h15 - CRYO-EM, PROTEASOMES AND DRUG DISCOVERY

Professor Paula da Fonseca – University of Glasgow

16h15-17h20 – Group Photo + Coffee-break + Poster Session (Odd numbers)

Scientific Session 2

Chairs: Dr. Miguel Machuqueiro, Dr. Diana Lousa and Dr. Arménio Barbosa

Oral Presentations

17h20-17h50

OP3. MOLECULAR INSIGHTS INTO pH-SENSITIVE REGULATION OF hAQP7

Marta S. P. Batista - BioISI: Biosystems and Integrative Sciences Institute

OP4. AI-DRIVEN ANTIVIRAL DEVELOPMENT: A RAPID RESPONSE FRAMEWORK FOR VIRAL THREATS

Diogo H. Silva - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

OP5. UNRAVELING THE ENERGY BARRIERS AND FUNCTIONAL DYNAMICS OF THE 5₂ KNOT IN UCH-L1

Sara G. F. Ferreira - BioISI: Biosystems and Integrative Sciences Institute

17h50-18h05 - Q&A Session

Flash Talks

18h05-18h45

FT6. COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN OF MONOBODY BINDERS TO TARGET VIRAL THERAPEUTICAL EPITOPES

Pedro Moreira - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

FT7. INTEGRATING MACHINE LEARNING IN PROTEIN TARGET DISCOVERY AND NATURAL PRODUCT OPTIMIZATION

Ana Laura Dias - Research Institute for Medicines (iMed.Ulisboa), Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Lisbon, Portugal

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FT8. INTEGRATING MOLECULAR DYNAMICS INTO COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN OF SARS-CoV-2 SPIKE PROTEIN-TARGETING PROTEINS

Rita I. Teixeira - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

FT9. CANCER WEAPONS AGAINST NEURODEGENERATION

Francisca Afonso - Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa

FT10. AUTOMATED ENZYME DISCOVERY AND ENGINEERING FOR OPTIMIZED METABOLIC PATHWAYS

João P.G. Correia - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

FT11. COMPUTATIONAL INSIGHTS INTO ASP_{2.50} PROTONATION AND GPCR (DE)ACTIVATION PATHWAYS

João Vitorino - BiolSI: Biosystems and Integrative Sciences Institute

FT12. DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MHEASE MUTANTS FOR IMPROVED PET DEGRADATION: A COMBINED *IN SILICO* AND *IN VITRO* STUDY

Constança Ilunga - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

18h45-19h - Q&A Session

19h00-22h00 – “GET TOGETHER” - Biophysics Party

9th of May

Scientific Session 3

Chair: Dr. Sandra Macedo Ribeiro

SPBF Young Biophysicist Prize - Plenary Lecture 2

09h30-09h50 - **POWERING UP: HOW PERIPLASMIC CYTOCHROMES CHARGE MICROBIAL NANOWIRES** CHAIR

Dr. Pilar Portela - Hovione

Oral Presentations

Chairs: Dr. Paula Gameiro and Dr. Mariana Ferreira

09h50-10h20

OP6. SARS-CoV-2 Nsp1: A METAL-REGULATED NUCLEASE WITH DISTINCT FUNCTIONAL DOMAINS

Bruno A. Salgueiro - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

OP7. STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO X-RAY-INDUCED PHOTO-REDUCTION OF ARSENITE OXIDASE: IMPLICATIONS FOR MECHANISM AND BIOSENSOR DESIGN

Filipa Engrola - UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit

OP8. CYTOSOLIC ZINC UNDER HYPOXIC STRESS AT HIPPOCAMPAL CA3 SUBFIELD

João L. Ribeiro-Alves - CNC-UC, Center for Neuroscience and Cell Biology, University of Coimbra, Portugal

10h20-10h35 - Q&A Session

Flash Talks

10h35-10h50

FT13. IN VITRO VALIDATION OF PARPi DERIVATIVES ACTIVITY FOR METASTATIC TRIPLE NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER

Leonardo G. Miranda - Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa

FT14. METALLOENZYMES INVOLVED IN THE INFECTION PROCESS OF *NEISSERIA GONORRHOEAE*

Daniela S. Barreiro - UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon

FT15. TARGETING LYTR-CPSA-PSR PROTEINS FOR DISRUPTION OF BIOFILM FORMATION IN *STREPTOCOCCUS DYSGALACTIAE SUBSP. DYSGALACTIAE* THROUGH VIRTUAL SCREENING AND STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS

João Paquete-Ferreira - UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon

10h50-11h00 - Q&A Session

11h00-12h00 - Coffee-break & Poster Session (Even numbers)

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Scientific Session 4

Chair: Dr. Cláudio M. Soares

IUPAB Plenary Lecture 3

12h00-12h50 - RSV and MED25 reshape antiviral responses

Professor Christina Sizun – ICSN Université Paris- Saclay

12h50-13h00 – IUPAB Pitch Presentation

13h00-14h30 - Lunch break

Scientific Session 5

Chairs: Dr. Marlene Lúcio and Dr. Armindo Salvador

Oral Presentations

14h30-14h50

OP9. EXPLORING SERS AND MACHINE LEARNING FOR STROKE DETECTION: A COST-EFFECTIVE APPROACH

Cristina Freitas - UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit

OP10. DECODING LIQUID-LIQUID PHASE SEPARATION TOWARD MINIMALIST PEPTIDE DESIGN

Joana Calvário - Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa

14h50-15h00 - Q&A Session

Flash Talks

15h00-15h25

FT16. INSIGHTS TOWARDS CUTINASE STABILIZATION: MODELLING INTERACTIONS WITH TRIAZINE-SCAFFOLDED SYNTHETIC AFFINITY LIGANDS

Afonso Coelho - iBB—Institute for Bioengineering and Biosciences

FT17. DFT STUDIES APPLIED TO SUZUKI COUPLING IN PYRROLO[4,3,2-DE]QUINOLINONE DERIVATIVES

Bárbara Bahls - BioISI: Biosystems and Integrative Sciences Institute

FT18. ELECTROCHEMICAL AND FLUORESCENCE ANALYSIS OF 5-FAM INCORPORATED INTO DNA

Marcela Hrušková - Institute of Biophysics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Královopolská 2590/135, CZ-612 00, Brno, Czech Republic

FT19. EXPLORING NEW RADIATION THERAPY APPLICATIONS: TARGETING NEURODEGENERATIVE DISORDERS THROUGH AMYLOID DISRUPTION

Carina Marques Coelho - Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa (FCUL)

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**FT20. TOWARDS NANO-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR MEDICAL IMPLANTS WITH
ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES AND IMPROVED OSTEOINTEGRATION**

João Magueijo - GIMM – Gulbenkian Institute for Molecular Medicine, Lisbon, Portugal

15h25 -15h40 - Q&A Session

15h40 -16h00 - Coffee Break

Scientific Session 5

Chair: Dr. Ana Cecília Roque

UCIBIO Plenary Lecture 4

**16h00-16h50 - FROM NATURE TO THE DRAWING BOARD: DESIGN OF DYNAMIC PROTEIN
ASSEMBLIES**

Dr. Alena Khmelinskaia - LMU Universität, München

16h50-17h00 - Closing Session & Awards

Dr. Ana Cecília Roque, UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit Coordinator

Dr. Sandra Macedo Ribeiro, President of the Portuguese Biophysical Society, SPBf

M.Sc. Cátia Soares, Representative of the Organizing Committee, PYBphy

PLENARY LECTURES

Overview

PL1. CRYO-EM, PROTEASOMES AND DRUG DISCOVERY

[Dr. Paula da Fonseca – University of Glasgow](#)

PL2. POWERING UP: HOW PERIPLASMIC CYTOCHROMES CHARGE MICROBIAL NANOWIRE CHAIR

[Dr. Pilar Portela - Hovione](#)

PL3. RSV AND MED25 RESHAPE ANTIVIRAL RESPONSES

[Dr. Christina Sizun – ICSN Université Paris- Saclay](#)

PL4. FROM NATURE TO THE DRAWING BOARD: DESIGN OF DYNAMIC PROTEIN ASSEMBLIES

[Dr. Alena Khmelinskaia – LMU Universität, München](#)

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Overview

OP1. UNVEILING THE ROLE OF THE N-TERMINAL AND INTERNAL FUSION PEPTIDES IN SARS-CoV-2 VIRAL ENTRY

Carolina C. Buga, Mariana Valério, Marta Alenquer, Maria João Amorim, Miguel A. R. B. Castanho, Cláudio M. Soares, João B. Vicente, Diana Lousa, Ana Salomé Veiga

OP2. EXPLORING PpcG's DUAL REDOX-BOHR CENTERS: REVOLUTIONIZING ELECTRON TRANSFER IN URANIUM BIOREMEDIATION

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Diogo H. Silva, Moreira, Pedro, Parada, Mariana, Conceição, Carlota J., Buga, Carolina C., Miranda, Marta, Oliveira, Christine, Veiga, A.S, Castanho, Miguel, Soares, Cláudio M., Vicente, João B., Lousa, Diana

OP5. UNRAVELING THE ENERGY BARRIERS AND FUNCTIONAL DYNAMICS OF THE 5₂ KNOT IN UCH-L1

Sara G. F. Ferreira, Patrícia F. N. Faísca, Miguel Machuqueiro

OP6. SARS-CoV-2 Nsp1: A METAL-REGULATED NUCLEASE WITH DISTINCT FUNCTIONAL DOMAINS

Bruno A. Salgueiro, Saramago M, Arraiano CM, Matias PM, Matos RG, Moe E, Romão CV

OP7. STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO X-RAY-INDUCED PHOTO-REDUCTION OF ARSENITE OXIDASE: IMPLICATIONS FOR MECHANISM AND BIOSENSOR DESIGN

Filipa Engrola, David von Stetten, Arwen Pearson, Maria João Romão, Gleb Bourenkov, Teresa Santos-Silva

OP8. CYTOSOLIC ZINC UNDER HYPOXIC STRESS AT HIPPOCAMPAL CA3 SUBFIELD

João L. Ribeiro-Alves, Marta S. Sousa, Rosa M. Quinta-Ferreira, M. Emília Quinta-Ferreira, Carlos M. Matias

OP9. EXPLORING SERS AND MACHINE LEARNING FOR STROKE DETECTION: A COST-EFFECTIVE APPROACH

Cristina Freitas, João Eleutério, Gabriela Soares, Maria Enea, Daniela Nunes, Elvira Fortunato, Rodrigo Martins, Hugo Águas, Eulália Pereira, Helena L.A. Vieira, Lúcio Studer Ferreira, Ricardo Franco

OP10. DECODING LIQUID-LIQUID PHASE SEPARATION TOWARD MINIMALIST PEPTIDE DESIGN

Joana Calvário, Diogo Antunes, Rita Cipriano, Ana Pina

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FLASH TALKS

Overview

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Diogo Gonçalves, Ricardo Silva, Nuno Bernardes, Ana M. Azevedo, Carmen Fernandez-Becerra, Sandra N. Pinto, Fábio Fernandes

FT2. O₂ DAMAGE ON MO/W FORMATE DEHYDROGENASES AND THEIR INNATE PROTECTION MECHANISM

Guilherme Vilela-Alves, A.R. Oliveira, R.R. Manuel, A. Viegas, P. Carpentier, C.Léger, V. Fourmond, B. Guigliarelli, I.C. Pereira, M.J. Romão, C. Mota

FT3. MUCIN GLYCODOMAINS RECOGNITION BY IMMUNE-RELATED LECTINS UNVEILED BY NMR SPECTROSCOPY

Cátia O. Soares, S. Grosso, Helena Coelho, Carlos D. L. Lima, Alejandra Travecedo, David Sánchez-Navarro, Irene Ginés Alcober, Ramón-Hurtado Guerrero, Jesús Jiménez-Barbero, June Ereño-Orbea, Filipa Marcelo

FT4. UNRAVELING THE MOLECULAR RECOGNITION MECHANISMS OF HUMAN GALECTIN-2 THROUGH NMR

Alejandra Travecedo, Montana Manselle, Alejandro Cagnoni, Sandra Delgado, Ana Ardá, Gabriel Rabinovich, Jesús Jiménez-Barbero, Ana Gimeno

FT5. A HYBRID NMR APPROACH TO STUDY OXIDASE SUBSTRATE BINDING IN DIRECTED EVOLUTION

Maria L. Martins, Guillem Hernandez, Vânia Brissos, Lígia O. Martins, Tiago N. Cordeiro

FT6. COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN OF MONOBODY BINDERS TO TARGET VIRAL THERAPEUTICAL EPITOPES

Pedro Moreira, Shuhao Xiao, Ye Wei, Joseph Schmidt³, Mariana Parada, Carlota J.B. Conceição, Madalena C. Marques, Carolina C. Buga, Christine Cruz-Oliveira, Marta Miranda, Beatriz Vieira-da-Silva, Marta Alenquer, Maria João Amorim, Miguel Rocha, Manuel N. Melo, Ana S. Veiga, Miguel A.R.B Castanho, Isabel Abreu, João B. Vicente, Bruno E. Correia, Cláudio M. Soares¹, Diana Lousa

FT7. INTEGRATING MACHINE LEARNING IN PROTEIN TARGET DISCOVERY AND NATURAL PRODUCT OPTIMIZATION

Ana Laura Dias, Carlos M. M. Afonso, Gonçalo J. L. Bernardes, Tiago Rodrigues

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Constança Ilunga, Alexandra Balola, Sofia Ferreira, Cláudio M. Soares, Isabel Rocha

FT13. *IN VITRO* VALIDATION OF PARPI DERIVATIVES ACTIVITY FOR METASTATIC TRIPLE NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER

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FT14. METALLOENZYMES INVOLVED IN THE INFECTION PROCESS OF *NEISSERIA GONORRHOEAE*

Daniela S. Barreiro, Marta S. P. Carepo, Margarida M. C. dos Santos, Sofia R. Pauleta

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PLENARY LECTURES

Abstracts

Plenary Lecture 1

PL1. CRYO-EM, PROTEASOMES AND DRUG DISCOVERY

Paula da Fonseca
University of Glasgow, UK

Professor Paula da Fonseca is a Professor of Cryo-Electron Microscopy at the University of Glasgow, and a leader of a research group focused on Structural Biology. Paula graduated in Biochemistry from the Faculdade de Ciências at the Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal, and completed her PhD in Biochemistry at the University of London, UK, based at the Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine. Later, she held postdoctoral positions at the Imperial College School of Medicine and the Institute of Cancer Research in London. In 2013, Paula moved to Cambridge, UK, to establish her own research group at the MRC Laboratory of Molecular Biology. In April 2020, she relocated her group to the University of Glasgow, where she now holds the position of Professor. Paula has specialized in studying regulatory protein complexes, primarily using electron microscopy-based techniques.

Her current research focuses on the structure and function of eukaryotic proteasome complexes, with particular emphasis on understanding the various human proteasome variants. Paula is also exploring the application of high-resolution cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) in drug development. Her work has been instrumental in validating the Plasmodium proteasome as a potential target for antimalarial drugs. The structural insights her lab has provided are now being applied to design Plasmodium proteasome inhibitors with enhanced specificity and potency.

ABSTRACT

Despite the indisputable role of the human 26S proteasome as a fundamental cell regulator, key aspects of its function and regulation are still not fully understood. To address this, we optimised the preparation of human 26S proteasomes in the absence of exogenous nucleotides, breaking one of the dogmas in the field. The functional and cryo-EM analysis of the resulting samples revealed the presence of two distinct proteasome populations and a new level of proteasome regulation by divalent cations. Our findings have implications to our understanding of proteasome function and its deregulation in conditions such as cancer and neurodegeneration. We also explore cryo-EM capabilities, with an emphasis on its use in drug discovery. Our initial cryo-EM structure of the human 20S proteasome, bound to a substrate analogue inhibitor molecule, served as proof of principle that cryo-EM is a realistic tool for structure-based drug design, with its own advantages compared with other methods of structure determination. Within this context, we extended our cryo-EM studies to validate the *Plasmodium falciparum* proteasome as an antimalarial target. High-resolution structural information was needed to identify differences in its active sites, compared with the human complex, that can be used to drive the development of new drugs. Our initial cryo-EM structure of the *Plasmodium* proteasome revealed the molecular basis for ligand specificity towards the parasite proteasome active sites and provided a framework to guide in the improvement of the prototype ligand into a potent new antimalarial. Our most recent data, with a second-generation specific inhibitor and at considerably higher resolution, provided further information to guide drug development, while also revealing unexpected advantages of using cryo-EM in the development of *Plasmodium* proteasome targeting antimalarials. We are now extending these studies to other pathogenic parasites and, as a cryo-EM based lab, to other proteins and protein complexes.

SPBF Young Biophysicist Prize - Plenary Lecture 2

PL2. POWERING UP: HOW PERIPLASMIC CYTOCHROMES CHARGE MICROBIAL NANOWIRES

Pilar C. Portela
Hovione

Pilar C. Portela earned her PhD in Biotechnology from FCT-NOVA, in collaboration with Yale University. Her research focused on the biophysical and structural characterization of multiheme cytochromes using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and she was recognized with a Fulbright Scholarship that enabled part of her work at Yale, culminating in a first-author publication in Nature Communications.

Her projects explored sustainable energy pathways through the investigation of microbial electron transfer in *Geobacter* species. Currently, as an Analytical Scientist at Hovione, Pilar has expanded her scientific interests into innovative analytical approaches in pharmaceutical research, embracing new challenges that bridge traditional biophysical techniques with cutting-edge methodologies in drug development.

ABSTRACT

Did you know that some bacteria can form small “nanowires” that conduct electricity? In my talk, I’ll show how we used a suite of orthogonal techniques—including NMR spectroscopy and electrochemistry—to reveal how periplasmic cytochromes (PpcABCDE) charge these unique structures with electrons. By integrating multiple approaches, we uncovered hidden electron transfer pathways that open up exciting possibilities for sustainable energy applications.

Plenary Lecture 3

PL3. HOW A DUAL INTERACTION BETWEEN RSV NS1 AND MED25 ACID DOMAIN CONTRIBUTES TO RESHAPING ANTIVIRAL RESPONSES.

Christina Sizun
ICSN Université Paris- Saclay

Professor Christina Sizun obtained her PhD in Chemical Physics at the University of Strasbourg where she applied NMR to a variety of samples used for chemical catalysis. Then, she moved to the Max Planck Institute for Biochemistry in Martinsried as a post-doc fellow in the group of Burkhard Bechinger, where she conducted research on membrane peptides and model membranes by solid-state NMR, entering in the field of biophysics. She then did a second post-doc in the group of Erick Dufourc at the European Institute for Chemistry and Biology in Bordeaux on a similar project. Currently, she is a CNRS Research Director at Institut de Chimie des Substances Naturelles at Université Paris-Saclay, where she was accredited to supervise research in 2013. She teaches several courses on NMR and biophysics in master programs in the Université Paris-Saclay and Université Sorbonne and on NMR and structural biology summer schools, and has supervised 8 PhD students since 2005. Christina has also assumed a major role in the French Biophysical Society as vice-president (2015-2017) and board member (2010-2014) as well as in the IUPAB as Treasurer (2022-current). Her research interests focus mostly on the structural characterization of therapeutic targets, using NMR as the main tool to analyse the structure, dynamics and interactions of protein assemblies of biomedical significance at the atomic level. Her research combines NMR data with functional assays to unravel the molecular mechanisms underlying pathogenic processes such as the replication of pathogenic agents, and to design potential drugs. Some of the systems Christina has worked on are the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase complex of the respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) and the complex between the CXCL12 chemokine and the CXCR4 receptor.

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ABSTRACT

Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), responsible for pneumonia in infants, elicits a weak innate immune response. This is partly due to interferon antagonism of the non-structural RSV NS1 protein. It was recently suggested that NS1 could modulate host transcription. We and others showed that NS1 physically interacts with the MED25 subunit of the Mediator, a transcriptional co-activator [1,2,3]. We found that NS1 binds to the MED25-ACID domain, a target of transcription factors (TFs), in particular of TFs involved in the control of the innate immune response. Since, unlike TFs, NS1 lacks a DNA binding domain, modulation of host transcription occurs via a yet unknown mechanism. NS1 is a small protein consisting of a globular core domain and a C-terminal helix α_3 . The latter was suggested to be key for the function of NS1 [2]. We investigated binding of NS1 to MED25 ACD by complementary biophysical techniques, and showed that NS1 α_3 and the core domain act cooperatively to achieve nanomolar affinity. This strong interaction was rationalized by a dual NS1 binding site on MED25 ACID predicted by AlphaFold3, which overlaps with the two canonical binding interfaces of TF transactivation domains (Figure 1). The binding site was validated by NMR and site-directed mutagenesis. Several NS1 mutations resulted in attenuated replication of recombinant rRSV and in increased expression of antiviral interferon-stimulated genes (ISG) in interferon-competent cells. In MED25 knockdown cells, the difference between WT and NS1-mutated rRSV was partially lost, suggesting that RSV uses MED25 to control antiviral responses via the NS1-MED25 ACID complex. The strong interaction and the extended binding surface of NS1 on MED25 ACID provide evidence for a mechanism, where NS1 blocks access of TFs to MED25 ACID, and thereby MED25 mediated transcription active

IUPAB Plenary Lecture 4

PL4. FROM NATURE TO THE DRAWING BOARD: DESIGN OF DYNAMIC PROTEIN ASSEMBLIES

Alena Khmelinskaia
Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich

Prof. Dr. Alena Khmelinskaia, is a leading researcher in biophysical chemistry, specializing in protein design, self-assembly, and biohybrid materials. She is currently a professor at Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich (LMU), where she explores the fundamental principles of protein interactions to design dynamic and adaptive biomaterials.

Prof. Khmelinskaia earned her Ph.D. in Physics from Ludwig Maximilian University, conducting research at the Max Planck Institute of Biochemistry. Following her doctoral studies, she was a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Washington, Institute for Protein Design, where she focused on computational approaches to de novo protein design. In 2021, she was appointed as an Argelander Junior Professor at the University of Bonn, where she led research on computational design of protein self-assembly.

Her work bridges computational design, biophysics, and nanotechnology, with applications ranging from synthetic biology to medical therapeutics. She has authored numerous high-impact publications and has been recognized for her contributions to protein-based biohybrid materials.

Abstract

Recent computational methods have been developed for designing novel protein assemblies with atomic-level accuracy. Yet, when compared to their natural counterparts, the structural and functional space covered by de novo designed assemblies remains limited. I will share with you our ongoing virus-inspired efforts in diversifying the structural repertoire of protein assemblies and developing strategies to dynamically control protein assembly state. First, I will describe our approaches to the design of complex polyhedral geometries, from interlocked architectures assembled from rigid building blocks to the introduction of structural flexibility and the use of quasi-equivalence principles. Then, I will present our recently developed design module for the generation of symmetric or asymmetric oligomers mediated by small molecule-dependent protein-protein interfaces.

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Abstracts

OP1. UNVEILING THE ROLE OF THE N-TERMINAL AND INTERNAL FUSION PEPTIDES IN SARS-CoV-2 VIRAL ENTRY

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Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, fusion peptides, membrane fusion, viral entry.

ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 entry into host cells is mediated by the spike glycoprotein (S-protein), which facilitates fusion of the host and viral membranes. The fusion peptide (FP) is a key domain of the S-protein, known to insert into and disturb the host membrane. Once the FP anchors the virus to the host cell, the S-protein undergoes conformational changes allowing the completion of fusion. Despite its crucial role in viral entry, the region within the S-protein that corresponds to the FP is not yet fully understood. To shed light on this matter, we combined computational and experimental methods to characterize two previously proposed FPs, the N-terminal FP (nFP) and the internal FP (iFP). Our results indicate that the iFP has a stronger affinity for membranes and exhibits higher hydrophobicity compared to the nFP, which tends to localize at the membrane-water interface. Moreover, the iFP causes higher membrane perturbation than the nFP, inducing lipid mixing and lipid vesicle content leakage. Furthermore, engineered spike-pseudotyped lentiviruses containing substitutions on the iFP region are unable to infect cells. These findings suggest that the nFP may play a role in interacting with the membrane more superficially, possibly facilitating the deeper insertion of the iFP into the membrane, where the latter induces a large effect on the membrane properties and promotes membrane fusion. By highlighting the roles of the nFP and iFP in the entry of SARS-CoV-2, our study provides important insights into the virus's fusion mechanism.

OP2. EXPLORING PpcG's DUAL REDOX-BOHR CENTERS: REVOLUTIONIZING ELECTRON TRANSFER IN URANIUM BIOREMEDIATION

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Keywords: *Multiheme Cytochromes, Extracellular Electron Transfer, Functional Characterization.*

ABSTRACT

Multiheme cytochromes are key players in electron transfer processes that support the metabolic versatility of anaerobic bacteria. These proteins enable extracellular respiration by transporting electrons across membranes to electron acceptors in the environment. Among these organisms, *Geotalea uraniireducens* (*Gu*) has attracted attention for its role in uranium bioremediation, where soluble U(VI) is reduced to insoluble U(IV), limiting its mobility in contaminated environments [1].

Previous studies on the triheme cytochromes PpcA and PpcB from *Gu* revealed significant differences compared to their homologs in *Geobacter sulfurreducens*, the model organism for extracellular electron transfer [2]. These cytochromes exhibit less negative and more similar reduction potential values, ensuring efficient uranium reduction. The functional characterization of another member of this family, PpcG, showed that while the reduction potential values of the heme groups are comparable, their modulation by solution pH (redox-Bohr effect) is unprecedented among the family of triheme cytochromes. Using 2D-NMR, the stepwise oxidation of PpcG's hemes from the fully reduced to oxidized state at different pH values was monitored. The chemical shift variations of the heme methyl groups revealed the presence of two distinct redox-Bohr centers that regulate the redox potential of the hemes. These centers introduce an additional layer of electrostatic modulation, highlighting PpcG's role in a complex network of proton-coupled electron transfer events. This mechanism potentially enhances the efficiency of cellular uranium reduction, suggesting a specialized adaptation of PpcG to optimize electron flow in uranium reduction pathways. These findings provide a foundation for engineering mutants to improve bioremediation and bioenergy applications.

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References:

[1] E. S. Shelobolina, H. A. Vrionis, R. H. Findlay, and D. R. Lovley, "Geobacter uraniireducens sp. nov., isolated from subsurface sediment undergoing uranium bioremediation," *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 1075–1078, 2008, doi: 10.1099/ijs.0.65377-0.

[2] A. Almeida, D. L. Turner, M. A. Silva, and C. A. Salgueiro, "New insights in uranium bioremediation by cytochromes of the bacterium *Geotalea uraniireducens*," *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, vol. 301, no. 2, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.jbc.2024.108090.

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OP3. MOLECULAR INSIGHTS INTO pH-SENSITIVE REGULATION OF hAQP7

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Keywords: *aquaporins, CpHMD, protonation.*

ABSTRACT

Aquaporins (AQPs) are responsible for permeating solutes across membranes. They can be divided into two subgroups: classical aquaporins, strictly selective for water, and aquaglyceroporins, which are permeable to water and glycerol. Human aquaglyceroporin 7 (hAQP7) plays a crucial role in adipose tissue metabolism by mediating glycerol efflux for gluconeogenesis in the liver [1]. Notably, AQP7 is pH-sensitive, exhibiting high glycerol permeability at physiological pH (7.4), which decreases by approximately 50% under acidic conditions [2]. However, the molecular basis of this regulation remains unclear.

In this study, we employed Constant-pH Molecular Dynamics (CpHMD) simulations to investigate the behavior of titrable key residues in AQP7 at pH 5.0, 6.2, and 7.4.

Our simulations revealed histidine and glutamate residues inside AQP7 channel pores and vestibules, whose protonation significantly changes, suggesting their relevance in channel dynamics and substrate transport efficiency. Additionally, our results indicate that pH-induced structural rearrangements modulate the hydrophobicity and steric constraints of the permeation pathway, further impacting glycerol flux.

These findings provide molecular-level insights into the pH-dependent regulation of AQP7 and highlight potential mechanisms by which acidity may influence glycerol transport in adipose tissue. A deeper understanding of these regulatory mechanisms could contribute to developing targeted approaches for modulating AQP7 activity in metabolic disorders.

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References: [1] Madeira, A. et al. *Cell Mol Life Sci* 72, 759–771 (2015). [2] Mósca, A. F. et al. *Cells* 7, (2018).

OP4. AI-DRIVEN ANTIVIRAL DEVELOPMENT: A RAPID RESPONSE FRAMEWORK FOR VIRAL THREATS

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Keywords: *Computational Protein Design, Antiviral Development, Pandemic Preparedness, Artificial Intelligence.*

ABSTRACT

COVID-19 highlighted that prevention and preparedness will be crucial to mitigate the impact of future pandemics. Predicting the next outbreak is nearly impossible, making rapid strategies for producing effective therapeutics essential within the first months of an emerging pandemic.

This work demonstrates the use of computational protein design to create de novo proteins targeting viral proteins, using SARS-CoV-2 as a proof of concept. By leveraging AI-driven tools, including RFdiffusion [1], ProteinMPN [2], and AlphaFold 2 [3], combined with physics-based approaches like Rosetta [4] and molecular dynamics simulations, we designed thousands of miniproteins targeting the SARS-CoV-2 Spike receptor-binding domain (RBD) to block viral entry. Initial rounds of design and computational analysis led to a pool of 8 candidates that were produced in *Escherichia coli* with high yields. Biophysical characterization confirmed their stability under extreme thermal conditions. Functionally, a subset of these proteins demonstrated RBD binding and SARS-CoV-2 neutralization. A second design cycle that focused on optimizing the protein-target interface was conducted, significantly improving computational metrics and predicted binding affinity. Of 17 newly produced proteins, all appear to bind to RBD, and 3 showed very promising neutralization results.

This research highlights computational protein design as a powerful tool for rapidly developing therapeutics in response to emerging viral threats. By designing de novo tailor-made proteins, we illustrate a forward-thinking and adaptable strategy for viral preparedness, with the potential for rapid deployment as part of a pandemic response framework.

Acknowledgements: “la Caixa” Foundation, EvaMobs, Protein Modelling Lab and Applied Protein Biochemistry Lab.

References: [1] Watson, J.L. et al., Nature 620, 1089-1100 (2023). [2] Dauparas, J. et al., Science 378, 49-56 (2022). [3] Jumper, J. et al., Nature 596, 583-589 (2021). [4] Leaver-Fay, A. et al., Methods Enzymol 487, 545-574 (2011).

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OP5. UNRAVELING THE ENERGY BARRIERS AND FUNCTIONAL DYNAMICS OF THE 5_2 KNOT IN UCH-L1

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Keywords: *Knotted proteins, UCH-L1, Neurodegenerative diseases, MD simulations, Free Energy Profile*

ABSTRACT

Knotted proteins, characterized by the presence of an open knot in their native fold [1], pose intriguing challenges in understanding protein stability and folding mechanisms. UCH-L1, a monomeric cysteine protease with a 5_2 knot, is essential in the ubiquitin-proteasome system and has also been linked to neurodegenerative disorders [2]. Furthermore, the proximity of its knotted N-terminal tail to the active site raises the possibility that the knot may influence enzymatic activation by modulating stability and conformational flexibility [3].

To investigate this potential role, we developed a computational strategy leveraging steered molecular dynamics to step-wisely untie the knotted structure. By applying targeted forces at specific reference points, we generated a series of intermediate structures that captured distinct stages of the unknotting process. These intermediates were simulated using MD and an umbrella sampling scheme to quantify the energetic barriers, shedding light on the structural constraints imposed by the knotted topology. Additionally, unrestrained MD simulations of a fully unknotted variant, obtained via our steered MD approach, were performed in both apo and holo states to assess the impact of knot removal on protein stability and function. In the holo form, these simulations also provided a more comprehensive view of the knot's potential role in modulating ubiquitin binding. Our findings reveal that, despite being shallow, the knotted conformation is energetically favorable, with a substantial barrier to spontaneous unknotting. Furthermore, UCH-L1's knotting carries a significant energetic cost, suggesting that the knot must form during folding, as the high energy barrier makes late-stage formation unlikely.

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References: [1] W. R. Taylor, A Deeply Knotted Protein Structure and How It Might Fold, *Nature* 406, 916 (2000). [2] Y.-T. C. Lee and S.-T. D. Hsu, Familial Mutations and Post-Translational Modifications of UCH-L1 in Parkinson's Disease and Neurodegenerative Disorders, *Curr. Protein Pept. Sci.* 18, 733 (2017). [3] S. G. F. Ferreira, M. K. Sriramoju, S.-T. D. Hsu, P. F. N. Faísca, M. Machuqueiro, Is there a functional role for the knotted topology in protein UCH-L1?, *J. Chem. Inf. Model.*, 64, 6827 (2024).

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OP6. SARS-CoV-2 Nsp1: A METAL-REGULATED NUCLEASE WITH DISTINCT FUNCTIONAL DOMAINS

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Keywords: RNA/DNA cleavage, Tyrosyl radical, Membrane association.

ABSTRACT

Non-structural protein 1 (Nsp1) is a crucial virulence factor of SARS-CoV-2, known for repressing host translation and promoting viral replication. Our recent data demonstrate that Nsp1 also exhibits metal-dependent nuclease activity, indicating an additional role in viral infection [1,2].

We have characterized the biochemical and biophysical properties of Nsp1 in the presence of divalent metal ions (Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+}) using spectroscopic techniques, enzymatic assays, and structural analysis. Additionally, we generated truncated Nsp1 variants to determine the distinct functional contributions of its N-terminal (NTD) and C-terminal (CTD) domains [1].

Our results indicate that Nsp1 functions as a metal-dependent nuclease, cleaving both RNA and DNA independently of the ribosome. The R124A/K125A variant lacks RNA nuclease activity, but retains DNA cleavage, suggesting distinct binding sites for each substrate [1]. Furthermore, the CTD exhibits catalytic activity, while the NTD is responsible for the nucleotide binding [2]. A tyrosyl radical was detected during nuclease activity, and mutational analysis confirmed Y136 as essential for DNA cleavage. Moreover, the CTD's preference for hydrophobic environments suggests a potential role in membrane association [2].

Overall, our results identify Nsp1 as a novel coronavirus nuclease, with its activity regulated by metal ions. The distinct functional roles of its NTD and CTD provide valuable insights into its mechanism of action, deepening our understanding of SARS-CoV-2 pathogenesis and identifying potential antiviral targets.

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References: [1] Salgueiro BA, Saramago M, Tully MD, et al (2024) SARS-CoV2 Nsp1 is a metal-dependent DNA and RNA endonuclease. *BioMetals*. doi:10.1007/s10534-024-00596-z. [2] Salgueiro BA, Saramago M, Tully MD, et al (2024) SARS-CoV2 Structural function mapping and mechanistic insights of the SARS CoV2 Nsp1. *Protein Science*. doi:10.1002/pro.5228.

OP7. STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO X-RAY-INDUCED PHOTO-REDUCTION OF ARSENITE OXIDASE: IMPLICATIONS FOR MECHANISM AND BIOSENSOR DESIGN

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Keywords: *Arsenite oxidase, X-ray photoreduction, AI limitations, metalloenzymes*

ABSTRACT

Arsenite oxidase (Aio) is a molybdenum enzyme essential for arsenic detoxification and widely studied for biosensor applications. So far, its structural characterization has been limited to artifactually reduced states caused by X-ray photoreduction (e.g. PDB 1g8k, 4aay). This limitation extends to computational predictions, such as AlphaFold cannot reliably model metal-center redox chemistry without experimental benchmarks. Moreover, most structures in the PDB suffer from uncharacterized radiation damage, to which metalloenzymes are particularly sensitive.

We collected high-resolution diffraction data ($<1.5 \text{ \AA}$) of *Alcaligenes faecalis* Aio's oxidized (MoVI) state through an integrated approach using dose-control data sets (100-1000 kGy) at P14 (PETRA III, Germany). In previous experiments, complementary biophysical techniques, like UV-Vis spectroscopy, were attempted to validate redox states correlate to structural and electronic changes.

The low radiation damage structure reveals an asymmetric *cis*-dioxo MoVI geometry – O=Mo=O – which corresponds to the functional oxidized form. Dose increments induce sequential ligand dissociation to form the reduced MoIV state observed in all current PDB entries (Mo=O). The proximal pterin's conformational flexibility – absent in AlphaFold predictions – emerges as critical for electron transfer.

This work provides the first reliable structural reference for Aio's oxidized catalytic state, crucial for assessing X-ray-induced damage and visualization of the initial mechanistic step. Our high-resolution experimental data can enhance AI's predictions of metal-center reactivity, directly impacting (1) biosensor design, (2) database curation, and (3) the development of next-generation prediction tools for redox-active enzymes.

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OP8. CYTOSOLIC ZINC UNDER HYPOXIC STRESS AT HIPPOCAMPAL CA3 SUBFIELD

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Keywords: *Hypoxia, Mitochondria, FAD-linked autofluorescence, Mossy fiber synapses, NG-DCFDA.*

ABSTRACT

Zinc, a highly abundant metallic element in the brain, particularly in glutamatergic presynaptic vesicles of hippocampal mossy fibers, is coreleased with glutamate to modulate synaptic transmission. Zinc influences mitochondrial function and can be either neurotoxic or neuroprotective, depending on its concentration. Given its well-established roles in neuronal function, understanding zinc dynamics in health and disease could provide insights into therapeutic strategies for neurodegenerative diseases. Hypoxia, which is characterized by a reduction in oxygen availability, disrupts zinc homeostasis and may cause neurotoxicity, yet its impact on zinc dynamics remains less understood. This study aims to characterize neuronal zinc changes under hypoxic conditions.

Hippocampal slices from adult female Crl:WI(Han) rats were incubated with the fluorescent zinc probe NG-DCFDA. Zinc signals were obtained by subtracting FAD-linked autofluorescence (measured from indicator-free slices) from the measured fluorescence signals. These were recorded at CA3 mossy fiber synapses, which were chemically stimulated with 20 mM KCl, under normal conditions and with different degrees of hypoxia.

Moderate (40% O₂) and severe (0% O₂) hypoxia led to a slight increase and a significant postsynaptic zinc decrease, respectively, explained by reduced zinc release due to hypoxia. Inhibition of mitochondrial complexes I, III, and IV with rotenone, myxothiazol and sodium azide, respectively, and the blockage of the mitochondrial calcium uniporter with Ru265, reduced postsynaptic cytosolic zinc changes, under severe hypoxia.

The results confirmed that, under severe hypoxia, the measured zinc signals are postsynaptic and originate from presynaptic zinc release. Moreover, mitochondrial activity influences zinc buffering, while ROS-producing structures modulate zinc dynamics.

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OP9. EXPLORING SERS AND MACHINE LEARNING FOR STROKE DETECTION: A COST-EFFECTIVE APPROACH

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Keywords: Stroke, surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS), silver nanostars (AgNS), plasma samples, glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), machine learning (ML)

ABSTRACT

Stroke impacts approximately 12 million people globally each year, making rapid diagnosis critical to prevent fatal outcomes. Current hospital imaging protocols often cause delays in treatment, highlighting the urgent need for portable and rapid point-of-care diagnostic tools.

This study explores a combined approach using Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) and machine learning (ML) for rapid stroke differentiation between ischemic and hemorrhagic. Healthy human plasma spiked with different concentrations of glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), a key biomarker elevated during hemorrhagic stroke, were used for mimicking patient samples. Silver nanostars were used as probes for SERS. For that, plasma samples were incubated with silver nanostars, deposited on an aluminum foil substrate, and the SERS signal was acquired.

SERS spectra exhibited distinct profiles corresponding to GFAP concentrations, which, when combined with ML models improved the accuracy of stroke type classification. This enabled reliable differentiation between ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke while reducing false positives for ischemic cases. Optimized AgNS-plasma interactions and controlled plasma-to-AgNS ratios ensured robust spectral signal detection. The ML model achieved rapid and precise stroke classification within seconds, demonstrating high sensitivity and specificity, highlighting its potential for real-time clinical decision-making.

The SERS-ML approach facilitated rapid and accurate stroke classification, effectively distinguishing between ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke while minimizing false positives. This integrated method offers a promising path toward portable, cost-effective diagnostics, enhancing stroke care and enabling timely intervention in pre-hospital settings.

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OP10. DECODING LIQUID-LIQUID PHASE SEPARATION TOWARD MINIMALIST PEPTIDE DESIGN

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Keywords: *Membraneless Organelles, Liquid-Liquid Phase Separation (LLPS), Intrinsically Disordered Proteins (IDPs), Amino acid Enrichment, Motif discovery, Peptides, Minimalistic peptide design*

ABSTRACT

Liquid-Liquid Phase Separation (LLPS) forms membraneless organelles, enhancing biochemical processes. The stickers-and-spacers model, with its aromatic 'stickers' and polar 'spacers', explains LLPS but is mainly validated in Prion-like RNA Binding Proteins [1,5].

We explore the roles of peptide motifs in LLPS by extending the research to broader protein contexts and functionalities. We developed a novel computational approach for motif discovery and characterization, implemented in 178 phase-separating proteins (PhSePs). Our method was complemented by the FuzDrop and CIDER servers, which identified droplet-promoting regions (DPRs) and examined intrinsic disorder-related characteristics, respectively.

DPRs in PhSePs showed enrichment of Gly, Ser, Pro, and Ala, more polar residues, and fewer hydrophobic/aromatic residues. A comparative analysis of peptide motifs (3-6 residue combinations) between PhSePs and non-PhSePs revealed 129 statistically significant motifs enriched in DPRs, with tetrapeptides prevailing. Key features included glycine-rich sequences punctuated with aromatic, charged, and polar residues, as well as homopeptide repeats, with notable motifs being QQQQ, PPPP, GRGG, GGDR, QQQP, SRGG, YGGG, GGGN. Motif presence and frequency analysis uncovered both widely distributed and highly repetitive motifs contributing to phase separation propensity. Based on these findings, we developed a data-driven approach for a minimalistic peptide design, exploring co-occurrences of motif trios in PhSePs. We designed 8 diverse peptides, incorporating various motif combinations and amino acid distributions.

Our approach bridges a non-biased computational approach with experimental validation, offering insights into the key sequence determinants and mechanisms of phase separation, with the potential for designing minimalistic synthetic condensates with tailored properties, advancing biotechnological and medical applications.

References: [1] De Sancho. *Biophys. J.* 2022. [2] Borchers. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 2021. [3] Boeynaems. *Trends Cell Biol.* 2018. [4] Wang. *Cell.* 2018 [5] Martin. *Science.* 2020

FLASH TALKS

Abstracts

FT1. EXPLORING THE MOLECULAR DETERMINANTS INFLUENCING SCAVENGING OF BACTERIAL TOXINS BY EXTRACELLULAR VESICLES

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Keywords: *Bacterial infection, Extracellular vesicles, S. aureus α -hemolysin, Giant Unilamellar Vesicles*

ABSTRACT

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are small, membrane-bound nanoparticles released by cells that play a role in intercellular communication. They can carry proteins, lipids, nucleic acids, and other molecules, and have been shown to have therapeutic potential in various diseases, including those caused by bacterial infections. These particles were recently recognized as part of the innate immune response to bacterial infection, acting as decoys of bacterial toxins. In this work, our goal was to identify the molecular determinants influencing the efficacy of EVs in inhibiting the toxicity of *S. aureus* alpha hemolysin (Hla).

The cytotoxic activity of commercially available *S. aureus* alpha-hemolysin (Hla) against the L-929 mouse fibroblast cell line was quantified in different cell culture medium. The permeabilizing activity of Hla was assessed directly through a confocal microscopy-based calcein leakage assay confirming the ability of the toxin to induce an increase in cellular permeability at a short time scales. Exosomes were isolated from human cell line sources using weak anion exchange chromatography (AEX) and utilized for evaluation of inhibition potential against Hla cytotoxicity. GUV assays were employed to explore toxin inhibition of EVs and LUVs of different membrane compositions. Hybrid vesicles were also created to test the effectiveness of altering EV membrane composition. Strong inhibition of Hla activity by EVs and hybrid EVs was confirmed. Results validate the potential of EVs in the framework of antivirulence therapeutic strategies in drug-resistant bacterial infections.

FT2. O₂ DAMAGE ON MO/W FORMATE DEHYDROGENASES AND THEIR INNATE PROTECTION MECHANISM

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Keywords: CO₂ reduction, Metal-dependent formate dehydrogenase, O₂ inactivation, X-ray crystallography, Mo/W enzymes

ABSTRACT

The reversible CO₂/formate interconversion by Mo/W-Formate dehydrogenases (Fdhs) is a promising route for green-house gas sequestration and sustainable fuel production. The periplasmic W-FdhAB from *D. vulgaris* is an efficient enzyme for CO₂ reduction [1], being an heterodimer with four [4Fe-4S] and a W ion active site, coordinating two MGDs, a Se(Cys) and S ligand. DvFdhAB is a suitable model for biocatalytic applications due to its robustness and high catalytic activity for CO₂ reduction [2,3]. Mo/W-Fdhs are O₂-sensitive hampering industrial use. Nonetheless, the chemical/structural consequences of O₂ damage are unknown but crucial to devise protection mechanisms. Our biochemical, spectroscopic, and crystallographic studies reveal that O₂ inactivation is promoted by the presence of either substrate and involves forming a new active site species, reproducibly captured in the crystal structures, where the SeCys is displaced from tungsten coordination and replaced by an O₂/H₂O₂ molecule. Furthermore, these results prove that oxidative inactivation does not require Mo/W reduction, as widely assumed, occurring in the oxidized state in the presence of CO₂ [4]. Our team also found that the formation of a conserved disulfide bond [5], reduces enzyme activity and protects DvFdhAB from oxidative inactivation, when transiently exposed to O₂ under physiological concentrations of formate (low μM). Our structural studies disclosed the allosteric mechanism responsible for transducing the signal from the surface exposed disulfide bond to the deeply buried active site [5]. We characterized the O₂ inactivated state of DvFdhAB and disclosed an allosteric mechanism responsible for enzyme activation and O₂ protection.

References: [1] S. da Silva et al., Microbiology. 2013, 159, 1760-9. [2] A.R. Oliveira et al., ACS Catalysis. 2020, 10(6), 3844-56. [3] A.R. Oliveira et al., ACS Chemical Biology. 2022, 17(7), 1901-9. [4] G. Vilela-Alves et al., Chemical Science. 2024, 15, 13090-13101. [5] A.R. Oliveira et al., Nat Chem Biol. 2024, 20, 111-19.

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FT3. MUCIN GLYCODOMAINS RECOGNITION BY IMMUNE-RELATED LECTINS UNVEILED BY NMR SPECTROSCOPY

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Keywords: MUC1 O-glycosylation, tumour-associated glycans, NMR, Lectins

ABSTRACT

Aberrant O-glycosylation of Mucin-1 (MUC1) is a hallmark feature in cancer [1]. In malignancy, MUC1 O-glycans become truncated, due to changes in the expression, location or activity of glycosyltransferases, resulting in new glycan epitopes recognized by lectins [1]. Through this binding event, lectins such as Siglecs, Galectins and MGL, trigger pro-tumour immunological responses and promote metastasis [2]. Therefore, strategies to disrupt these tumour-glycan/lectin interactions are essential to potentially alleviate anti-tumour immunosuppression and reduce metastasis. Herein, short MUC1 O-glycodomains that mimic tumour-associated MUC1, were chemoenzymatically synthesized, yielding products carrying different tumour-associated glycans, specifically the Tn antigen and the sTn antigen, in distinct density schemes. The molecular recognition of these MUC1 O-glycodomains by the lectins Siglec-7 and MGL was investigated using high-resolution NMR, specifically through ¹H, ¹⁵N- and ¹H, ¹³C-HSQC titrations from the perspective of the ¹³C, ¹⁵N-labelled MUC1 O-glycodomains. MGL and Siglec-7 engage the MUC1-4TR O-glycodomains with distinct glycan antigens density. However, they do not exhibit a preference towards a peptide region. The mucin glycodomains can be exploited in future immunological assays for their potential immunomodulatory function. The NMR methodology should be extended to glycan-binding receptors that might have a peptide backbone preference.

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References: [1] D. M. Beckwith & M. Cudic, *Semin. Immunol.*, 2020, 47, 101389. [2] E. Rodríguez, S. T. T. Schettler, & Y. Van Kooyk, *Nat. Rev. Immunol.*, 2018, 18, 204–211.

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FT4. UNRAVELING THE MOLECULAR RECOGNITION MECHANISMS OF HUMAN GALECTIN-2 THROUGH NMR

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Keywords: *Galectin-2, Blood group antigens, NMR*

ABSTRACT

Galectins are a family of β -galactoside-binding proteins that play essential roles in numerous physiological and pathological processes. Among them, Galectin-2 is involved in tissue inflammation, immune regulation, and cell apoptosis.

Galectin-2 has dual, context-dependent effects in disease progression. In certain cancers, such as oral squamous cell carcinoma and breast cancer, its overexpression has been linked to anti-inflammatory properties and improved prognosis. Conversely, in the context of atherosclerosis, blocking Galectin-2 with antibodies has been shown to reduce inflammation and to slow disease progression. Despite these seemingly opposing roles, these findings underscore the potential of Galectin-2 as a therapeutic target, while emphasizing the need for a deeper understanding of its molecular recognition mechanisms. However, the precise details of the interaction between human Galectin-2 and its preferred ligands remain unclear.

This study seeks to address this gap by examining the interaction between Galectin-2 and the histo-blood group antigens, which are known ligands for galectins. Using a combination of STD-NMR, isothermal titration calorimetry, and molecular dynamics simulations, we aim to characterize the molecular recognition of these ligands by Galectin-2 at the atomic level.

The obtained results strongly suggest that the recognition of blood group antigens by galectin-2 shares common features with other galectins, where the central β -Gal moiety serves as key epitope for ligand binding. Moreover, additional decorations in the common β -Gal scaffold of the blood group antigens, such as α -Gal, α -GalNAc and α -L-Fuc, enhance the binding affinity.

Ultimately, these findings will provide valuable insights to guide the rational design of novel therapeutic strategies targeting Galectin-2.

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FT5. A HYBRID NMR APPROACH TO STUDY OXIDASE SUBSTRATE BINDING IN DIRECTED EVOLUTION

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Keywords: *Metallo-oxidases, methionine-rich region, NMR, Substrate Binding, Methionine isotopic labelling*

ABSTRACT

McoA is a hyperthermostable multicopper oxidase from *Aquifex aeolicus* characterized by a highly flexible 29 residue long methionine rich loop (Met loop). The Met loop is spatially located over the T1 Cu site and binding pockets and undergoes through transient open to close transitions that either expose or occlude the T1 Cu site. An evolved variant with enhanced catalysis for ABTS oxidation, a standard model substrate for laccases, was obtained through directed evolution. A hybrid NMR strategy was devised to decouple enzyme substrate interaction from catalysis. We combine Saturation Transfer Difference (STD) with methyl NMR to gain valuable insights into the binding interactions between bulky aromatic substrates and McoA, evolved variant 2F4 and loop truncated variants.

Despite displaying slightly stronger STD effects with 2F4 variant, the binding substrate epitope remains unchanged by the directed evolution. Notably, ABTS binding to 2F4 exhibited increased promiscuity, aligning with improved catalysis. This distinct characteristic can be attributed to the positioning of the Met loop over the active T1 Cu center in this enzyme. Variants with loop truncated demonstrated reduced nonspecific binding. The application of methyl NMR allowed us to scrutinize the direct interaction between the Met loop and the aromatic substrate and identify key interacting residues, providing further insights into the molecular mechanisms governing substrate binding in the evolved enzyme.

This comprehensive NMR strategy contributes to a nuanced understanding of the intricate interplay between enzyme and substrate, paving the way for the targeted evolution of enzymes with improved catalytic properties.

FT6. COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN OF MONOBODY BINDERS TO TARGET VIRAL THERAPEUTICAL EPITOPES

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Keywords: *Monobodies, Computational Protein Design, Viral Therapeutics*

ABSTRACT

Monobodies (Mobs) are synthetic antibody-like miniproteins derived from Human Fibronectin type III. Mobs offer several advantages over monoclonal antibodies, such as the Mob's monomeric assembly and their absence of glycosylation and disulfide bonds. These characteristics allow Mobs to be suitable for bacterial expression, which helps provide a significant economic benefit over antibodies. Mobs have been engineered as therapeutic agents for cancer and viral targets. However, the discovery of Mobs with high binding affinity to a selected epitope usually relies on screening large *in-silico* libraries, a process that is costly and time-consuming. Computational protein design tools can speed up this process, but pipelines capable of designing Mobs as binders remain scarce.

Here, we propose a computational platform to predict Mob binder sequences with expected strong affinity for specific protein targets. We developed a generative pipeline incorporating several state-of-the-art artificial intelligence protein design tools to predict such Mob sequences. Mob designs that present the most promising AlphaFold2 metrics are tested in a wet lab environment.

This protocol was validated by generating a library consisting of one thousand Mob sequences designed for binding affinity to the SARS-CoV-2 Receptor Binding Domain. These sequences were experimentally screened using Yeast Display. Several of these sequences displayed significant affinity signals. Further testing demonstrated that some of these Mobs neutralize viral entry into host cells, with IC50 values in the low μM range.

This research demonstrates the rapid development of antibody-like binders targeting viral epitopes using a validated computational framework.

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FT7. INTEGRATING MACHINE LEARNING IN PROTEIN TARGET DISCOVERY AND NATURAL PRODUCT OPTIMIZATION

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Keywords: *Natural products, Machine learning, Computer-aided drug design, Small molecules*

ABSTRACT

The discovery of novel bioactive small molecules requires navigating unexplored yet biologically relevant chemical spaces [1]. Natural products (NPs) provide unique and diverse scaffolds that often differ from the ones found in synthetic small molecule libraries, making them valuable starting points for hit and lead discovery [2]. However, elucidating their mode of action and identifying molecular targets remains challenging.

In this study, we leveraged machine learning (ML) algorithms to predict potential protein targets for an unexplored alkaloid NP and expanded its chemical library. Our approach incorporated supervised and unsupervised ML models trained on the ChEMBL database (version 31), which contained activity data for 1167 and 2036 protein targets, respectively. We employed CATS2 pharmacophore descriptors and SMILES representations for both fixed-feature learning and deep representation learning. Integrating both ML strategies, we identified a GPCR target hit for the alkaloid NP, demonstrating an IC₅₀ of 10 μM. Furthermore, we applied traditional medicinal chemistry modifications and computer-aided drug design to generate new derivatives, which were synthesized and evaluated against the identified GPCR. This led to the synthesis of new compounds with comparable or enhanced activity against the identified GPCR.

In conclusion, ML-driven target identification enabled the systematic exploration of this unexplored NP, leading to a novel small molecule library and deeper insights into its biological mode of action. This study highlights the transformative role of machine intelligence in medicinal chemistry, leveraging chemical data to drive discovery and innovation.

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References: [1] Nelson A, Karageorgis G. RSC Medicinal Chemistry. 2021;12(3):353-62. [2] Atanasov AG, Zotchev SB, Dirsch VM, the International Natural Product Sciences T, Supuran CT. Nature Reviews Drug Discovery. 2021;20(3):200-16.

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FT8. INTEGRATING MOLECULAR DYNAMICS INTO COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN OF SARS-CoV-2 SPIKE PROTEIN-TARGETING PROTEINS

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Keywords: VFP, Spike Protein, MP, protein design, MD simulations

ABSTRACT

The global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the urgent need for pandemic preparedness strategies to mitigate emerging viral outbreaks. One promising strategy involves targeting viral fusion proteins (VFP) to disrupt infection. In previous work, we implemented a computational framework to design *de novo* tailor-made miniproteins (MP) targeting the Spike protein receptor-binding domain (RBD), leveraging AI and physics-based methods. Here, we emphasize the importance of Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations in complementing the computational protein design, by evaluating the stability and efficacy of the designed MPs.

We selected the top candidate of the *de novo* design campaign and performed large-scale MD simulations to assess its binding to the fully glycosylated Spike protein, providing a realistic representation of the conditions encountered during viral infection. Following the simulation setup, we conduct performance benchmarking and executed the simulations to capture detailed insights into the stability and conformational adaptability of the MP-Spike complex.

By analyzing key interaction metrics from these simulations, we identified the molecular mechanisms underlying binding affinity and structural stability. With our analysis, we observe that MP maintains key interactions with the RBD, indicating binding specificity and stability of the complex.

This study underscores the value of MD simulations in guiding antiviral protein design, offering insights into the MP:Spike dynamic behavior in an aqueous environment, going beyond static structural predictions. This combined approach provides a robust, adaptable strategy to aid the rapid development of effective therapeutics, enhancing our preparedness for future viral pandemics.

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FT9. CANCER WEAPONS AGAINST NEURODEGENERATION

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Keywords: *Neurodegeneration, Proton Therapy, Proton-boron fusion, Amyloid aggregation, Simulations*

ABSTRACT

Neurodegenerative disorders are characterized by the accumulation of toxic amyloid structures. Low-dose radiation therapy has shown potential for treating conditions like peripheral amyloidosis, which shares pathological similarities with neurodegenerative diseases. Recent approaches enhance the effectiveness of proton radiation therapy by incorporating boron compounds, which emit three high-energy alpha particles. We aim to investigate how boron-based compounds, combined with low-dose proton radiation (PR), can reduce amyloid aggregation and decrease their toxicity.

We utilized TOPAS-nBio, a GEANT4-based toolkit, to study the effects of radiation on amyloid structures. We used the "PDB4DNA" extension, which integrates Protein Database Bank biomolecules and simulates radiation-induced bond breaks. We modified this extension to allow the simulation of protein structures. Simulations analyzed amyloid bond breaks induced by ionizing radiation, and simulations of proton-boron reaction were conducted to validate the occurrence and dose enhancement.

Simulations show that proton beam results in more bond breaks in comparison with an electron beam. In addition, results show that proton-boron reaction does not enhance the dose delivered due to the low cross-section value; however, the number of alphas produced in the simulation has increased significantly.

PT is a promising modality for reducing amyloid aggregation compared to other modalities. Despite simulations with proton-boron reaction not showing enhancement in the dose absorbed, the alphas produced with high LET may induce more bond breaks to the amyloid structures. Future work will focus on applying boron to amyloid structures to enhance breakage, with in vitro cell studies and microscopy techniques to verify the effects of PR.

FT10. AUTOMATED ENZYME DISCOVERY AND ENGINEERING FOR OPTIMIZED METABOLIC PATHWAYS

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Keywords: *Enzyme Engineering, Gene Discovery, Metabolic Pathway Optimization, Biocatalysis*

ABSTRACT

Enzymes and microorganisms play a crucial role in catalyzing the production of value-added compounds across diverse industries. However, challenges such as poor protein expression, low catalytic efficiency, co-factor limitations, substrate scarcity, and product toxicity hinder their performance in natural or engineered pathways. Protein engineering offers an effective solution to these limitations by re-designing enzyme catalytic properties to enhance desired reactions and improve metabolic pathways [1-3].

To address these challenges, we developed an automated platform for gene discovery and enzyme engineering. This platform is designed to identify and optimize enzymes that catalyze rate-limiting steps in target pathways for value-added compound production. The objectives range from improving enzyme efficiency to enabling novel catalytic functions beyond those of the wild-type sequence. The platform comprises three major modules: a random mutation generator, an atomistic homology modeler, and a binding energy evaluator. These steps collectively generate mutant enzyme candidates and prioritize those with the highest potential for experimental validation and enzymatic testing.

The platform successfully identifies natural and mutant enzyme variants capable of catalyzing specific reactions. By systematically screening and evaluating enzyme candidates, this approach enhances the efficiency and scope of enzyme engineering strategies.

Experimental validation of multiple case studies confirms the platform's effectiveness in optimizing metabolic pathways [2,3]. This study underscores the potential of automated enzyme engineering approaches to overcome key challenges in biocatalysis, paving the way for more efficient and sustainable production of value-added compounds.

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References: [1] Du, J., Shao, Z., & Zhao, H., *Journal of Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 2011, 38(7), 873–890. [2] Hanko, E. K. R., Correia, J., Souza, C. S., Green, A., Chromy, J., Stoney, R., Yan, C., Takano, E., Lousa, D., Soares, C. M., & Breitling, R., *BMC Research Notes*, 2023, 16(1), 343. [3] Ferreira, S., Balola, A., Sveshnikova, A., Hatzimanikatis, V., Vilaça, P., Maia, P., Rocha, I., *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 2024, 12, 1360740.

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FT11. COMPUTATIONAL INSIGHTS INTO ASP^{2.50} PROTONATION AND GPCR (DE)ACTIVATION PATHWAYS

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Keywords: CpHMD, Protonation, pKa Calculations, Hydration

ABSTRACT

G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) constitute targets for ~35% of approved drugs. Evidence suggests that class-A GPCRs exhibit a conserved (de)activation mechanism, denoted by distinct changes within the residue interaction network [1]. Asp^{2.50} has been suggested as a crucial microswitch for this process; yet its precise role remains incompletely elucidated [2].

pK_a calculations were performed on 100 ns MD trajectories using CHARMM36m, on five different class A GPCRs in active and inactive conformations, and both protonated and deprotonated states of Asp^{2.50}. Macroscopic pK_a value estimates were derived via a Linear Response Approximation framework. CpHMD simulations (250ns) were conducted for selected systems. However, in the inactive state, the low hydration level of the Asp^{2.50} pocket prevented Poisson-Boltzmann from properly assessing solvent accessibility, resulting in artificially high pK_a values.

A 1.3 pK_a shift was observed between active and inactive states in non-constitutive GPCRs, whereas constitutive receptors exhibited negligible or inconsistent shifts (-0.3 to 0.3) [3]. On the other hand, our CpHMD simulations unveiled a possible limitation in the sampling of Asp^{2.50} hydration, and further long MD simulation pre-equilibration runs are needed to ensure accurate solvent exposure and protonation sampling.

Our findings highlight the critical role of hydration in accurately modeling Asp^{2.50} protonation. This study underscores the need for careful system preparation in pK_a and protonation calculations and provides a refined approach for understanding GPCR (de)activation mechanisms. These insights may guide future studies on GPCR function and drug discovery.

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References: 1 - Qingtong et al., 2019, doi:10.7554/eLife.50279; 2 - Ranganathan et al., 2014, doi:10.1021/bi5008723; 3 - Barreto, Vitorino et al., 2024, doi:10.1021/acs.jcim.4c01125

FT12. DESIGN AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MHETASE MUTANTS FOR IMPROVED PET DEGRADATION: A COMBINED *IN SILICO* AND *IN VITRO* STUDY

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Keywords: *MHETase, Protein Engineering, PET Degradation, Molecular Docking, Molecular Dynamics, Protein Solubility*

ABSTRACT

Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) is a durable, chemically inert petroleum-based plastic. Its improper disposal and inefficient recycling pose environmental challenges. Remarkably, two enzymes from *Ideonella sakaiensis* can biodegrade PET: PETase breaks down PET into products like mono-(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (MHET), while MHETase hydrolyzes MHET into the final monomers terephthalic acid (TPA) and ethylene glycol (EG). While PETase has been extensively studied and engineered, MHETase remains largely underexplored. This study addresses this gap by engineering MHETase mutants to improve catalytic efficiency towards MHET and potentially other PET intermediates, and by improving its solubility, a key bottleneck for industrial applications.

An in-house computational pipeline was used to evaluate thousands of MHETase mutants by modifying amino acid residues in its active site, and to select the most promising variants for in vitro validation. Molecular dynamics simulations will be performed to understand how these mutations influence substrate interactions, guiding further optimization. Additionally, machine learning tools AggreProt and MutCompute were used to identify mutations outside the active site to improve MHETase's solubility.

14 promising activity-enhancing variants were selected. In vitro screenings identified four mutants with increased activity against MHET. For solubility enhancement, 5 selected mutants – some were preliminarily suggested by SDS-PAGE to be more soluble – will be quantitatively evaluated using the split-GFP method.

Through this holistic approach, MHETase variants with improved activity against MHET were identified and will be combined with mutations aimed at improving solubility. In the future, optimized MHETase variants, in combination with efficient PETase variants, could significantly enhance PET biodegradation.

FT13. *IN VITRO* VALIDATION OF PARPI DERIVATIVES ACTIVITY FOR METASTATIC TRIPLE NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER

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Keywords: *Triple-negative breast cancer, Brain metastases, Blood-brain barrier, PARP inhibitors, Blood-brain peptide shuttle.*

ABSTRACT

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is an aggressive breast cancer subtype with a poor prognosis, due to the high relapse rate, high metastization capacity (mainly to the lung, bone, and brain), and lack of targeted receptors, making it challenging to treat. Currently, non-specific chemotherapy remains the primary therapeutic approach, although often with limited efficacy. The treatment of TNBC brain metastasis (BM) is even more challenging because the blood-brain barrier (BBB) restricts drug penetration in the Central Nervous System. PARP inhibitors (PARPi), like Olaparib, have shown efficacy against primary tumors, but limited BBB permeability reduces their impact on BM. This study aims to develop PARPi derivatives conjugated to a well-characterized blood-brain peptide shuttle (BBBpS) to enhance brain bioavailability.

The work involved the validation of the activity of Olaparib derivatives with different linker length to further accommodate the BBBpS. After synthesis and purification, the conjugates were tested in three TNBC cell lines with and without BRCA mutation (MDA-MB-231, HCC1937, and HCC1795). Cell viability was assessed by fluorescence spectroscopy.

After a first screening, Olaparib-linker compound 73 (longest linker) was select for the same cancer cell elimination capacity as Olaparib. Compound 73 was then conjugated to a BBBpS, and further validation confirmed the maintenance of cancer cell toxicity.

In conclusion, we developed an optimized Olaparib-BBBpS conjugate that conserves Olaparib activity. By potentially enhancing BBB translocation, this compound holds the promise of contributing to solve an unmet clinical need in the treatment of brain metastases in BC.

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FT14. METALLOENZYMES INVOLVED IN THE INFECTION PROCESS OF *NEISSERIA GONORRHOEAE*

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Keywords: *copper nitrite reductase, c-type cytochromes,*

ABSTRACT

Neisseria gonorrhoeae is the obligate human pathogen responsible for the sexually transmitted disease gonorrhoea.[1] During infection, this pathogen is exposed to oxidative stress induced by the host immune system,[2] such as H₂O₂ and NO, and low levels of O₂ typical of its infection site.[3] Peroxide detoxification is carried out by the periplasmic bacterial peroxidase (BCCP), reported as the first line of defense mechanism.[4] The anaerobic respiration pathway comprises the periplasmic copper nitrite reductase (AniA), that uses NO₂⁻ as an alternative electron acceptor to O₂, and the inner-membrane nitric oxide reductase (NorB) that detoxifies NO.[3] A small periplasmic c-type cytochrome (Cyt_{c2}) has been proposed as the physiological electron donor to BCCP and AniA. In this work, Cyt_{c2} and AniA were heterologously produced in *Escherichia coli* and their spectroscopic, redox and thermostability properties were studied using several biophysical techniques. Cyt_{c2} is a class I, subgroup b c-type cytochrome with a E^o of +150 mV, pH 7.0 and a melting temperature of 59.0 ± 0.1 °C. AniA belongs to the blueish-green copper nitrite reductases, exhibiting a thermostability of 94 ± 2 °C,[5] and a high affinity towards nitrite (~ 4 μM). The ability of Cyt_{c2} to donate electrons to AniA or BCCP was confirmed for the first time by steady-state kinetics and electrochemistry, respectively.

Acknowledgements:

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References: [1] World Health Organization, 2023, Gonorrhoeae (*Neisseria gonorrhoeae* infection) ; [2] Seib, Kate L. *et. al*, *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev.* 2006, 70(2):344-361; [3] Tzeng, Yih-Ling, *et. al*, *Infect. Immun.* 2023, 91(5):e00079-23 ; [4] Barreiro, Daniela S. *et. al*, *Coord Chem Rev.* 2023, 485:215114; [5] Barreiro, Daniela S. *et. al*, *Biomolecules.* 2023, 13(8):1215

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FT15. TARGETING LYTR-CPSA-PSR PROTEINS FOR DISRUPTION OF BIOFILM FORMATION IN *STREPTOCOCCUS DYSGALACTIAE* SUBSP. *DYSGALACTIAE* THROUGH VIRTUAL SCREENING AND STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS

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Keywords: *Bacteria, Biofilms, CWGPs, LCP proteins, Virtual Screening*

Abstract

Cell wall glycopolymers (CWGPs) are essential structural components of the cell wall in Gram-positive bacteria, playing a critical role in bacterial survival and biofilm formation. The final step in CWGP biosynthesis is mediated by the LytR-CpsA-Psr (LCP) family of proteins, which are extracellular. Given their crucial role in biofilm formation, LCP proteins present an attractive target for therapeutic strategies against biofilm-associated infections.

In this study we used a multidisciplinary approach using X-ray crystallography, *in silico* studies, namely molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and virtual screening (VS), ¹H NMR and biological assays.

The crystal structure of the LytR protein was solved at 2.80 Å resolution (PDB ID: 8QTY). Structural analysis showed that it contains a hydrophobic pocket that accommodates the lipidic part of the CWGP precursor. At the top of this pocket is the active site. It contains 4 conserved arginine residues and a Mg²⁺ coordinate site - important for the stabilization of the diphosphate moiety.

MD simulations with the crystal structure showed that the diphosphate is crucial for protein ligand interaction. This allowed using ADP as substrate. The reaction was followed by ¹H NMR by tracking the chemical shift of the H8 of the purine.

VS with the crystal structure identified 10 promising compounds which were validated through MD simulations and MM/GBSA calculations. Notably, these compounds showed highly promising efficacy in biofilm inhibition and eradication assays across the isolates tested.

This study highlights the crystal structure of LytR as a key driver for uncovering its function and therapeutic potential.

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FT16. INSIGHTS TOWARDS CUTINASE STABILIZATION: MODELLING INTERACTIONS WITH TRIAZINE-SCAFFOLDED SYNTHETIC AFFINITY LIGANDS

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Keywords: Molecular docking, triazine scaffold, synthetic affinity ligands, cutinase stabilization

ABSTRACT

The binding of a protein to a specific ligand involves the formation of intermolecular interactions that induce changes in the physicochemical environment around the binding site. Such changes can lead to local rigidification of protein's tertiary structure with positive effects on stability. The stabilization of cutinase from *Fusarium solani pisi* with a triazine-scaffolded synthetic ligand has previously been reported [1]. However, due to limited solubility, the stabilizing ligand had to be attached to a solid support (agarose). Furthermore, the stabilization mechanisms at a molecular level were not fully understood.

The interactions between residues on the surface of cutinase and this previous ligand were investigated using molecular docking methods [2] across different software (*DiffDock*, *LeDock*, *Smina* and *Glide*). Initially, blind docking was conducted to identify potential binding regions for the ligand. Subsequently, a focused docking was carried out on consensus regions to precisely characterize the molecular interactions involved. The ligand was observed to bind to residues Arg20, Lys65 and Gly16 by establishing interactions such as π -cation interactions and hydrogen bonds. These interactions suggest the ligand binds to the region previously characterized to trigger enzyme unfolding.

Additionally, modifications to the triazine core incorporating amino acids, sulfonamides, and PEG moieties were evaluated computationally for their predicted impact on water solubility. Based on these predictions, a new ligand will be synthesized, and its stabilizing efficacy on cutinase assessed through thermostability assays.

References: [1] I.T. Sousa, N.M.T. Lourenço, C.A.M. Afonso, and M.A. Taipa, Protein stabilization with a dipeptide mimic triazine-scaffolded synthetic affinity ligand, *J. Mol. Recognit.* 2013, 26(2) 104–112. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmr.2252>.

[2] N. Aniceto, T.S. Albuquerque, V.D.B. Bonifácio, R. C. Guedes and N. Martinho, Using Machine Learning and Molecular Docking to Leverage Urease Inhibition Data for Virtual Screening, *Internat. J. Mol. Sci.* 2023 24(9) 8180. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijms24098180>

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FT17. DFT STUDIES APPLIED TO SUZUKI COUPLING IN PYRROLO[4,3,2-DE]QUINOLINONE DERIVATIVES

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Keywords: DFT, synthesis, pyrroloquinolinone, Suzuki Coupling,

ABSTRACT

Natural alkaloids containing the pyrrolo[4,3,2-*de*]quinolinone (PQ) scaffold exhibit many biological activities, like cytotoxicity against cancer cell lines and topoisomerase I inhibition [1]. A proposed anticancer mechanism of PQ derivatives involves their binding to G-quadruplex (G4) nucleic acids. G4s are unique secondary structures formed in guanine-rich DNA/RNA sequences, playing crucial roles in gene regulation, replication, and transcription. While numerous small molecules have been developed to selectively target G4s, especially within oncogene promoters [2], none have advanced to clinical use. To address this limitation, novel chemical scaffolds such as PQs must be investigated.

The PQ core was synthesized following the procedure of Yang et. al. [3]. Then, DFT calculations were used to explore the mechanism and reactivity of this scaffold using a simple boronic acid as template and three different solvents: dioxane, dimethoxyethane, and methanol. The reactions were reproduced in small scale and analyzed by HPLC-ESI-MS to validate computational studies. The PQ core was synthesized in 3 steps with a 68% global yield. The reaction mechanism was studied by DFT and the calculated energies of the intermediates and transition states showed that the solvent affect the barriers of the reaction. The reaction mixture's HPLC-MS data showed the formation of the desired product and validated *in silico* predictions.

In silico studies indicated methanol as the best solvent to perform the Suzuki Coupling with pyrrolo[4,3,2-*de*]quinolinone. Preliminary synthetic reactions partially confirm these results; however, methanol can also cause degradation of the products. Therefore, the chosen solvent for these reactions was dimethoxyethane.

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References: 1. Delfourne, E. Analogues of Marine Pyrroloiminoquinone Alkaloids: Synthesis and Antitumor Properties. *Anticancer Agents Med. Chem.* 2008, 8, 910–916. 2. Mendes, E.; Aljnadi, I.M.; Bahls, B.; Victor, B.L.; Paulo, A. Major Achievements in the Design of Quadruplex-Interactive Small Molecules. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)* 2022, 15, 300. 3. Yang, C.; Chen, X.; Tang, T.; He, Z. Annulation Reaction of 3-Acylmethylidene Oxindoles with Huisgen Zwitterions and Its Applications in the Syntheses of Pyrrolo[4,3,2-*de*]Quinolinones and Marine Alkaloids Ammosamides. *Org. Lett.* 2016, 18, 1486–1489.

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FT18. ELECTROCHEMICAL AND FLUORESCENCE ANALYSIS OF 5-FAM INCORPORATED INTO DNA

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Keywords: *Fluorophores, DNA, electrochemistry, fluorescence microscopy, streptavidin magnetic beads.*

ABSTRACT

Nucleic acids are electrochemically active, allowing their electrochemical analysis without the need for labeling. However, DNA labeling is often used in various applications to increase the selectivity and sensitivity of detection. There are various approaches used for DNA labeling, with DNA labels based on electrochemical redox activity being the most widely applied ones. Such labeled DNA can be studied using various electrode materials, including graphite electrodes.

In this study, we tested the possibility to combine electrochemical detection of labeled DNA with its detection using fluorescence microscopy. For this purpose, a fluorophore with known electrochemical behavior, (5-carboxyfluorescein, 5-FAM) (Compton, 1988) was chosen. 5-FAM was incorporated into DNA during primer extension reaction (PEX); instead of natural dCTP, 5-FAM-modified dCTP was used for the reaction. For further analysis, a biotinylated primer was used for the PEX reaction, which enabled subsequent separation of the biotin-labeled PEX products using streptavidin magnetic beads (SMB).

The optimal PEX product:SMB ratio was determined using fluorescence microscopy. This approach also enabled assessment of the amount of fluorophore incorporated into the DNA chain. Additionally, part of the DNA sequence was cleaved using restriction endonucleases at the restriction site, enabling further analysis of the truncated PEX products.

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Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (grant number 23-05688S).

References: Compton, R. G., Mason, D. & Unwin, P. R. The reduction of fluorescein in aqueous solution (at pH 6). A new DISP2 reaction. *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1* 84, 483–489 (1988).

FT19. EXPLORING NEW RADIATION THERAPY APPLICATIONS: TARGETING NEURODEGENERATIVE DISORDERS THROUGH AMYLOID DISRUPTION

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Keywords: *Neurodegenerative diseases, protein aggregation, protein expression, radiation therapy.*

ABSTRACT

Radiation therapy (RT) is a well-established cancer treatment modality and has shown promise in addressing extra-cranial amyloidosis. Emerging evidence suggests its potential in treating amyloid-associated neurodegenerative disorders (ND's) such as Alzheimer's, and Huntington's diseases. Among RT modalities, proton therapy (PT) offers superior depth dose distribution, reduced lateral spread, and minimal scatter, minimizing secondary effects. However, its application in neurodegeneration remains underexplored.

Our multidisciplinary approach combines Monte Carlo (MC) simulations with experimental validation across multiple RT modalities. Gamma, photon, electron, and proton irradiations were performed on cell lines expressing ND-associated proteins. To ensure reproducibility, a custom-designed phantom for biological sample irradiation at clinical facilities was developed and characterized via MC simulations. To perform PT experiments a large-window beam exit and a dosimetric system based on radiochromic films were developed and implemented at CMAM.

Gamma-irradiation demonstrated a dose-dependent reduction in pathological protein expression and aggregation. Photon and electron experiments using a clinical linear accelerator corroborated these findings. Early PT measurements also corroborate the previous findings but at superior dose levels. MC simulations validated the phantom's dosimetric accuracy, enabling standardized biological sample irradiation. The dosimetry system established for PT represents a fast and suitable method to determine the dose delivered to the samples.

Our findings highlight RT's capacity to diminish amyloid aggregates and mutant protein expression. By extending RT beyond oncology, this work lays the foundation for novel therapeutic strategies against ND's. Successful implementation could enhance the versatility of PT facilities and transform treatment paradigms for currently incurable disorders.

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FT20. TOWARDS NANO-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR MEDICAL IMPLANTS WITH ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES AND IMPROVED OSTEOINTEGRATION

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Keywords: Silver nanostars, 1-hydroxyphenazine, antimicrobial coatings, osteogenesis, nanomedicine.

ABSTRACT

The success of medical implants relies, among other factors, on effective osteointegration and resistance to infections, particularly those caused by biofilm-forming pathogens. Prosthetic joint infections (PJI) are a major cause of implant failure, often requiring revision surgeries that impose significant medical and economic burdens. This work aimed to explore the potential of silver nanostars (AgNS) and 1-hydroxyphenazine (HP) as antimicrobial and osteoinductive agents for implant coatings.

AgNS were synthesized via a two-step chemical reduction method and characterized by biophysical techniques (UV-Vis spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy, dynamic light scattering and zeta potential measurements), demonstrating their stable colloidal nature and distinct star-shaped morphology. Antibacterial activity against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was quantified as minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) using the standard microdilution assay.

The antimicrobial potential of HP was evaluated against *K. pneumoniae* ATCC 13883, Gram-negative and clinically relevant PJI-associated bacteria. HP demonstrated significant antibacterial activity, with an experimentally determined minimum inhibitory concentration (eMIC) of 250 μM and a calculated MIC (cMIC) of approximately 106 μM . Additionally, the cytotoxicity and osteogenic potential of AgNS and HP is being assessed using the MG-63 osteoblast-like cell line.

By integrating nanotechnology-based strategies with bioactive compounds, our main goal is to contribute to the development of functionalized implant surfaces that simultaneously prevent infections and enhance bone regeneration, potentially improving the long-term success rates of medical implants, while trying to develop a stable AgNS-HP conjugate to evaluate this synergistic antimicrobial and osteoinductive effects.

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POSTER SESSION

Abstracts

P1. A COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH TO IDENTIFYING NOVEL SMALL-MOLECULE INHIBITORS OF TIGIT FOR CANCER TREATMENT

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Keywords: Cancer, Computer-Aided Drug Design, Small molecules, T cell Immunoglobulin and ITIM Domain (TIGIT)

ABSTRACT

TIGIT, an immune checkpoint protein, is overexpressed in cancer patients and is associated with a poorer prognosis. TIGIT inhibits a co-stimulatory protein, thereby preventing the proper activation of immune cells to eliminate cancer cells. Currently, no TIGIT inhibitors are approved by regulatory agencies [1]. In this study, both structure- (SB) and ligand-based (LB) approaches were employed to identify potential inhibitors. In the SB approach, the Protein Ligand Interaction Profiler software was used to identify key interactions within TIGIT's binding site, specifically involving residues Q56, N58, E60, L65, I68, N70, L73, H76, K82, and Y113. These interactions based the generation of pharmacophore models for each PDB structure. Subsequently, all models were aligned, except for the 3Q0H's, which was also observed to be highly unstable in Molecular Dynamics simulations. For the LB approach, a small dataset of micromolar inhibitors [2] was used to construct various Machine Learning models, including supervised (Random Forest and Decision Trees) for screening DrugBank, as well as unsupervised (Hierarchical Clustering, PCA, and t-SNE). Additionally, the most active compound from the dataset [2] and ZINC1857574521 [3] were used in a similarity-based search within DrugBank and ChEMBL employing Morgan and RDKit fingerprints, as well as chemical descriptors. Similarity was assessed using Tanimoto and Euclidean metrics. In conclusion, this research has elucidated the binding mode of TIGIT and identified potential hits. Future work will involve docking studies to evaluate the binding poses and scores of these hits, advancing the development of a TIGIT inhibitor as a possible cancer treatment.

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References: [1] Sun, J.; Zhang, X.; Xue, L.; Cheng, L.; Zhang, J.; Chen, X.; Shen, Z.; Li, K.; Wang, L.; Huang, C.; et al. Structural Insights into the Unique pH-Responsive Characteristics of the Anti-TIGIT Therapeutic Antibody Ociperlimab. <https://papers.ssrn.com/papers> **2023**. [2] Xiong, F.; Yu, M.; Xu, H.; Zhong, Z.; Li, Z.; Guo, Y.; Zhang, T.; Zeng, Z.; Jin, F.; He, X. Discovery of TIGIT Inhibitors Based on DEL and Machine Learning. *Front. Chem.* **2022**, *10*, 982539. [3] Sasikumar, P.G.N.; Ramachandra, M.; Naremaddepalli, S.S.S.; Chennakrishnareddy, G. Method of Modulating Tigit and Pd-1 Signalling Pathways Using 1,2,4-Oxadiazole Compounds. *World Patent* **2019**.

P2. A MOLECULAR DYNAMICS PROTOCOL TO EVALUATE BINDING AND UNBINDING PHENOMENA OF DRUG:CYCLODEXTRIN COMPLEXES

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Keywords: *Molecular Dynamics, Cyclodextrins, Drug Delivery, Inclusion Complex, Molecular Mechanics/Poisson Boltzmann Surface Area calculations.*

ABSTRACT

Pharmacokinetics plays a significant role in the pharmacological effect of drugs and exploring delivery systems that can improve such properties is paramount for drug development. In this scope, cyclodextrins (CDs) are a group of cyclic oligosaccharides containing a hydrophilic outer surface and a lipophilic central cavity that can form inclusion complexes with several drugs, often improving their aqueous solubility, thus, being suitable vehicles for drug delivery.

In this communication, we highlight how Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations, can be used to study the interactions between drugs and CDs. Three cyclodextrin systems (HP α CD, HP β CD and HP γ CD) are being studied in combination with 39 different drugs. Several analyses have been performed, namely root mean squared deviation (RMSD), deviation of the drug to the center of geometry of the CD, interface area, energy landscapes and Molecular Mechanics/Poisson-Boltzmann Surface Area (MM/PBSA) calculations.

These analyses indicate that often the same drug can bind different sized CDs in completely different poses and binding energy profiles. The MM/PBSA calculations results were compared with experimental data, presenting a moderate correlation between the vacuum (MM) components of the calculation and poor correlation to the solvation (PBSA) components, revealing serious limitations in this approach.

It was possible to conclude that most systems tend to show fewer unbinding events with HP β CD and HP γ CD, compared to the smaller HP α CD, and that although these methods seem to adequately capture the qualitative aspects of binding phenomena, they are very limited for the calculation of binding free energies.

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P3. ADVANCED APTAMER-BASED ELASA AND QCM BIOSENSORS FOR SENSITIVE ACUTE MYELOID LEUKEMIA DETECTION USING THE K19 APTAMER

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Keywords: *Aptamer-based sensors, Acute Myeloid Leukemia, K19 aptamer, ELASA, Quartz Crystal Microbalance*

ABSTRACT

Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML) is an aggressive hematologic malignancy that requires early and accurate detection for improved patient outcomes. Aptamers, such as the AML-specific K19 aptamer, provide a highly specific and stable alternative to antibodies in diagnostic applications.

This study develops two aptamer-based detection platforms: an Enzyme-Linked Aptamer Sorbent Assay (ELASA) for AML biomarker detection in patient samples and a quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) aptasensor for Kasumi-1 cell detection. The K19 aptamer was immobilized on both platforms to enhance specificity. ELASA was optimized for biomarker recognition, while the QCM sensor detected target cells based on mass change upon aptamer binding.

ELASA demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity for AML biomarker detection in complex biological samples. The QCM aptasensor exhibited a low limit of detection (LOD) and strong selectivity for Kasumi-1 cells.

This research highlights the promising future of aptamer-based diagnostics for AML, demonstrating the potential of ELASA and QCM aptasensors with the K19 aptamer as innovative, rapid, and cost-effective detection tools. Their high specificity, sensitivity, and reusability pave the way for advanced, non-invasive diagnostic strategies, bringing aptamer technology closer to clinical application and personalized treatment in hematologic oncology.

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P4. ADVANCING ANTIVIRAL THERAPIES: DESIGN, PRODUCTION, AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MINIPROTEINS TARGETING RSV F PROTEIN

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Keywords: *Respiratory Syncytial Virus, Protein Design, Antivirals, F protein.*

ABSTRACT

Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) is a major cause of acute respiratory infections, which tend to be particularly severe in neonates and older adults. This study focuses on developing novel antiviral therapeutics designed to target the RSV fusion (F) protein, a key mediator of viral entry into host cells.

We used computational methods to *de novo* design miniproteins with optimized binding interfaces for the RSV F protein. The recombinant miniproteins are currently being produced in bacterial expression systems and purified by chromatographic techniques. The miniproteins will be characterized using different biophysical techniques, such as far-UV circular dichroism, differential scanning fluorimetry, dynamic light scattering, and surface plasmon resonance to assess folding, stability, aggregation propensity, and binding affinity to the F protein, respectively.

The computational design yielded 13 miniproteins with excellent computational metrics. The production and purification of the recombinant miniproteins are underway. Biophysical characterization studies will allow ranking the miniproteins according to their stability and binding affinity, enabling the future development of the best hits.

This study presents a robust approach to developing antiviral therapeutics against RSV using computationally designed miniproteins. The production and initial characterization of these miniproteins will provide a foundation for further development of potential RSV treatments. Future work will focus on evaluating the neutralization capacity of the top miniproteins candidates against RSV infection.

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P5. ANTIBIOFILM EFFECT OF CONJUGATED SILVER NANOSTAR-ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDE ON GRAM-POSITIVE AND GRAM-NEGATIVE BACTERIA

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Keywords: Antimicrobial peptides, silver nanostars, antibiofilm, antibacterial, nanoparticles.

ABSTRACT

The discovery and development of antibiotics have significantly reduced the burden of infectious diseases. However, the overuse and misuse of antibiotics in recent years have resulted in antibiotic resistance, compromising their efficacy. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are a class of peptides that have attracted interest due to their significant potential as alternative therapies for infectious diseases. Silver nanoparticles have garnered attention in this field due to their efficacy as antimicrobial agents and have the potential to be used as delivery systems for AMPs, improving their stability and reducing toxicity. Silver nanostars (AgNSs) are particularly advantageous due to their unique shape, which increases surface-to-volume ratio. The aim of this work is to investigate the effect of star-shaped silver nanoparticles conjugated to the synthetic AMP PyAMP1B5 to improve their antibacterial and antibiofilm potential.

To assess the impact of the conjugate, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) assays were conducted with unconjugated AgNSs, PyAMP1B5, and the conjugate, against different strains of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria associated with Prosthetic Joint Infections (PJI). Additionally, biofilm inhibition and eradication assays are ongoing, to evaluate the conjugate's effectiveness in preventing and disrupting biofilms.

Both the peptide and AgNSs show promising MIC values independently, on planktonic cells. Moreover, their conjugate demonstrated higher antibacterial activity against planktonic cells of the tested strains.

The conjugate demonstrated potent antibacterial activity, highlighting its potential as a promising solution for fighting infections associated with resistant and biofilm forming pathogens.

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P6. ASSESSING HYDROGEN PEROXIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE EXTRACELLULAR SPACE OF HUMAN TISSUES.

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Keywords: *hydrogen peroxide, redox signaling, reaction-diffusion modeling.*

ABSTRACT

We are exploring how the concentration and diffusion range of H₂O₂ in the extracellular space (ECS) of tissues depends on the interplay between cellular release rates, membrane permeability, and depletion of intracellular antioxidant pools in various physiological settings. Here, we estimated the maximal H₂O₂ concentrations attained in the ECS near a cell with extreme production rates (fully activated macrophage) and examined the extent to which this depletes the intracellular redox pools.

We modeled H₂O₂ release to the ECS, its diffusion and its permeation into cells where it is cleared by peroxiredoxins, glutathione peroxidases and catalase. We modeled the dynamics of these enzyme systems in each cell by a system of ordinary differential equations, and the diffusion of H₂O₂ using a one-dimensional spherical coordinate system, in which the production is implemented via boundary conditions. We considered $\kappa=0.01-10$ $\mu\text{m/s}$ permeability constants, and a 0.20 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ area-specific H₂O₂ production rate.

For a tissue with cell membrane H₂O₂ permeabilities like those of human cell lines in culture (10 $\mu\text{m/s}$), maximal H₂O₂ concentrations near the macrophage membrane do not exceed 240 nM, which causes negligible depletion of the cellular redox pools. Only in tissues with a 1000-fold lower κ are μM H₂O₂ attainable near the macrophage.

Physiological H₂O₂ concentrations in the extracellular space of tissues are unlikely to attain μM values.

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P7. BIOCHEMICAL AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATION OF CYTOCHROME C₂ INVOLVED IN H₂O₂ DETOXIFICATION IN *NEISSERIA GONORRHOEAE*

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Keywords: gonorrhoea, ROS, bacterial peroxidase, electron transfer complexes, kinetics.

ABSTRACT

The obligatory human pathogen *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* employs a wide array of enzymes and mechanisms to thrive in the human body. Despite its discovery and isolation in 1878, effective long-term treatments remain elusive, primarily due to the emergence of antibiotic resistance [1]. In this context, a promising approach is the structural and biochemical characterization of enzymes involved in the bacterium's defense strategies, such as those responsible for detoxifying H₂O₂, with the ultimate goal of targeting and disrupting these defense mechanisms. To address this challenge, our research focuses on three periplasmic proteins, a bacterial peroxidase (NgBCCP) [2], a small c-type cytochrome (NgCyt_{c2}), and a small blue copper azurin (NgLAz).

We are working to structurally characterize NgCyt_{c2} using NMR spectroscopy. Furthermore, we will investigate the electron transfer complex between NgBCCP and NgCyt_{c2} by steady-state kinetics and molecular docking simulations. Finally, competition studies between the NgCyt_{c2} and NgLAz for NgBCCP will also be performed.

The resonance assignment of NgCyt_{c2} is currently underway. We already demonstrated that NgCyt_{c2} is an electron donor to NgBCCP *in vitro*, and that the interaction is thermodynamically favorable with a transient interface that is likely driven by hydrophobic interactions.

Given that NgBCCP is highly conserved across *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* strains and is located in the periplasm, it presents a promising target for the design of pharmacologically active compounds aimed at combating this opportunistic pathogen.

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References: [1] Unemo, M., *et al.* Gonorrhoea, 2019, *Nature Rev. Disease Primers*, 5, 79. [2] Nóbrega, C.S., *et al.* Biochemical Characterization of Bacterial Cytochrome c Peroxidase from the Human Pathogen *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, 2017, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 171, 108-119.

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P8. BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF CbcS FROM *Geobacter sulfurreducens* - INSIGHTS ON A PUTATIVE NEW PATHWAY FOR EXTRACELLULAR ELECTRON TRANSFER

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Keywords: *Geobacter*, Extracellular electron transfer, Quinone-cytochrome c oxidoreductase complexes, Multiheme cytochromes

ABSTRACT

Electroactive bacteria exchange electrons with the cell exterior in a process designated extracellular electron transfer (EET). A crucial step in this process is the transfer of electrons from the quinone pool to inner membrane-associated quinone-cytochrome c oxidoreductase complexes, which subsequently relay electrons to redox partners in the periplasm. *Geobacter sulfurreducens* is the model organism for these bacteria and its genome codes for six inner membrane oxidoreductase gene clusters [1]. Cbc4 is a quinone-cytochrome c oxidoreductase complex which is composed by a membrane anchored multiheme c-type cytochrome (CbcS), an iron-sulfur protein with four [4Fe-4S] centers (CbcT) and an integral membrane subunit (CbcU). *cbcS* was upregulated in the presence of Fe(III) oxides and downregulated on Mn(IV) oxides. However, *cbcS* deletion does not affect growth, indicating that CbcS is not essential to Fe(III) and Mn(IV) reduction [2].

The cytochrome domain of CbcS was produced in *Escherichia coli*, and structurally and functionally characterized. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy was used to validate the heme core arrangement predicted by AlphaFold, and initial 2D EXchange Spectroscopy revealed that heme IV is the first heme to oxidize. UV-Visible potentiometric redox titrations were conducted to determine the reduction potential of CbcS at different pH and, in the context of the EET pathways of *G. sulfurreducens*, the electron transfer between CbcS and PpcA was monitored by NMR. The findings presented provide new insights into the molecular mechanisms of EET in *G. sulfurreducens*, further elucidating its electron transport pathways towards potential applications in bioelectrochemical technologies.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia through grants 2022.11900.BD (JMAA), UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (UCIBIO), and LA/P/0140/2020 (i4HB).

References: [1] K. Joshi *et al.*, «*Geobacter sulfurreducens* inner membrane cytochrome CbcBA controls electron transfer and growth yield near the energetic limit of respiration», *Mol. Microbiol.*, 116, 1124–1139, 2021. [2] M. Aklujkar *et al.*, «Proteins involved in electron transfer to Fe(III) and Mn(IV) oxides by *Geobacter sulfurreducens* and *Geobacter uraniireducens*», *Microbiology*, 159, 515–535, 2013.

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P9. BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF DIFFERENT VARIANTS OF BACTERIAL PEROXIDASE FROM *NEISSERIA GONORRHOEAE*

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Keywords: *Bacterial peroxidase, hydrogen peroxide, thermostability, activation mechanism*

ABSTRACT

Gonorrhoea is a sexually transmitted infection, being this of great concern because there is still no vaccine. In addition, this bacterium has demonstrated an ability to acquire resistance to the antibiotics already in use.[1]

It is known that, during infection, the immune system produces reactive oxygen species as a form of protection, to attack and eliminate the pathogenic bacteria, thus favoring oxidative stress. However, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* contains protective enzymes, namely bacterial peroxidase. This enzyme is in the periplasm, where it acts as the first line of defense against hydrogen peroxide, reducing it into water and mitigating oxidative damage.[2]

Our work is focused on the biochemical characterization of this enzyme, using various biophysical and spectroscopic techniques. This enzyme requires calcium for maximum activity that also modulates its monomer-dimer equilibrium.[3] To tackle this aspect, we are combining DSC, CD and mass photometry to understand this equilibrium and its effect in the thermostability of this enzyme. The absence of calcium leads to lower stability and the existence of several species in solution, while the presence of calcium leads to steeper folded-unfolded transition (higher enthalpy change).

In addition to the characterization of the calcium ions in the wild-type bacterial peroxidase, we are also biochemically characterizing variants, obtained by site-directed mutagenesis, in key residues proposed to be involved in the catalytic mechanism and electron transfer between the two hemes of this enzyme. These variants have already been obtained and are currently being produced and characterized: activation mechanism (visible spectroscopy), stability and catalytic activity.

Acknowledgements: We thank FCT.IP and MOSBRI for the support.

References: [1] Unemo, M., Seifert, H.S., Hook, E.W. et al. Gonorrhoea. *Nat Rev Dis Primers* 5, 79 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41572-019-0128-6> [2] Barreiro, D. S., Oliveira, R. N. S., & Pauleta, S. R. (2023). Bacterial peroxidases – Multivalent enzymes that enable the use of hydrogen peroxide for microaerobic and anaerobic proliferation. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 485, 215114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2023.215114> [3] Nóbrega, C. S., Carvalho, A. L., Romão, M. J., & Pauleta, S. R. (2023). Structural Characterization of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* Bacterial Peroxidase-Insights into the Catalytic Cycle of Bacterial Peroxidases. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 24(7), 6246. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24076246>

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P10. BIOINFORMATICS ANALYSIS OF SARS-COV2 NSP1: SEQUENCE CONSERVATION AND PHYLOGENETIC INSIGHTS

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Keywords: *Sequence conservation, Domain analysis, Phylogenetics*

ABSTRACT

Non-structural protein 1 (Nsp1) is a highly conserved protein across all Coronaviridae (CoVs), including α - and β -coronaviruses. This protein plays a pivotal role in suppressing immune responses, inhibiting host signaling and transcription, enhancing viral replication and immune evasion, making it a promising therapeutic target.

To gain deeper insights into the evolutionary relationships and sequence conservation of Nsp1 within the Coronaviridae family, we performed a computational biophysics approach to analyze the Nsp1 sequences of α - and β -coronaviruses. Additionally, we evaluated the conservation of specific Nsp1 domains, including the N-terminal domain (NTD), the NTD with loop, the C-terminal domain (CTD), and the CTD with loop, to identify potential evolutionary pressures shaping this protein.

The results aim to provide valuable insights into the evolutionary conservation of Nsp1 highlighting potential conserved regions that may contribute to the multi-functionality across coronaviruses. Understanding the conservation patterns of Nsp1 among coronaviruses will provide valuable information for future studies focusing on therapeutic strategies targeting Nsp1.

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P11. BIOPHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF miRNA-150

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Keywords: *pre-MIR150, G-quadruplex, QUMA-1, Lung cancer.*

ABSTRACT

Elevate expression levels of the MIR150, are associated with various solid cancers, namely lung cancer, one of the most common deadly worldwide. Precursor-microRNAs are an intermediate form of mature microRNA (miRNA) and may serve as potential biomarkers. It has been demonstrated that precursor microRNAs containing a guanine-rich motif can form a stable G-quadruplex (G4) structure, rendering them recognisable by specific molecules, such as small ligands or proteins.

Herein, we studied the properties of a specific parallel G4 structure probe denominated QUMA-1, the formation of an RNA G4 structure in a sequence found in the human precursor pre-MIR150 and its interaction with QUMA-1 by biophysical and *in cell* studies. UV-vis spectroscopy assessed the photophysical and spectroscopic properties of the probe, circular dichroism (CD) and native polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE) evaluated the capability of pre-MIR150 forming G4 structure and CD, fluorescence emission spectroscopy, and confocal microscopy to evaluate miRNA-150 internalization and *in cell* G4 formation.

CD and PAGE experiments showed a possibility of parallel G4 structure formation in KCl and the interaction of miRNA-150 with QUMA-1 demonstrated an effectively stabilized G4 structure formed within pre-MIR150. This resulted in an enhancement in fluorescence, moderate affinity with the K_D value in the micromolar range, and an increase in melting temperature upon forming the complex. Cellular studies also demonstrated a noticeable increase in fluorescence intensity when the ligand was present along with the sequence, showing possible RNA G4 structure formation *in cell*.

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P12. BIOPHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF NOVEL APTAMERS DERIVATIVES OF AS1411

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Keywords: *G-quadruplex, aptamers, AS1411 derivatives; Nucleolin*

ABSTRACT

G-quadruplexes (G4s) are nucleic acid secondary structures with growing relevance as therapeutic targets and cancer biomarkers. The main objective of this study is to investigate the structural behavior and cellular potential of G4 AS1411 derivatives sequences.

The sequences (AS-A2, AS-A2A, AS-A3, AS-A3A) were resuspended and analyzed using different biophysical techniques, including Circular Dichroism (CD), UV-Vis, Isothermal Difference Spectroscopy (IDS), Thermal Difference Spectroscopy (TDS), FRET melting curve (FRET-MC), and ISO-form Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (ISO-FRET), under different ionic conditions (K⁺ buffers). Additionally, confocal microscopy was employed to assess the internalization ability of the sequences via nucleolin. To check if internalization is mediated by this protein, anti-nucleolin antibody was used to block surface-expressed nucleolin by saturating its binding site.

CD spectra indicated partial G4 folding, with low ellipticity values and sequence-dependent spectral variability. Melting profiles lacked sharp transitions, suggesting low thermal stability and heterogeneous conformations. IDS and TDS spectra failed to reveal classical G4 signals, pointing to weak or alternative folding. FRET assays supported incomplete G4 formation. These findings imply that minor changes in sequence or folding conditions can significantly impact G4 stability.

While the tested sequences did not consistently form stable G4s, this work reinforces the sensitivity of G4 folding to chemical context and sequence design. The results provide valuable insights into the rational development of aptamer-based therapeutic tools.

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P13. CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPUTATIONALLY ENGINEERED ANTIBODY MIMETIC PROTEINS AGAINST FLAVIVIRUSES

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Keywords: *Structural Biology, Computational Biology, Flaviviruses, Neutralizing Antibodies*

ABSTRACT

The development of therapeutics against flaviviruses, including zika (ZIKV) and dengue (DENV), requires the design of molecules capable of neutralising the virus and preventing cell infection. Among the known ZIKV epitopes for neutralising antibodies, the fusion loop (FL), located in the envelope (E) protein, is of particular interest since it mediates the first step of cell infection, and is highly conserved among flaviviruses.

Small synthetic proteins were computationally engineered to bind to the ZIKV FL with high affinity. The best candidate was experimentally synthesized (ZVPA3). It comprises the immunogenic region of human neutralizing antibodies grafted into selected scaffold protein cyclophilin.

Structural, biophysical and immunological characterization of ZVPA3 was performed. ZVPA3 binds to its ZIKV target epitope with high affinity (E protein or the whole virus) and shows cross-reactive neutralizing capacity against ZIKV and DENV1,2 *in vitro*. The 3D structure of ZVPA3 was determined by X-ray crystallography to 1.7 Å resolution, it validates the computational design and offers additional insights into the structural basis of flavivirus neutralization targeting the FL envelope protein.

Further neutralization assays are on-going with other flaviviruses, such as yellow fever and Japanese encephalitis viruses. A tag has been fused to ZVPA3 to increase its half-live *in vivo*.

References: Viana et al. *Mol Syst Des Eng* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2ME00170E>

P14. COLLAGEN MIMETIC PEPTIDES REIMAGINED: THE ROLE OF NON-BIASED SEQUENCES IN STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY

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Keywords: *Collagen Mimetic Peptides, Triple Helix, Self-assembly, Aromatic Interactions.*

ABSTRACT

Collagen, the predominant structural protein in animals, provides crucial mechanical support to connective tissues through its triple-helical structure formed by three polyproline II (PPII) polypeptide chains [1]. Collagen mimetic peptides (CMPs), designed with Gly-X-Y repeats, emulate collagen's self-assembly into hierarchical fibers and networks, offering a cost-effective alternative to natural collagen, which is hindered by expensive extraction and complex synthesis [2]. This study introduces a novel CMP (designated PMC-1) that diverges from traditional collagen sequences yet retains self-assembly capabilities via PPII triple-helix formation. Demonstrating structural integrity without canonical motifs, this innovation expands the design flexibility of collagen-like materials, enabling adaptable applications across biomedical and material sciences bioelectronics.

To investigate peptide self-assembly, samples were prepared in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 6 or 8) at concentrations ranging from 1 mM (solubilized PMC-1) to 10 mM (stable gel formation). Structural analyses were performed to characterize the peptide's conformational transitions and identify the key properties driving its self-assembly mechanism.

Circular dichroism spectroscopy confirmed that the PCMC-1 adopts PPII structures, which further assemble into triple helices—consistent with the behavior of conventional CMPs. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy not only validated these structural features but also indicated that aromatic interactions may drive the peptide's supramolecular assembly.

The experimental data demonstrates that this non-canonical peptide sequence retains the structural integrity typical of CMPs. This breakthrough opens new avenues for designing adaptable peptides with tunable properties, broadening their potential applications across diverse scientific disciplines.

References: 1. Engel J. and Bächinger H. P. *Top. Curr. Chem.* 2005; 2. O'Leary L. E. R. et al. *Nat. Chem.* 2011.

P15. COMPUTATIONAL MODEL OF PHOSPHATIDYLINOSITOL PROTONATION: INSIGHTS INTO MEMBRANE AND PROTEIN INTERACTIONS

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Keywords: *Constant pH Molecular Dynamics, Phosphatidylinositol, Protonation*

ABSTRACT

Phosphatidylinositols (PIPs) are ubiquitous signaling molecules, offering various functions, ranging from membrane trafficking to cellular proliferation. Most PIPs, if not all, have distinct biological roles and their metabolisms are tightly controlled. Their structural properties are mainly determined by the characteristics of the polar group, which, at physiological pH, is very negatively charged and has the possibility of establishing strong electrostatic interactions. The global protonation state of PIPs has a large influence on their binding affinities and specificity for certain protein domains, their interaction with other lipids (including PIPs themselves), and with divalent cations.

Constant pH Molecular Dynamics simulations (3x 50 ns), with the CHARMM force field, were performed for different PIPs free in solution and embedded in a POPC lipid bilayer, with a pH ranging from 0 to 9. Titration curves, and respective pK_a values, were obtained through Henderson-Hasselbach or Hill equation fitting.

The results show that the neighboring phosphate negative charges promote the overall protonation, hence increasing the PIPs pK_a values. Moreover, in the lipid bilayer model, we also show the contribution of desolvation on PIPs' protonation, resulting in higher pK_a values compared to the PIPs in solution.

Our model fully captures the effect of the environment on the protonation behavior of PIP molecules. This is an important step towards understanding how the pH affects PIPs' interactions and further comprehending the role of protonation in their binding affinities, which are essential for their diverse functions.

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References: Kooijman, E. E., King, K. E., Gangoda, M., Gericke, A. (2009) *Biochemistry*, 48, 9360

P16. COMPUTATIONAL STUDY OF THE BIOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF A CoCp ANTICANCER AGENT

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Keywords: cobalt, metalodrug, biological membrane, molecular dynamics, quantum mechanics.

ABSTRACT

According to the World Health Organization, 19 million new cases of cancer were diagnosed in 2022, along with 9.7 million deaths reported, with breast cancer being one of the most common [1]. Cisplatin complexes are still being used in chemotherapy, but with multiple secondary effects and promoting multidrug resistance, raising the need for new drugs. Dr. Tânia Morais Lab. has developed and tested several new compounds, including derivatives of $[\text{RuCp}(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{bipy})]^+(\text{TM34})$, which showed promising results [2,3]. Derivatives based on Co(III)Cp compounds showed high cytotoxicity in cancer cell lines, mostly due to ROS production, apoptosis, autophagy induction, and disruption of the mitochondrial membrane. This also increases the potential to substitute other drugs that rely on expensive metals like platinum, gold, or ruthenium [4].

Here, we propose to use Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations to study the interaction between a biological membrane model and a series of CoTM34 derivatives. These compounds needed a detailed parameterization at the Quantum Mechanics (QM) level that relied on structure optimizations and RESP calculations to obtain the atomic partial charges for the force field GROMOS 54A7. We use simple POPC lipid bilayers to study the compounds' partition and preferred orientation in this membrane model.

The QM calculations provided charge sets that are very well aligned with the TM34 compound, already reported in the literature [2,3]. We will also show the partition profiles of the different potential drugs and a direct comparison with their parent reference compound, TM34.

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References: [1] Global cancer burden growing, amidst mounting need for services. [cited 9 Nov 2024]. [2] Franco Machado J, Machuqueiro M, Marques F, Robalo MP, Piedade MFM, Garcia MH, et al. Novel "ruthenium cyclopentadienyl"-peptide conjugate complexes against human FGFR(+) breast cancer. Dalton Trans. 2020;49: 5974-5987. [3] Franco Machado J, Sá M, Pires I, da Silva MT, Marques F, Coelho JAS, et al. Dual FGFR-targeting and pH-activatable ruthenium-peptide conjugates for targeted therapy of breast cancer. Dalton Trans. 2024;53: 7682-7693. [4] Franco Machado J, Cordeiro S, Duarte JN, Costa PJ, Mendes PJ, Garcia MH, et al. Exploiting $\sigma(\text{III})$ -cyclopentadienyl complexes to develop anticancer agents. Inorg Chem. 2024;63: 5783-5804.

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P17. COMPUTER-AIDED DESIGN AND VALIDATION OF NOVEL AFFINITY LIGANDS TOWARDS THE SARS-CoV-2 SPIKE PROTEIN

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Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, spike protein, affinity ligands, de novo design

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the need for the continuous improvement of diagnostics and therapeutics tools, and affinity ligands represent a core component for the capture of antigenic viral proteins, either to prevent infection or to purify them for various purposes. The development of a novel small peptidomimetic affinity ligand towards the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein is herein described as a proof-of-concept [1].

The design involved the use of computational tools to elaborate a 120-ligand combinatorial library modelled based on structures of known strong ligands, simulating the interactions between them and the spike protein [2]. The combinatorial library was then screened both experimentally and *in silico* against spike protein with AutoDock 4.2.6, AutoDock Vina 1.2.0 and MOE 2022.02 using blind docking.

One lead ligand was selected, yielding >95% binding and ca. 64-73% recovery for wild type and BA.5 variant spike protein. When screened against clarified supernatant containing spike protein, the enrichment factor of spike protein after one run was 15. Molecular dynamics and free energy calculations revealed putative interactions, namely salt bridges established through a ligand carboxyl group, along with some hydrophobic interactions and H-bonds.

This methodology was successfully demonstrated for the quick development of high-affinity, inexpensive and sustainable ligands towards any target, and can be used as a rapid-response in future pandemics. This work has been published in [3].

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References: [1] Í. L. Batalha and A. C. A. Roque, *J. Chromatogr. B*, **1031**, 86-93, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jchromb.2016.07.035. [2] C. F. S. Costa, A. J. M. Barbosa, A. M. G. C. Dias and A. C. A. Roque, *Biotechnol. Adv.*, **59**, 107986, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.biotechadv.2022.107986. [3] C. F. S. Costa, I. Lychko, C. M. Natal, A. J. M. Barbosa, A. M. G. C. Dias and A. C. A. Roque, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, **366**, 132778, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.seppur.2025.132778.

P18. DECIPHERING MUCIN O-GLYCAN RECOGNITION: STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO A NOVEL CBM32 FROM *BACTEROIDES CACCAE*

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Keywords: *human gut microbiota, Bacteroides caccae, carbohydrate-binding module, mucin O-glycans, X-ray crystallography, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance.*

ABSTRACT

The gastrointestinal tract harbors a diverse community of commensal bacteria that impacts on human health. In a low-fiber diet, some commensal bacteria can switch from dietary carbohydrates to host mucin O-glycoproteins as alternative substrates. In this context, the commensal *Bacteroides caccae* was implicated in the deconstruction of the colonic mucous layer, increasing susceptibility to pathogen infection and progression of intestinal diseases. During growth of *B. caccae* on mucin O-glycans, an increase of the expression of modular enzymes, including modular M60-like metallopeptidases (also known as mucinases), with appended non-catalytic carbohydrate-binding modules of family 32 (CBM32), is observed. These enzymes are organized in gene clusters, termed polysaccharide utilization loci (PUL), which encode all the genes necessary for the breakdown and uptake of a given glycan.

Herein, we describe our research advancement using an integrative approach to uncover glycan recognition by a novel CBM32 (BC16100-CBM) appended to a putative mucinase of PUL-53.

Analysis using a MUC-1 O-glycopeptide microarray, combined with affinity studies, showed a remarkable specificity towards GalNAc α -Ser/GalNAc α -Thr (Tn antigen). The molecular determinants of Tn-antigen recognition by BC16100-CBM were elucidated combining NMR and X-ray Crystallography.

This data shows the first clues of the molecular mechanism behind the recognition of tumour-associated antigens and utilization of mucin substrates by *B. caccae*.

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P19. DECIPHERING THE INNER-MEMBRANE QUINOL OXIDOREDUCTASE CbcBA REDOX NETWORK: AN INDEPENDENT ELECTRON TRANSFER PATHWAY IN *GEOBACTER*

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Keywords: *Geobacter*, Extracellular electron transfer, Multiheme cytochromes, Protein interactions, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance.

ABSTRACT

Biotechnological applications such as bioremediation, bioenergy production, and microbial electrosynthesis are emerging as sustainable alternatives to conventional industrial practices with significant environmental impact [1]. Enhancing these technologies requires a deeper understanding of extracellular electron transfer (EET), a mechanism that involves electron transfer through a series of redox partners bridging the inner membrane and the extracellular environment.

The CbcBA complex, a quinol:cytochrome *c* oxidoreductase from *Geobacter sulfurreducens*, is essential for the reducing of extracellular metal oxides and electrodes with a redox potential below -210 mV [2]. This complex consists of CbcA, an heptaheme *c*-type cytochrome anchored to the membrane via a C-terminal α -helix, and CbcB, an integral membrane di-heme *b*-type cytochrome. Additionally, CbcC, a periplasmic dodecaheme cytochrome from the same gene cluster, is proposed to function as a redox partner in this electron transfer pathway.

To investigate their structural and functional properties, the periplasmic domains of CbcA (37 kDa) and CbcC (41 kDa) were heterologously expressed in *E. coli* and analyzed using complementary spectroscopic techniques. The crystal structure of CbcA was solved at 1.9 Å resolution, revealing unique structural features. Circular dichroism analysis indicated that both proteins exhibit high stability, while potentiometric redox titrations demonstrated distinct electrochemical behaviors: CbcA has the most negative reduction potential among *G. sulfurreducens* inner-membrane oxidoreductases, whereas CbcC operates within the redox potential range of the PpcA-family cytochromes. Moreover, NMR studies confirmed electron transfer interactions between CbcA and CbcC, and between CbcA and the PpcA-family, providing deeper insights into the EET networks of *G. sulfurreducens*.

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References:

[1] Kumar R et al. (2015) Int J Energy Res 39, 1048–1067. [2] Joshi K et al. (2021) Mol Microbiol 116, 1124–1139

P20. DESIGN OF ANTIVIRAL BIOLOGICS TARGETING ZIKA VIRUS ENVELOPE PROTEIN

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Keywords: *Zika Virus, Antivirals, Protein Design, Molecular Dynamics, Miniproteins.*

ABSTRACT

Zika virus (ZIKV) can cause Guillain-Barré Syndrome in adults and microcephaly in fetuses, with no approved vaccines or antivirals available. ZIKV's envelope (E) protein is a promising accessible target for neutralizing therapies. The E protein has three domains: Domain I shields the fusion loop, Domain II contains the fusion loop, that is essential for viral fusion with cellular membranes, and Domain III interacts with cellular receptors. This study aims to develop antiviral biologics for ZIKV by using advanced computational tools to design miniproteins for multiple domains of the E protein.

Several target-binder backbone structures were generated using RFdiffusion. ProteinMPNN, an inverse folding model, was used to attribute sequences to each backbone. Promising results were selected based on AlphaFold predictions and biophysical metrics. Designs were filtered to remove unstable and unbinding structures, followed by refinement steps using ProteinMPNN to increase affinity in the interface region. Molecular dynamic simulations assessed the stability of the miniprotein and the target-binder complex.

Designed miniproteins are negatively charged helix bundles with 70-100 amino acids. Sixteen miniproteins were designed for ZIKV structural protein E: four targeting Domain III and twelve targeting Domain II.

This study demonstrates the successful application of computational tools to design miniproteins targeting multiple epitopes on the ZIKV E protein. The designed miniproteins show promising biophysical properties, paving the way for experimental validation. These findings could contribute significantly to the development of effective antiviral therapies against ZIKV, addressing an unmet medical need.

P21. DESIGN, PRODUCTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ANTIVIRAL BIOLOGICS TO COMBAT INFLUENZA A VIRUS

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Keywords: *Hemagglutinin, monobody, computational methods, confidence metrics, MD simulations.*

ABSTRACT

The emergence of viral pandemics highlights the need for preparedness. Influenza, a virus with high pandemic potential, relies on hemagglutinin (HA) to invade host cells. HA is a homotrimeric glycoprotein that promotes fusion of viral and host endosome membranes, making it a privileged target for antivirals. This project developed Monobodies (Mobs), small and stable proteins derived from fibronectin type III domain, capable of binding to HA and blocking viral entry.

Mobs were computationally designed using two strategies: the ‘grafting’ strategy, where a stable Mob was grafted with segments of loops from an antibody against HA; and the ‘library’ strategy, where a large pool of Mob and Mob-like motifs were selected and docked onto an epitope using MaSIF¹. In both strategies, the binding loops were subsequently re-designed to increase binding affinity using ProteinMPNN², and computational metrics were used to filter the results using AlphaFold2^{3,4} and Rosetta Interface Analysis. Molecular dynamics simulations confirmed structural stability. Experimental characterization assessed thermal stability and aggregation profiles. Far-UV circular dichroism (CD) verified β -sheet structures across all designs. Functional characterization was estimated by binding affinity assays using fluidics-free surface plasmon resonance.

Some designs showed promising confidence metrics scores, including shape complementarity, interface-predicted template modeling score, and unsatisfied hydrogen bonds in the interface. The designs exhibited different degrees of thermal stability and aggregation profiles. Five Mobs appeared to interact with HA, four of which are particularly stable.

This work contributes to developing and validating an innovative strategy that can be applied to tackle various viruses, including influenza A.

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References: [1] Gainza, P. et al. (2020). *Nat Methods* 17; [2] Dauparas, J. et al (2022). *Science*; [3] Roney, J. P. et al (2022); *Phys Rev Lett*; [4] Jumper, J. et al (2021). *Nature*.

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P22. DEVELOPMENT OF MODIFIED APTAMERS TARGETING EPHRIN RECEPTOR TYROSINE KINASE A2 (EPHA2) IN GLIOBLASTOMA STEM CELLS

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Keywords: RNA aptamers, SELEX, ephrin type-A receptor 2, biophysical techniques, thermal stability.

ABSTRACT

DNA and RNA aptamers are short synthetic nucleic acids able to adopt distinctive three-dimensional structures. These structures allow aptamers to bind, with high affinity and specificity, to a wide variety of molecular targets, including small molecules, proteins, nucleic acids, as well as cells and tissues [1]. Besides DNA aptamers, the outstanding therapeutic potential of the RNA aptamers should be highlighted, which as DNA aptamers can be identified through in vitro selection techniques, such as SELEX (Systematic Evolution of Ligands by Exponential Enrichment) [2]. In 2019, Condorelli's group identified an RNA aptamer, namely A40s, a 30-mer oligonucleotide containing 2'-F-ribo residues, capable of binding the cell surface of human glioblastoma stem cells (GSCs) through direct recognition of the ephrin type-A receptor 2 (EphA2) [3,4]. The physicochemical properties of the aptamer A40s were analyzed using several biophysical techniques (CD, UV, TDS, DSC and SVD). Furthermore, various modified analogues of A40s were designed and synthesized with the aim of developing aptamers with improved thermal stability, enhanced nuclease resistance in serum and efficiency in binding EphA2 compared to A40s. The preliminary results indicate that the selected modifications markedly improved not only the aptamer's thermal stability but also nuclease resistance in serum and binding efficiency to EphA2. This paves the way for the development of novel systems characteristics suitable and appropriate for future clinical applications.

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References: [1] Ali MH et al. Int. J. Mol. Sci. 20 (2019) 2511. [2] Ulrich H et al. Comb Chem High Throughput Screen. 9 (2006) 619-32. [3] Affinito A. et al. Ann. Oncol. 30 (2019) v802. [4] Affinito A. et al. Mol Ther Nucleic Acids 20 (2020) 176-185.

P23. DYNAMIC INTERACTION OF *E. COLI* DI-IRON YTFE WITH PROTEINS INVOLVED IN THE FORMATION OF IRON-SULFUR CENTRES

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Keywords: *Di-iron protein, Fe-S biogenesis, ISC system, SAXS, NMR.*

ABSTRACT

Iron-sulfur (Fe-S) proteins have essential functions in all organisms, from bacteria to humans. The biogenesis of Fe-S clusters requires complex machineries that in bacteria are represented by the ISC, SUF and NIF systems [1].

Escherichia coli YtfE is a di-iron protein with homologous widely spread in the pathogens [2][3][4]. *E. coli* YtfE is a L-shaped protein of 25 kDa, consisting of a four helix bundle with a hemerythrin-like domain that contains the di-iron centre coordinated by highly conserved histidines and glutamates. YtfE has the capacity to donate the iron the Iron Sulfur Cluster (ISC) system for the assembly of the *novo* Fe-S clusters, as well as to restore the activity of the damaged Fe-S proteins [5][6][7].

The interactions between YtfE and the proteins of the ISC system, namely the cysteine desulfurase IscS and the scaffold protein IscU, have been shown [8]. In this work we provide the structural basis of the YtfE-IscU-IscS complex. We resorted to 2D NMR experiment to titrate apo-YtfE with N15-labelled IscU. Preliminary data allowed us to identify the key residues of IscU that interact with YtfE. Furthermore, we isolated the complex IscS-IscU-YtfE and analysed it by X-ray scattering (SAXS). These results are herein presented and discussed.

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References: [1] Blanc B, et al. *Biochim Biophys Acta- Mol Cell Res.* 2015;1853(6): 1436-47. [2] Justino MC et al. *J Biol Chem.* 2007;282(14):10352-9. [3] Overton TW et al. *J Bacteriol.* 2088;190(6):2004-13. [4] Nobre LS et al. *Protist.* 2016;167(3):222-33. [5] Nobre LS, et al. *PLoS ONE* 2014; 9(4): e95222. [6] Nobre LS et al. *FEBS Lett.* 2015;589(4):426-31. [7] Silva LSO et al. *Molecules.* 2022 Jun 23;27(13):4051. [8] Silva LSO et al. *Front Microbiol.* 2021; 12:670681.

P24. EFFECT OF RADIATION ON PATHOLOGICAL PROTEIN AMYLOIDS: PILOT LIVE-CELL STUDIES IN NEW MODELS OF HUNTINGTON'S DISEASE

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Keywords: *radiation therapy, hormesis, neurodegeneration, pathological protein aggregation, Huntington's disease.*

ABSTRACT

Neurodegenerative disorders (NDDs) are a heterogeneous group of neurological diseases affecting millions worldwide and lacking disease-modifying treatments. A key pathological hallmark common to many NDDs and considered an important contributor to disease progression is the aggregation of misfolded proteins in amyloid structures. Radiation therapy (RT) exhibits a hormetic nature, inducing beneficial effects at low doses. It is used to treat extracranial amyloidosis conditions, which involve the deposition of toxic beta-sheet fibrillar protein aggregates in different tissues, structurally similar to those in NDDs. However, RT's effects on the brain and NDDs remain poorly understood.

We aim to explore RT's potential as a treatment for NDDs by studying its effects on new human and bacterial Huntington's disease models, where exon 1 of mutant Huntingtin protein aggregates and produces pathological phenotypes. Using CRISPR/Cas9 technology, we will insert mutant Huntingtin exon 1 fused with a reporter protein into human and *Deinococcus radiodurans* bacterium genomes. These models will be then subjected to several sources and doses of radiation (e.g. electrons and photons), followed by comprehensive analysis of radiation-induced alterations at cellular and protein levels.

Preliminary tests on HeLa cells transiently expressing mutant HTT showed a significant increase in the number of cells exhibiting HTT aggregates following irradiation compared to non-irradiated cells. No significant increases in HTT expression were observed in irradiated cells.

These findings suggest that ionizing radiation may promote the formation of larger huntingtin aggregates by assembling pre-existing smaller oligomers, rather than increasing huntingtin expression, potentially altering HTT aggregation kinetics.

P25. ENGINEERING AN ANTI-AQP9 scFv LIBRARY: A TARGETED APPROACH TO MODULATE INFLAMMATION

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Keywords: Aquaporins, Biologics, Inflammatory Diseases, Inflammation, Targeted-Therapy.

ABSTRACT

The immune cells' ability to shift shape for motility, phagocytosis or antigen uptake is supported by crucial proteins, such as aquaporins (AQPs). AQPs are crucial for volume changes regulation. AQP3 and AQP9 are water/glycerol/H₂O₂ channels highly expressed in macrophages and neutrophils, respectively. Recently, we investigated the role of AQP3 macrophage priming and NLRP3-inflammasome activation in THP1 cells. AQP3-silencing by shRNA or blockage by Auphen, resulted in LPS-priming blockage and deficient NLRP3-inflammasome activation, unveiling AQPs as potential targets to treat inflammatory diseases. Here, we develop an AQP9 pore-directed single-chain variable fragment (scFv) to block AQP-driven fluxes and prevent inflammation.

A peptide corresponding to an external loop near the entrance of AQP9 pore was synthesized and used to immunize rabbits. After 2 months, rabbits were euthanized, and spleen (S) and bone marrow (BM) cells were collected to isolate RNA. Corresponding cDNA was used to amplify variable domain of the immunoglobulin heavy chain (VH) and light chain (VL) gene segments using pre-designed primers to be posteriorly combined using short or long linkers to achieve a scFvs anti-AQP9 library.

Rabbits immunization resulted in amplifications of VH and VL in spleens (2 and 28, respectively) and bone marrow (3 and 13, respectively) cDNA. Purified VH and VL fragments were subsequently combined using different length linker strategies resulting in 56 and 52 combinations of scFv in spleen and bone marrow, respectively, to construct an anti-AQP9 scFv library.

This scFv-library provides a valuable foundation for developing AQP9-targeting therapeutics, offering novel strategies to modulate inflammation.

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P26. ENGINEERING ATP-RESPONSIVE PEPTIDE-BASED PROTOCELLS

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Keywords: *Liquid-liquid phase separation, Complex coacervates, ATP hydrolysis, Out-of-equilibrium protocells.*

ABSTRACT

Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) serves as both a chemical signal and molecular fuel in cells, exemplified by its role in actin filament dynamics. ATP binding induces polymerization, while hydrolysis catalyzes depolymerization, creating an out-of-equilibrium state until ATP is depleted. Coacervates, membraneless droplets formed via liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS), are believed to have played a pivotal role as protocells during the origin of life. They selectively concentrate molecules, enhancing reaction rates through compartmentalization. Designing ATP-based coacervates allows for dynamic, functional systems that mimic out-of-equilibrium protocells.

Coacervate formation was achieved by mixing the P29 peptide solution and ATP in 15mM and 5mM, respectively. UV-visible spectroscopy was employed to monitor ATP hydrolysis over five days by tracking inorganic phosphate (Pi) levels in the presence and absence of P29-ATP coacervates. Confocal microscopy experiments were conducted to investigate the mechanism of coacervation, while fluorescence recovery after photobleaching (FRAP) was used to confirm the liquid-like nature of the coacervates.

We report the formation of dynamic condensates through the associative LLPS of the peptide P29 (KDFLPSPQTAW) with ATP. After four days, a significant increase in inorganic phosphate (pi) concentration was observed, suggesting accelerated ATP hydrolysis. Surprisingly, these coacervates showed motility and formed elongated structures after 4 days.

We hypothesize that the observed motion is due to the energy released during ATP hydrolysis, and the emergence of elongated structures is attributable to the ATP responsiveness of these coacervates. This study opens avenues for the creation of complex systems with diverse functionalities.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., through MOSTMICRO-ITQB R&D Unit (UIDB/04612/2020, UIDP/04612/2020) and LS4FUTURE Associated Laboratory (LA/P/0087/2020).

P27. ENSEMBLIFY: A USER-FRIENDLY TOOL FOR GENERATING ENSEMBLES OF INTRINSICALLY DISORDERED REGIONS OF ALPHAFOLD OR USER DEFINED MODELS

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Keywords: *Intrinsically disordered proteins, Conformational ensembles, Structural database sampling, AlphaFold.*

ABSTRACT

AlphaFold [1] has emerged as a groundbreaking innovation that predicts protein structures with atomic-level precision [2]. Despite its immense success, AlphaFold struggles with predicting the structure of multi-domain and intrinsically disordered proteins [3] since these are better represented by structural ensembles that describe the accessible conformational space rather than a single structure. The current state-of-the-art offers low-confidence metrics for these proteins, hindering our understanding of their structure and function.

Our tool leverages the PyRosetta Python interface [4] and implements a Metropolis Monte Carlo algorithm to explore protein conformational space. Dihedral angle values are sampled from a tripeptide database built from intrinsically disordered regions. Secondary structure biases can be defined, and conformational sampling can be customized according to AlphaFold confidence metrics.

Ensemblify is a user-friendly tool for generating conformational ensembles for low-confidence regions of AlphaFold or user-defined models. Ensembles can be reweighted using SAXS experimental data, and structural metric analysis is available through an interactive graphical dashboard. A user-friendly HTML interface is provided to assist in generating the required input parameters file. Ensemblify functions as a Command Line Interface tool or as a Python library.

We introduce Ensemblify, a robust computational framework for generating protein conformational ensembles that is versatile, fast, and accessible. It accommodates diverse structural architectures, realistically samples secondary structure propensities in disordered regions, and leverages AlphaFold confidence metrics for dynamic insights. Featuring comprehensive documentation and integrative analysis tools, it integrates experimental validation with ensemble generation, supporting both research and educational applications.

References: [1] Jumper J et al. Nature. 2021 Aug;596(7873):583–9.; [2] Kryshchuk A et al. Proteins. 2021 Dec;89(12):1607–17.; [3] Elofsson A. Curr Opin Struct Biol. 2023 Apr 13;80:102594.; [4] Chaudhury S et al. Bioinformatics. 2010 Mar 1;26(5):689–91.

P28. EXPLORING NEW PEPTIDE-BASED CONSTRUCTS FOR WOUND HEALING: BIOPHYSICAL AND MICROSCOPIC INSIGHTS

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Keywords: Antimicrobial peptides, liposomes, bacterial membrane, chronic wounds.

ABSTRACT

Chronic wounds are associated with a prolonged inflammatory phase of the wound healing process, usually triggering collagen destruction. These wounds are quite liable to infection by bacteria, commonly related to antimicrobial resistance. Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) have been widely explored as alternatives to conventional antibiotics, due to their broad spectrum of action at very low concentrations and to the lower chances of antimicrobial resistance development [1]. Gomes *et al.* designed peptide-based constructs, by combining an AMP (3.1, with amino acid sequence KKLLKWLLKLL) with a collagen-boosting peptide (CBP) (PP4, with amino acid sequence KTTKS). Peptides 3.1-PP4 and its isomer PP4-3.1 combine antimicrobial action and faster healing, being promising for the treatment of infected wounds [2, 3].

In this work, we combine biophysical and microscopic techniques (fluorescence spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering, confocal laser scanning microscopy and atomic force microscopy experiments) to clarify the peptide-bacterial membrane interactions and unveil their mechanism of action (MOA) against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, using mimetic model systems (large and giant unilamellar vesicles) and bacterial susceptible strains (*E. coli* ATCC 25922 and *S. aureus* ATCC 29213).

The results revealed different effects resultant from the action of 3.1-PP4 and PP4-3.1 in bacterial membranes, suggesting a different MOA.

The combination of AMPs with CBPs revealed to be a promising strategy to treat chronic wounds.

Acknowledgements: This work received financial support from the PT national funds (FCT/MECI, Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia and Ministério da Educação, Ciência e Inovação) through the project UID/50006 -Laboratório Associado para a Química Verde - Tecnologias e Processos Limpos. MF thanks FCT and REQUIMTE-LAQV for a post-doc fellowship (REQUIMTE 2019-34). AG and CN thank FCT for funding through the Scientific Employment Stimulus - Individual Call (AG: 2022.08044.CEECIND/CP1724/CT0004; and CN: 2022.05608.CEECIND/CP1724/CT0002).

References: [1] Moretta, A. *et al.*, *Front. Cell Infect. Microbiol.* **11** (2021): 668632. [2] Gomes, A. *et al.* *Front. Microbiol.* **10** (2019): 1915. [3] Gomes, A. *et al.*, *Pharmaceutics* **13** (2021) 11: 1962.

P29. EXPLORING SILVER NANOSTARS AS ANTIBACTERIAL AGENTS AGAINST *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS*

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Keywords: *Silver nanostars, Metal nanoparticles, Antibacterial, Antibiofilm, Nanomedicine.*

ABSTRACT

The alarming rise of multidrug-resistant bacteria has prompted the development of novel antimicrobial solutions¹. Among those, silver nanoparticles (AgNP) are promising candidates due to their broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity and low propensity for resistance development in bacteria². From the AgNP reported, silver nanostars (AgNS) have shown enhanced antimicrobial potential, but have their biomedical application largely unexplored³.

AgNS were synthesized by a two-step method at room temperature³. Their morphology, optical properties and surface chemistry in suspension were assessed by transmission electron microscopy, UV-Vis, FTIR and light scattering spectroscopies. Antibacterial and antibiofilm activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* were determined by estimation of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and quantification of *S. aureus* biofilm biomass, respectively. AgNS activity at the cellular level was assessed by determining changes in cell membrane potential and reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels, using fluorescence spectroscopy.

AgNS characterization revealed that size distribution, surface chemistry, and star-shaped morphology agree with the expected results. *S. aureus* growth was inhibited after incubation with AgNS for 24 h at 7.14 pM (MIC). When using the MIC concentration to inhibit and eradicate biofilms, AgNS decreased biofilm biomass by 87% and 49%, respectively. AgNS eradicated biofilms through membrane depolarization (1.7-fold increased) and intracellular ROS accumulation (4.9-fold higher), inducing oxidative damage that reduces bacterial cell viability.

This study explores AgNS potential as antimicrobial agents against *S. aureus*. Furthermore, understanding the mechanisms of action of AgNS against bacteria will be crucial for establishing their biomedical application.

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References: 1. Fair RJ, Tor Y. *Perspect Medicin Chem.* 2014;6:25-64. doi:10.4137/PMC.S14459. 2. Salomoni R, Léo P. *Micro Ser.* 2015;5:851-857. doi: 9421/fmrt34978. 3. Bessa LJ, Gameiro P. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17:7891. doi:10.3390/ijerph17217891.

P30. EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF SPHINGOLIPID AND STEROL STRUCTURAL PROFILES ON YEAST PLASMA MEMBRANE ORGANIZATION

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Keywords: *Fungal plasma membrane, Sphingolipid hydroxylation, Sterol-rich domains, Fluorescent probe, Membrane biophysics.*

ABSTRACT

In yeast, sphingolipids (SLs) localize primarily to the outer plasma membrane (PM) leaflet, while ergosterol is concentrated in the inner leaflet¹. This asymmetry influences PM organization and biophysical properties, including gel-phase sphingolipid-enriched domains (SLEDs), identified in our lab and absent in mammalian membranes under physiological conditions².

To assess the impact of altered SL or sterol profiles on yeast PM properties and architecture, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* wild-type and mutant strains were used: *sur2Δ* and *scs7Δ* with defective sphingolipid hydroxylation, *isc1Δ* and *ipt1Δ* with impaired sphingolipid metabolism, and *erg6Δ* lacking ergosterol, and accumulating other sterols instead. Intact yeast cells were labeled with fluorescent membrane probes, such as di-4-ANEPPS, reporting on several membrane biophysical properties.

Membrane dipole potential measured through di-4-ANEPPS excitation spectra was lower in *erg6Δ* cells, the strain with markedly altered sterol profile, confirming the probe's ability to report on sterol-rich domains. Additionally, mutants with altered SL hydroxylation pattern still display small changes in the properties reported by di-4-ANEPPS indicating that SL hydroxylation influences sterol-rich domains. This structural detail, therefore, has a greater impact on membrane properties than the larger changes in other SL mutants.

Higher SL hydroxylation in yeast, compared to mammals, was previously identified as a key structural detail stabilizing SLEDs³. Although SLEDs and sterol-rich domains do not co-localize in yeast PM, in this work, we showed that SL hydroxylation also influences sterol-rich domains organization. Altogether, SL hydroxylation emerges as a promising target for developing more effective therapies aimed at tackling antifungal resistance.

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References: [1] Solanko, Lukasz M et al. "Ergosterol is mainly located in the cytoplasmic leaflet of the yeast plasma membrane." *Traffic* (Copenhagen, Denmark) vol. 19,3 (2018): 198-214. [2] Santos, Filipa C et al. "Sphingolipid-enriched domains in fungi." *FEBS letters* vol. 594,22 (2020): 3698-3718. [3] Marquês, Joaquim Trigo et al. "Sphingolipid hydroxylation in mammals, yeast and plants - An integrated view." *Progress in lipid research* vol. 71 (2018): 18-42.

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P31. FUNCTIONALIZATION OF SUPRAMOLECULAR PEPTIDE MATERIALS FOR ELECTROCHEMICAL APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: *Collagen Mimetic Peptides, Flexible Bioelectronics, Peptide Electrochemistry, Cyclic Voltammetry.*

ABSTRACT

Collagen is a promising biomaterial for flexible bioelectronics due to its biocompatibility and electron transport capabilities, but production challenges like weak crosslinking and high-water retention limit its use. Collagen-mimetic peptides (CMPs) provide a more controllable alternative, forming conductive hydrogels through self-assembly. Aromatic residues enhance conductivity and stability, making CMPs ideal for sustainable e-skin applications, potentially replacing rigid metal-based electronics [1–3]. We present PSF-1, an aromatic-rich CMP that forms hydrogels, and R, a sustainable electroactive group to evaluate the peptide electrochemical activity with and without R, therefore highlighting the potential of peptide-based biomaterials for bioelectronics.

The self-assembly of the peptide (PSF-1) was performed at varying concentrations, and solution-based and solid-state cyclic voltammetry (CV) assays, were carried out only with the peptide and with the R moiety incorporated at a varying pH range from 4 to 8.

PSF-1 shows a non-reversible oxidation peak from its tryptophan residue across the pH range. Replacing the aromatic residues with R introduces electrochemical reversibility at low pH. Notably, PSF-1's self-assembly enables solid-state reversibility highlighting how molecular design and structural organization synergistically tune peptide electroactivity.

These experiments established pH 6 as the ideal pH for the optimal function of PSF-1 and R, solidifying their potential as viable biomaterial candidates for bioelectronic applications. Our research offers new insights into the development of sustainable and high-performance bioelectronics.

References: 1. S. Moreno et al. Adv. Electron. Mater. 2020; 2. O'Leary L. E. R. et al. Nat. Chem. 2011; 3. Ing N. L. J. Phys. Chem. B. 2018.

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P32. GENERATION AND DOCKING OF A LIBRARY OF OREXIN LIGAND-INSPIRED PHOTOSWITCHABLE LIGANDS TO TREAT ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE CIRCADIAN DISFUNCTION

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Keywords: *Virtual screening, Structure-based, Receptor-ligand interactions, Photopharmacology, Azobenzene*

ABSTRACT

Orexin receptors 1 and 2 (OX₁R and OX₂R) are key regulators of the sleep-wake cycle and potential targets for Alzheimer's disease (AD) therapy. Photoswitchable ligands provide precise control over receptor activity, making them tools for studying receptor signaling. Here, we employed a computational workflow to design and evaluate ligands containing substituted azobenzenes, targeting the OX₁R.

We curated a library of parent molecules from ChEMBL that had K_i data for OX₁R published. Using RDKit (v2023.03.3), molecules were modified by “breaking” bonds and attaching azobenzene to ortho, meta, and para positions. Additionally, a series of derivatives was generated using PSW-Designer-inspired reactions [1]. The resulting library was filtered to retain molecules with molecular weights between 300 and 500 Da. The *cis* and *trans* isomers were docked using Smina (version Oct 15 2019) within the OX₁R binding site. Ligands were selected based on parent pK_i (≥ 8.0), *cis* docking score (≤ -11.0 kcal/mol), and conserved interactions. Finally, visual inspection was conducted to identify ligands exhibiting a *cis* binding mode similar to that of experimentally resolved receptor-ligand complexes. The rationale for this is that *cis*-on photoswitchable ligands can be applied pharmacologically in a more versatile manner.

A total of 5,985 azobenzene derivatives were generated within the specified molecular weight range (11,970 *cis-trans* pairs). Of these, 192 exhibited the required receptor-ligand interactions. After applying further criteria, 50 azobenzenes met both the parent pK_i and the *cis* docking score thresholds. Upon visual inspection, 10 azobenzenes were identified as candidates due to their binding modes in *cis* and *trans*.

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References: 1. Simon IA, Homan EJ, Wijnmans M, Sundström M, Leurs R, De Esch IJP, et al. PSW-Designer: An Open-Source Computational Platform for the Design and Virtual Screening of Photopharmacological Ligands. *J Chem Inf Model.* 2023 Oct 13;63(21):6696–705.

P33. IDENTIFICATION OF GLYCOSYLTRANSFERASE INHIBITORS: PROMISING TARGETS FOR TUBERCULOSIS TREATMENT

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Keywords: *Arabinofuranosyltransferases, Structure-based drug design, Tuberculosis, Membrane protein, NMR.*

ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the leading causes of death worldwide and is caused by the infection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb). The emergence of multidrug-resistant mycobacteria has prompted the need to better understand antibiotic resistance mechanisms and develop novel therapeutics¹.

Arabinofuranosyltransferases (AraTs) are membrane glycosyltransferases involved in the biosynthesis of arabinan, an important component of the unique cell-envelope of Mtb. High virulence and resistance of Mtb to common antibiotics is related to the protective role of the mycobacterial cell wall, so these enzymes are attractive targets against TB²⁻⁵. This family of proteins, essential for bacterial survival and growth, comprises Embs (EmbA-C), which are known targets for ethambutol, a first-line drug for TB treatment; and Afts (AftA-D), which represent new potential drug targets against TB.

Structure-based virtual screening was performed, through the application of a new selection strategy, to identify molecules with potential to inhibit AftD from a collection of previously approved compounds⁶, using a drug repurposing approach. We also performed molecular dynamics studies (MD) with 5 compounds selected using our strategy and compared with the 5 compounds chosen taking into account the docking score value (usual strategy).

The efficiency of the selected compounds from each strategy was evaluated by the minimum inhibitory concentration (MICs) assays on *Mycobacterium smegmatis* and a newly developed NMR activity assay.

Our results suggest that our selection strategy may be more efficient than the usual strategy.

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References: 1- 2024 Global tuberculosis report. 2024; 2- F. E. Umesiri, et al., Med. Res. Rev., 2010, 30, 290–326; 3- M. Jankute, et al., Annu. Rev. Microbiol., 2015, 69, 405–423; 4- K. A. Abrahams and G. S. Besra, Parasitology, 2018, 145, 116–133; 5- C. E. Barry, et al., Infect. Disord. Drug Targets, 2007, 7, 182–202; 6- A. Brown and C. Patel, *Sci. Data*.

P34. IMPACT OF DETERGENTS IN THE ACTIVITY OF A TWO-DOMAIN TYROSINASE

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Keywords: Tyrosinase, Type-3 copper, Sodium dodecyl sulphate, activation, SRCD

ABSTRACT

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) are major contributors to climate change, making their reduction a global priority [1]. In this study, a tyrosine-like (Tyr) enzyme containing a type 3 copper centre [2] was identified to test its activity towards CO₂ and NO_x reduction. This enzyme is a two-domain tyrosinase [3], with the additional domain having no sequence homology, and its model structure was obtained using AlphaFold2.

The enzyme was heterologously produced, purified and characterised spectroscopically and kinetically. Its activity was studied using L-Dopa or hydroquinone (HQ) as substrate. Circular dichroism (CD) and SRCD spectra were obtained in the presence of SDS and other detergents to assess possible structural changes.

The purified tyrosinase has 2 Cu atoms/protein and an absorption band at 340 nm, indicating the presence of its catalytic centre. Kinetic assays showed a low activity towards L-Dopa (0.58 ± 0.03 μM/min/ng protein) compared to other tyrosinases. The presence of SDS increased the specific activity of the enzyme (4.14 ± 0.08 μM/min/ng protein). Cationic and zwitterionic detergents have no effect. HQ oxidation is also enhanced in the presence of SDS. SRCD data revealed changes in secondary structure content in the presence of SDS, accompanied by changes in thermal stability.

This study aims to provide insights into the activation mechanism of this two-domain tyrosinase, which will allow a deeper understanding of how this enzyme could be engineered towards other substrates of interest, such as CO₂ and NO_x.

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References: [1]R. Angamuthu, P. Byers, M. Lutz, A. L. Spek, and E. Bouwman, “Electrocatalytic CO₂ conversion to oxalate by a copper complex,” *Science* (1979), vol. 327, no. 5963, pp. 313–315, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1126/science.1177981. [2]M. Kanteev, M. Goldfeder, and A. Fishman, “Structure-function correlations in tyrosinases,” Sep. 01, 2015, Blackwell Publishing Ltd. doi: 10.1002/pro.2734.

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P35. IMPACT OF FREE AND MEMBRANE-BOUND CURCUMIN ON A β ₁₋₄₂ PEPTIDE AGGREGATION

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Keywords: Protein aggregation, Alzheimer's Disease, amyloid- β peptide (A β), curcumin

ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is accompanied by amyloid-beta (A β) peptide plaque formation. Beyond plaque and fibrils, A β ₁₋₄₂ peptide can exist as soluble amyloid- β oligomers (SA β Os). SA β Os in particular have been strongly associated with pathological effects. The polyphenol curcumin is suggested to inhibit A β aggregation, possibly through enrichment of off-pathway non-toxic soluble oligomers. However, curcumin administered orally is inefficiently absorbed, greatly reducing its bioavailability. Lipid-based formulated curcumin had promising impact on cognitive behavior of non-dementia adults, possibly achieved through increased bioavailability of this polyphenol. The goal of this work was to characterize the impact of lipid-based curcumin formulations on SA β O formation and structure.

The impact of both curcumin and curcumin-loaded liposomes on A β ₁₋₄₂ aggregation was monitored through kinetic assays of protein fibrillation using ThT and other amyloid-sensitive dyes, as well as through Fluorescence Correlation Spectroscopy (FCS).

The presence of liposomes, particularly those enriched in cholesterol, accelerated A β ₁₋₄₂ aggregation while incubation with free curcumin both reduced total fiber content and increased lag times for fibrillation. The use of fluorescent amyloid-sensitive probes with lipid-based formulations of curcumin is challenging due to intrinsic fluorescence of curcumin when incorporated in membranes. For this reason, fluorescently tagged A β ₁₋₄₂ was employed to monitor A β oligomerization and fibrillation in the presence of membrane-bound curcumin. Fluorescence polarization and FCS assays of fluorescently labelled A β ₁₋₄₂ were carried out with both free and membrane-based curcumin.

Free curcumin was shown to inhibit A β ₁₋₄₂ fibrillation, while membrane-bound curcumin was significantly less effective.

P36. IMPROVING TRANSIENT PORE FORMATION IN MARTINI 3 LIPID MEMBRANES

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Keywords: *Molecular Dynamics, Coarse-grain, Martini 3, Lipid membranes, Pore formation.*

ABSTRACT

The lipid membrane is a crucial structure as it plays many roles in the cell, such as regulation of metabolite transport. Ion flux is typically controlled by membrane transporters but they can also leak through transient lipid pores. Control over the metabolite concentration in the cell, and the electrochemical gradient generated through their transport, is essential for the maintenance of cell life, as it plays a major role in certain processes, like signal transduction and ATP synthesis. Thus, pores are crucial structures to gain insight into — since they allow exchanges between the intra and extracellular environments.

Coarse-grained (CG) molecular dynamics (MD) simulations allow us to study systems at time and size scales otherwise inaccessible, at the expense of some atomic detail. In the Martini 3 CG force field, transient lipid pores are not well modeled — with higher energies of formation than those obtained by atomistic (AA) methods. We studied Martini 3 simulations of transient pore formation in lipid bilayers and compared them to AA behavior, to try to identify the limitations of lipid pore simulations with the CG forcefield and address them.

We found a potential target — the lipid tail splay — that may affect formation behavior, and tested lipid prototypes with new topologies to analyze whether the free-energy profile improved.

Whilst we did not obtain better free-energy profiles, we believe this target may still cause incorrect modeling as we were not able to mimic the AA tail splay distribution with accuracy. Other potential targets and solutions will be explored soon.

P37. INHIBITING CYSTEINES IN FIKK KINASES FOR MALARIA THERAPY

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Keywords: *FIKKs, Covalent Inhibition, Cysteine Targeting, Antimalarial Development*

ABSTRACT

The *Plasmodium falciparum* FIKK kinase family, essential for parasite survival and host-pathogen interactions, offers a promising therapeutic target due to its non-canonical ATP-binding pockets and small gatekeeper residues [1, 2]. These structural features, combined with conserved cysteines proximal to the ATP-binding site, present a unique opportunity for covalent inhibitor design—an unexplored strategy for this kinase family.

Leveraging the crystallographic structure of FIKK13 bound to a reversible inhibitor [3], we employed covalent docking and structural modelling to design acrylamide-based inhibitors targeting reactive cysteines. Functional validation included site-directed mutagenesis in FIKK4.1's ATP-binding pocket and kinase activity assays. Diamide, a thiol-oxidizing agent, was also used to probe cysteine-dependent activity.

The crystal structure of FIKK13 revealed key hydrophobic residues that stabilize reversible inhibitors within the ATP-binding pocket. Covalent docking predicted that acrylamide derivatives could form stable thiovinyl adducts with the conserved cysteine. Mutation of this cysteine in FIKK4.1 resulted in a >95% loss of kinase activity, confirming its essential catalytic role. Similarly, diamide treatment abolished activity, highlighting the cysteine's redox-sensitive function.

Covalent targeting of FIKK cysteines is predicted to disrupt kinase function and parasite virulence based on structural insights and mutagenesis. This approach could leverage conserved, parasite-specific features absent in human kinases, paving the way for pan-FIKK inhibitors. While experimental validation of covalent inhibitors is still required, our findings suggest that cysteine-directed covalent inhibition could be a promising strategy for antimalarial development.

References: [1] Bertoldo *et al.* (2015). *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 58(12), 1234–1245. [2] Ettari *et al.* (2021). *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 65(7), e00345-21. [3] Belda *et al.* (2024). *BioRxiv*

P38. INTERACTION OF KETCONAZOLE WITH DPPC BILAYERS

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Keywords: *Antifungal agents, Fluorescence techniques, Membrane-drug interaction, Sphingolipid-enriched gel domains (SLEDs), Permeabilization.*

ABSTRACT

The increasing incidence of drug-resistant fungal infections contributed to the search for new antifungal drugs, namely, drugs derived from ketoconazole (Ke).¹ Ke acts as an antifungal agent by inhibiting cytochrome P450 14 α -demethylase hampering ergosterol biosynthesis. However, recent evidence suggests that azoles might interact with sphingolipid-enriched domains (SLEDs). SLEDs are in a gel phase and are unique to the fungal membrane.²

The main objective of this project was, through fluorescence spectroscopy, to understand the interaction of Ke with gel-phase lipid bilayers and how it can directly affect plasma membrane permeability. To this end, 1,2-dipalmitoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC) liposomes were used.

First, the intrinsic fluorescence of Ke in the presence of increasing concentrations of DPPC was monitored, allowing to determine the DPPC/Water partition coefficient ($K_{p,x}$): ($\sim 4.5 \times 10^4$), and understanding the microenvironment of Ke in this model system.

Moreover, the impact of Ke on DPPC bilayers hydration profile using the probes DPH and Laurdan was explored, which revealed that the effect of Ke is almost unnoticeable. The compound integrates DPPC bilayers in a very superficial way. Despite this, it has the ability to permeabilize the membrane.

Previously, it was shown that Ke interacts moderately with and is deeply inserted in a fluid phospholipid bilayer.³ In this work, it is shown that it also partitions efficiently to the surface of a gel phase bilayer, increasing its permeability. In summary, this work emphasizes the importance of membrane interactions for the antifungal activity and the potential of this azole as a therapeutic scaffold.

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References: ¹R.F.M. Almeida et al. (2019). New diphenylphosphane derivatives of ketoconazole are promising antifungal agents. *Sci.* ²Santos, F.C. et al. (2020) Sphingolipid-enriched domains in fungi. *FEBS* ³Andreia Bento-Oliveira et al. (2025) Membrane insertion properties of ketoconazole derivatives: Elucidating the path to fight drug resistant fungal infections. *J. Mol. Liquids*

P39. MAPPING CONSERVATION PROFILES OF VIRAL SURFACE PROTEINS TO IDENTIFY NOVEL TARGETABLE EPITOPES

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Keywords: *Henipavirus, Flavivirus, Mammarenavirus, PHAVEs, Conservation.*

ABSTRACT

Viral surface proteins, known as PHAVEs (Proteins responsible for Host Attachment and Viral Entry), are crucial for viral infectivity, mediating attachment and fusion with host cells. These proteins serve as key targets for immune neutralization, making the identification of conserved and variable regions essential for the development of broad-spectrum antiviral solutions. Conservation across viral families suggests functional or structural constraints, making these regions prime candidates for neutralizing therapies. Conversely, variable regions may provide insight into immune evasion strategies and offer opportunities for targeting adaptable viral sites. This study focuses on PHAVEs from henipaviruses, flaviviruses, and mammarenaviruses.

This study utilized the ConSurf-DB database, which integrates evolutionary sequence data to highlight structurally and functionally conserved residues to systematically map PHAVE conservation profiles and identify novel epitopes with high therapeutic potential. Structural data from repositories such as SabDaB will be incorporated to refine our understanding of PHAVE interactions with antibodies, nanobodies, and host receptors.

By mapping conserved regions, we anticipate the identification of structurally critical epitopes that can serve as targets for broad-spectrum neutralizing inhibitors. The comparison of conservation profiles with structural data will allow us to distinguish between highly conserved neutralization sites and variable regions associated with immune evasion.

This study will provide a comprehensive map of conserved PHAVE epitopes across henipaviruses, flaviviruses, and mammarenaviruses, offering valuable insights for antiviral drug and vaccine development. By leveraging conservation analysis, we aim to uncover previously unrecognized targetable sites, ultimately contributing to broad-spectrum antiviral strategies against emerging and re-emerging viral threats.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe HORIZON-HLTH-2024-DISEASE-08, GA 101191794 - SHIELD; Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (MostMicro: UIDP/04612/2020, LS4Future: LA/P/0087/2020).

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P40. MOLECULAR DYNAMICS INSIGHTS INTO THE STABILIZATION OF PROTEINS USING SMALL MOLECULES

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Keywords: *MD Simulations, Protein Stabilization, Small Molecules.*

ABSTRACT

Stabilization of proteins is critical for therapeutic and industrial applications, yet mechanistic insights into dynamic interactions remain limited. Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations offer a powerful tool to decode these interactions, but systematic validation of metrics for assessing stabilization is underexplored. This study bridges this gap by quantifying small-molecule effects on protein stability through MD-driven analysis.

MD simulations were performed for a model protein with different small molecule effectors and a ligand-free control. Systems were solvated, neutralized, and equilibrated. A robust analysis pipeline, integrating a wide range of molecular properties, was built to shed light into the behavior of each simulated system. This allowed us to perform a comparative analysis of the effect of different small molecule effectors on the properties of a given protein.

Systems containing small molecules effectors exhibited reduced protein dynamics, suggesting stabilized conformations when compared with the ligand-free control. For simulations at higher temperatures, protein unfolding is reduced in the presence of small molecule effectors. Differences in the contact between the ligands and the protein and ligand aggregation, suggest diverse interaction propensities and aggregation patterns. Experimental assays for thermal stability are in progress. Simulations with a larger set of small molecule effectors for the same protein model are ongoing; other protein models are being studied and considered for testing.

MD simulations are a promising tool to predict stabilization by small molecule effectors.

P41. MOLECULAR TARGETING OF A B-MYB G-QUADRUPLEX WITH AN ACRIDINE-BASED NUCLEIC ACID PROBE

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Keywords: *Targeting, B-MYB gene, G-Quadruplex; Acridine probes, Lung Cancer*

ABSTRACT

The B-MYB gene encodes a transcription factor (B-Myb) that regulates cell growth and survival. Abnormal expression of B-Myb is frequently observed in lung cancer and poses challenges for targeted drug therapy. Oncogenes often contain DNA structures called G-quadruplexes (G4s) in their promoter regions, and B-MYB is no exception. These G4s play roles in genetic regulation and are potential cancer treatment targets.

In this study, a probe was designed to specifically identify a G4 within the promoter region of the B-MYB gene. This probe combines an acridine derivative ligand with a DNA segment complementary to the target sequence, enabling it to hybridize with the adjacent sequence of the G4 being investigated.

Biophysical studies demonstrated that the acridine derivative ligands C₅NH₂ and C₈NH₂ not only effectively stabilized the G4 structure but also exhibited moderate affinity. They were capable of altering the G4 topology and exhibited enhanced fluorescence emission in the presence of this quadruplex. Additionally, these ligands increased the number of G4s observed in cellular studies. The probe was synthesized with good yields, and subsequent cellular studies validated its co-localization with the target sequence.

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P42. NMR-DRIVEN INSIGHTS INTO METABOLIC ADAPTATION OF *STREPTOCOCCUS PNEUMONIAE* TO HOST CELLS

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Keywords: *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, ¹H-NMR, Nitrosative stress, Metabolism, Biofilms.

ABSTRACT

Streptococcus pneumoniae can shift from a commensal biofilm state in the nasopharynx to an invasive and virulent form in normally sterile sites of the human body¹. The pathogenic transformation of this WHO-priority pathogen is frequently initiated by viral co-infections, which stimulate the activation of innate immune cells to produce the nitric oxide (NO) antimicrobial and fever^{1,2,3}. Here, we analyze bacterial metabolic adaptations occurring during this transition.

We utilized proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H-NMR) to assess the changes in extracellular metabolites concentrations during growth of the clinical strain TIGR4 in biofilm form, providing insights into metabolic fluxes and byproduct accumulation that reflect how the bacterium adapts its metabolism, under conditions that mimic the nasopharyngeal environment. Experimental conditions included a temperature shift from 34°C to 37°C combined with NO exposure. Additionally, RT-qPCR was employed to measure the expression dynamics of key genes involved in carbohydrate metabolism, while target gene deletions were generated to evaluate the role of these genes in nitrosative stress resistance.

Our data revealed that NO exposure triggers a specific metabolic response characterized by reduced carbohydrate consumption and diminished production of fermentation end-products during later biofilm stages and demonstrated significant alterations in the expression of genes associated with galactose metabolism.

This integrated approach using ¹H-NMR highlights how *S. pneumoniae* adapts metabolically to overcome nitrosative stress, not only clarifying the metabolic reprogramming induced by NO stress but also revealing potential avenues for therapeutic intervention in pneumococcal diseases.

References: 1. Weiser, J. N., et al. Nat Rev Microbiol (2018). 2. WHO Bacterial Priority Pathogens List, 2024: Bacterial Pathogens of Public Health Importance to Guide Research, Development and Strategies to Prevent and Control Antimicrobial Resistance. (2024). 3. Narciso, A. R., et al. Nat Rev Microbiol (2024).

P43. PARAMETERIZATION OF BACTERIAL PEPTIDOGLYCAN FOR STATE-OF-THE-ART MOLECULAR DYNAMICS COARSE-GRAIN FORCE FIELDS

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Keywords: *Bacterial cell wall, Peptidoglycan, Model parameterization, Coarse-grain, Martini 3*

ABSTRACT

The cell wall is one of the most defining characteristics of bacteria. It plays a crucial role in cell integrity while regulating the passive transport of many nutrients and proteins. The main culprit behind the cell wall properties is the peptidoglycan polymer. It is composed of a backbone of two alternating sugars (NAG and NAM) and a pentapeptide linked to every NAM sugar. This pentapeptide is capable of cross-linking with other peptides to create large meshes.

Coarse-grain (CG) molecular dynamics trade molecular detail for lighter calculation and larger time steps, reaching time and size scales compatible with simulation of the peptidoglycan mesh. In this work, we develop a peptidoglycan model for one of the most widely used coarse-grain frameworks for biomolecular simulations, the Martini 3 force field.

The glycan chain of peptidoglycan was parameterized by first simulating single disaccharide units using existing AA models. These parameters were then extended to represent the full glycan chain. Peptide stems were added to each NAM residue, with their parameters determined based on Martini 3 guidelines. The process also involved adjusting intramolecular non-bonded potentials to match the disaccharide units' flipping behavior between torsional states. This work is one of the first Martini 3 parameterization efforts to incorporate these factors.

This model can be adapted for Gram-positive bacteria by modifying the peptide stem, adding layers, and introducing pentaglycine bridges. In the end, our parameterization effort was one of the first in Martini 3 to take into account and correctly capture the kinetics of intramolecular dynamics.

P44. pH-DEPENDENT MEMBRANE INSERTION OF ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES: INSIGHTS FROM MD AND CpHMD SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *Antimicrobial Peptides, Anionic Membranes, Molecular Dynamics, Constant pH Molecular Dynamics.*

ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are natural small peptides that play a key role in innate immunity, exhibiting broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity and promising applications in medicine [1]. In this study, we modify and optimize peptides of the Mastoparan family (MP1 and MP2) to create a series of synthetic variants (H-MP1, L1A, and L1Am) and explore their affinities towards anionic membrane systems. Conventional molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and constant pH molecular dynamics (CpHMD) simulations were employed to investigate how the peptide protonation and conformation influence their interactions with the lipid bilayer. The positive charge distribution and the presence or absence of acidic residues collectively influence the helix propensity upon membrane interaction. Preliminary simulations indicate that MP1 has a deeper membrane insertion than H-MP1, which suggests stronger interactions, hence higher lipid packing perturbation. The wet-lab experiments on L1A also showed a strong membrane affinity and significant structural perturbations, further supporting its proposed antimicrobial mechanism [2]. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of peptide membrane insertion dynamics, elucidating their impact on lipid organization and the role of pH in modulating peptide charge and conformation. The CpHMD simulations also provide significant insights into the key residues modulating those pH effects, thereby advancing our understanding of these systems and improving the rational design of antimicrobial agents.

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References: [1] Huan Y, Kong Q, Mou H, Yi H. *Front Microbiol.* 2020;11: 582779. [2] Martins IBS, Viegas TG, Dos Santos Alvares D, de Souza BM, Palma MS, Ruggiero Neto J, et al. *Amino Acids.* 2021;53: 753–767.

P45. POINT-OF-CARE IMMUNOSENSING OF A KEY BIOMARKER FOR TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY DETECTION

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Keywords: *Electrochemistry; Immunosensor; Laser induced Graphene (LIG), Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS); Glial Fibrillary Acidic Protein (GFAP); Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI); Early detection; Biomarker*

ABSTRACT

The detection of glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), a biomarker for traumatic brain injury (TBI), is crucial due to its rapid release into the bloodstream following brain cell damage. Early diagnosis is essential to prevent further injury and improve patient outcomes, as current tools often lack the speed required for timely intervention.

A cost-effective, user-friendly biosensor was developed using anti-GFAP antibodies to detect GFAP concentrations above 22 pg/mL in buffer, a threshold for identifying mild TBI. The device incorporates electrochemical sensing using homemade laser-induced graphene (LIG) with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and differential pulse voltammetry. Biosensor preparation involved: (i) electrode functionalization with a mixture of alkanethiols, including the electrically conducting 4-mercaptobenzoic acid; (ii) antibody conjugation; and (iii) albumin blocking to increase specificity. The immunosensor's stepwise construction was assessed using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and EIS, as electrochemical techniques.

A limit of detection for GFAP below 22 pg/mL could be obtained, demonstrating the sensor's effectiveness in detecting GFAP at clinically relevant levels. The immunosensor's performance matched existing GFAP sensors while offering greater affordability and portability.

The proposed immunosensor shows strong potential for point-of-care GFAP detection, reducing reliance on complex procedures and enabling prompt TBI diagnosis and intervention.

P46. POLYPURINE REVERSE HOOGSTEEN HAIRPINS (PPRHS): A TRIPLEX FORMING OLIGONUCLEOTIDE FOR LUNG CANCER THERAPY

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Keywords: *Triplex Forming Oligonucleotides, PPRH, Lung cancer, B-MYB oncogene.*

ABSTRACT

The B-MYB proto-oncogene encodes a transcription factor crucial for regulating the cell cycle and differentiation; however, abnormal B-MYB expression associated with poor prognosis is observed in various cancers, namely lung cancer. The oncogene promoter regions are enriched in guanines, enabling the formation of G-quadruplexes (G4), which can play regulatory roles in gene expression due to their prevalence near transcription start sites and represent promising anticancer targets.

The Polypurine Reverse Hoogsteen hairpins (PPRHs) have been reported as a potential therapeutic tool because they can bind to polypyrimidine stretches in dsDNA by Watson-Crick bonds (forming a triplex), displacing the G-rich sequence of the DNA (forming G4), and subsequently induce gene-silencing. This approach is reported as more effective at lower doses, affordable, less immunogenic, and has a longer half-life.

Thus, B-MYB downregulation has become an attractive strategy for cancer therapy. Using a combination of bioinformatics, biophysical, and biochemical techniques, we first designed the PPRH oligos and then assessed the formation and biophysical properties of triplex structures. Subsequently, we evaluated the effects of PPRH in lung cell lines in terms of cytotoxicity, cell cycle and apoptosis, clonogenic capacity, and gene expression.

The biophysical experiments (CD, UV, NMR and SEC) revealed the ability of designed oligos to form stable triplex structures and the cellular assay demonstrated strong capacity to reduce cell viability, clonogenic capacity and induce apoptosis.

These findings highlight the B-MYB promoter region as a promising target and the use of triplex-forming oligonucleotides as a tool for developing innovative cancer therapies.

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P47. SEARCHING FOR NEW ANTIVIRALS AGAINST INFLUENZA: TARGETING NON-STRUCTURAL PROTEIN 1 (NS1)

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Keywords: *Influenza, NS1, HSQC-NMR, Protein Expression, Design of Experiments, Fragment-Based Drug Discovery.*

ABSTRACT

The influenza A virus poses a global health challenge through yearly epidemics and a continued threat of a pandemic. With the goal of developing last-resort antivirals against Influenza, we have targeted Non-Structural Protein 1 (NS1), one of the most conserved proteins of the Influenza's proteome.¹

Using a computationally driven Fragment-Based Drug Discovery (FBDD) approach, we identified molecular fragments that interact with NS1's Effector Domain (ED). Three out of eight fragments exhibited the strongest interactions in STD-NMR experiments, prompting titration studies to determine their K_d values. We plan to combine and/or grow selected fragments to enhance binding affinity, optimizing their interaction with the ED. ¹⁵N-labeled NS1 will be key in mapping fragment binding sites and assessing inter-fragment distances by NMR.²

To perform ¹⁵N-NMR experiments, NS1-ED must be labeled with ¹⁵N. This requires efficient protein expression in ¹⁵N-labeled medium. Therefore, we optimized the expression protocol first in LB medium and then in labeled minimal medium using "Design of Experiments". Three variables (growth time, temperature after induction, and induction time) were studied, and protein expression was followed by SDS-PAGE and quantification of total protein as quantitative responses in a Face-Centered Composite Design (FCCD) to determine optimal protein production conditions.

By integrating computational drug design with experimental techniques such as NMR, ITC, and fluorescence spectroscopy, we aim to shift NS1 inhibition research from the backburner to the forefront, advancing the discovery of effective antivirals against the Influenza virus.

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References: [1] Rosário-Ferreira et al., "The Central Role of Non-Structural Protein 1 (NS1) in Influenza Biology and Infection." [2] Cunha et al., "Unveiling New Druggable Pockets in Influenza Non-Structural Protein 1: NS1-Host Interactions as Antiviral Targets for Flu."

P48. SENSITIVE AML DETECTION VIA QCM APTASENSORS: HARNESSING APTAMER PRECISION FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS

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Keywords: *Acute myeloid leukemia, Quartz crystal microbalance, Aptasensor, Detection, Diagnosis.*

ABSTRACT

Aptamers, short single-stranded DNA or RNA oligonucleotides, are highly specific and have high affinity for a variety of biomarkers, including those on the surface of cancer cells. Depending on their selective binding to acute myeloid leukemia (AML) biomarkers, aptamers offer a promising avenue for targeted early AML detection.

We employed Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM) technology integrated with aptasensors to develop a label-free, sensitive diagnostic platform. QCM recognizes mass changes on the surface of a sensor making it ideal for real-time monitoring of biomolecular interactions. Our approach was to immobilize thiolated and biotinylated AML-specific aptamers on QCM sensor surface so that specific recognition of AML cell surface biomarkers and direct conversion of binding events into measurable frequency changes could be achieved.

Through systematic optimization, we developed QCM aptasensors functionalized with biotinylated and thiolated aptamers with low detection limits of AML cells. Notably, the sensors were also sensitive and selective while testing on clinical patient sample during validation, attesting to their robustness and translatability.

Our findings demonstrate the sensitivity, reliability, and early diagnosis capability of QCM aptasensors as a diagnostic tool for AML. Relying on the selectivity of the aptamers and the precision of QCM technology, the technique paves the way for real-time, non-invasive detection platforms with promising prospects for being implemented in a clinical environment.

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P49. STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF CbcV FROM Cbc3, A CYTOCHROME *bc₁* COMPLEX IN *GEOBACTER*'S REDOX NETWORK

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Keywords: *Geobacter*, Respiratory complex, Electron transfer, Rieske protein.

ABSTRACT

Geobacter sulfurreducens is an electrogenic bacterium with promising applications in bioremediation and microbial fuel cells, thus offering potential alternatives to high carbon footprint industries [1]. However, the full development of these technologies requires a deeper understanding of the process that enables the bacterium to transfer electrons to extracellular acceptors through a series of redox partners that is known as extracellular electron transfer.

CbcV is a Rieske iron-sulfur protein containing a [2Fe-2S] cluster and is a component of the cytochrome *bc₁* complex Cbc3, which is homologous to well-characterized respiratory complexes III. This complex also comprises CbcX, a pentaheme *c*-type cytochrome, and CbcW, an integral membrane-associated diheme *b*-type cytochrome. Previous studies showed that the *cbcV* and *cbcX* genes are upregulated when *G. sulfurreducens* is grown on Fe(III) oxides and that the deletion of *cbcV* results in a 2.5-fold decrease in Fe(III) reduction rates, suggesting a crucial role for the Cbc3 complex in iron reduction[2].

In this study, CbcV's periplasmic domain (12.7 kDa) was heterologously produced in *E. coli* and characterized using a range of spectroscopic techniques. Circular dichroism was employed to access its secondary structure and confirm the nature of the FeS center, while differential scanning calorimetry was used to evaluate its thermal stability. CbcV's redox potential was determined via potentiometric titrations monitored by UV-Visible spectroscopy. UV-Visible spectroscopy was also used to evaluate electron transfer between CbcV and CbcX, providing understanding of the electron transfer pathway within the respiratory complex Cbc3.

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References: [1] K. Rabaey and W. Verstraete, "Microbial fuel cells: Novel biotechnology for energy generation," *Trends in Biotechnology*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 291–298, Jun. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.tibtech.2005.04.008. [2] M. Aklujkar, D. Young, A. Holmes, R. B. Chavan, M. Risso, and D. R. Lovley, "Proteins involved in electron transfer to Fe(III) and Mn(IV) oxides by *Geobacter sulfurreducens* and *Geobacter uraniireducens*," *Microbiology (United Kingdom)*, vol. 159, no. 3, pp. 515–535, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1099/mic.0.064089-0.

P50. STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MASTOPARAN-L AND [I⁵, R⁸] MP PEPTIDOMIMETICS

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Keywords: Mastoparans, Peptidomimetics, Drug-resistant bacterial infections.

ABSTRACT

Drug-resistant bacterial infections continue to demand innovative alternative treatments. Mastoparan-like peptides are multifunctional molecules with broad antimicrobial potential, constituting an attractive alternative. However, their susceptibility to proteolytic degradation has hindered their clinical translation. In this sense, the substitution of L- by D-amino acids has proven to be an effective strategy to confer resistance to protease activity.

The peptides (D-mast-L, D-[I⁵, R⁸] MP, RI-mast-L, RI-[I⁵, R⁸] MP) were synthesized using the Fmoc solid-phase strategy. Circular dichroism was used to determine the peptides' secondary structures. To assess the peptides' antibacterial potential, the broth microdilution method was used. The cytotoxic activities were evaluated by hemolytic assays. The peptide stability towards human serum was performed by UPLC-MS, and the affinity by membrane models were studied by SPR.

Peptides' secondary structures in environments simulating bacterial membranes (e.g., 100 mM SDS and 30% TFE) showed α -helical conformations. The peptide RI-[I⁵, R⁸] MP showed MIC/MBC values between 8 and 2 μ M, whereas D-mast-L and D-[I⁵, R⁸] MP were mostly inactive. None of the peptides were hemolytic. The peptides RI-[I⁵, R⁸] MP and RI-mast-L showed the highest stability, with 100% and >75% of the peptides remaining after 4 hours, whereas D-mast-L and D-[I⁵, R⁸] MP were degraded within 2 to 4 h. In general, the peptides exhibited a higher binding affinity for POPC/POPG membranes than POPC membranes.

The peptidomimetic strategy employed here seems to influence the peptides' biological activities, secondary structures, and proteolytic stability. RI-[I⁵, R⁸] MP stood out for its antibacterial potential and stability in human serum.

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P51. STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS INTO THE CATALYTIC REDUCTION SITE OF HUMAN ALDEHYDE OXIDASE

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Keywords: *human aldehyde oxidase, drug metabolism, X-ray crystallography, molybdenum cofactor, enzymatic mechanism.*

ABSTRACT

Human aldehyde oxidase (hAOX1) is a molybdo-flavoprotein and is highly expressed in liver and adipose tissue¹. Due to its well-established role in drug metabolism, particularly in phase I biotransformation, this enzyme has gained significant interest to pharmaceutical companies in drug design campaigns¹. hAOX1 exhibits broad substrate specificity, catalysing the oxidation of various aldehydes and N-heterocycles, the hydrolysis of amide bonds, and the reduction of nitro and S/N-oxides¹. However, despite extensive studies, the mechanism by which this enzyme catalyses substrate reduction remains poorly understood, and the exact location of the reaction is still uncertain, although, the FAD site has been proposed as the potential reduction site².

hAOX1 was co-crystallized with a known inhibitor (thioridazine (Thi)) and reduction substrates (ziprasidone (Zp), 5-nitroquinoline (5Nq)). X-ray diffraction data were collected at beamline ID30A-1 of the European Synchrotron (ESRF) and the structures were determined by molecular replacement, refined and interpreted.

Crystals of the ternary complex hAOX1-Thi-Zp diffracted up to a resolution of 2.8 Å. Following refinement, the final crystallographic $R_{\text{work}}/R_{\text{free}}$ values were 0.18/0.24. Unexpectedly, the initial electron density maps (Fo-Fc) revealed positive density that enabled modelling Zp at the Mo active site, while Thi was modelled in a surface groove³. Regarding the crystals of hAOX1-Thi-5Nq complex, despite the lower resolution (3.1 Å), the 5Nq molecule could also be modelled near the Mo site.

The structural analysis of these complexes indicates that the tested reduction substrates of hAOX1 exhibit affinity for the Mo active site, suggesting that substrate reductions is likely to occur at this location.

References: 1.Mota C et al. Coordination Chemistry Reviews. 2018; 368:35–59. doi:10.1016/j.ccr.2018.04.006. 2. Paragas et al. Biochem Pharmacol. 2017;145:210–7. doi:10.1016/j.bcp.2017.09.002. 3. Coelho et al. Nat Chem Biol. 2015;11(10):779–83. doi:10.1038/nchembio.1895

P52. STRUCTURAL STUDIES ON PROMISING DRUG TARGETS IN BACTERIAL RNA METABOLISM

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Keywords: RNA metabolism, ribonucleases, drug resistance, emergent pathogens

ABSTRACT

Successful pathogens readily adapt to changing environmental conditions to express the appropriate virulence factors at each given moment. RNA metabolism plays a crucial role in this adaptability, as RNA is a key regulator of multiple processes in the cell. The continuous processing and decay of mRNA allows pathogens to thrive by promoting fast alterations in gene expression. Consequently, ribonucleases (RNases), the enzymes that catalyze RNA degradation, are important for the virulence of several pathogens.

We have been exploring unconventional/alternative metabolic pathways, such as RNA homeostasis, as a promising strategy to address the global crisis of antibiotic resistance. Our goal is to acquire in-depth knowledge about RNases and their molecular mechanisms to ultimately unveil new therapeutic options. In this regard, we are studying RNases from both established and emerging bacterial pathogens, using a comprehensive and integrative approach: (1) functional characterization (in vitro activity assays), (2) biophysical characterization (thermostability assays, dynamic light scattering and circular dichroism), and (3) structural characterization (X-ray crystallography, cryo-electron microscopy, and small-angle X-ray scattering).

Here, we will present preliminary cryo-EM data on the exoribonuclease RNase R from the opportunistic pathogen *Morganella morganii*. The structural data combined with the biochemical, biophysical, and functional data already gathered will contribute to a better understanding of the reaction mechanism of these RNases, and to propose a model for RNA degradation. By disclosing the overall architecture of this enzyme and gaining insights into its mechanism of action, we can assess its potential as a putative drug target to fight this emergent pathogen.

P53. STRUCTURE-ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP AND VIRTUAL SCREENING APPROACHES FOR IDENTIFYING NATURAL PRODUCT MODULATORS OF OREXIN RECEPTORS

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Keywords: *Alzheimer's Disease (AD), Orexin Receptors, Natural Products, Virtual Screening, Molecular Docking*

ABSTRACT

Orexin receptors (OX₁R and OX₂R) are G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) that play critical roles in regulating sleep-wake cycles, metabolism, and cognitive functions. Emerging evidence supports a link between orexin signaling and Alzheimer's disease (AD), mainly through influence on sleep disturbances, neuroinflammation, and β -amyloid clearance [1]. Targeting orexin receptors may, therefore, represent a promising novel therapeutic strategy for AD. Natural products, with their rich and diverse chemical structures and biologically relevant scaffolds, are invaluable in the discovery of new drugs. Screening natural products for orexin receptor modulation may reveal novel bioactive compounds with enhanced selectivity and favorable ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) profiles, suitable for AD therapy.

Dataset & SAR analysis: ChEMBL data was preprocessed and analyzed to determine SAR by MCS filtering and various descriptor calculations

PLIP results of crystallized ligands and molecular docking results for ChEMBL data were used to study receptor-ligand interactions and refine hit selection

Computational approaches like molecular docking, clustering, and ML were used to study a natural compound database (COCONUT)

Chemical space comparison of ChEMBL and COCONUT data. ADMET property prediction, molecular docking scores, and rules based on SAR, PLIPs, and ML techniques were used to filter the COCONUT database to identify potential lead compounds.

Potential lead compounds from the COCONUT database would be interesting to study in binding assays to validate their potential as novel therapeutics for AD. SAR and PLIP analysis provided insight that could aid in further optimizing these leads.

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References: [1] Gao, F., Liu, T., Tuo, M., & Chi, S. (2021). The role of orexin in Alzheimer disease: from sleep-wake disturbance to therapeutic target. *Neuroscience Letters*, 765, 136247.

P54. STUDY OF THE MONOMER-DIMER EQUILIBRIUM OF THE pH SENSING PROTEIN PSBS USING MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *Photoprotection, dimerization, pH-sensitive behaviour, constant-pH molecular dynamics.*

ABSTRACT

Under intense sunlight, plants prevent photooxidation by dissipating excess absorbed energy as heat, a protective mechanism known as non-photochemical quenching (NPQ) [1]. This process is triggered by PsbS, a membrane protein responsive to pH changes in the thylakoid lumen [2]. Although the precise mechanism of PsbS activation remains unclear, experimental evidence suggests that certain glutamate (Glu) residues on the lumen side may act as pH sensors, and that both the monomer-dimer equilibrium and the dimer conformation are pH-dependent.

A recent computational study on the PsbS monomer [3] supports these observations, identifying unusually high pKa values for several lumen-exposed Glu residues, suggesting a key role in pH sensitivity under physiological conditions. The study also reported pH-induced folding of a loop likely involved in dimerization and revealed correlations between protonation states across the membrane, potentially enabling lumen-stroma communication.

The present work extends this investigation to the PsbS dimer, using constant-pH molecular dynamics (CpHMD) simulations, as in the previous study, to determine pKa values, conformational dynamics, and correlations between protonation and structural changes. By combining monomer [3] and dimer data, the pH-dependence of dimerization and the role of key residues will be assessed using a thermodynamic linkage relation [4].

This study employs the GROMACS molecular dynamics package, alongside in-house tools: meadTools, PETIT, and ST-CpHMD. The outcomes are expected to enhance our understanding of the PsbS activation mechanism and contribute to the development of strategies for improving plant photoprotection and crop performance [5].

References: [1] Müller et al (2001) *Plant Physiol.* 10:1104. [2] Xiao-Ping Li et al (2002) *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 10:1073. [3] Liguori et al (2019) *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 10:1737. [4] Rocha et al (2022) *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 18:1982. [5] Kromdijk et al. (2016) *Science* 354:857.

P55. STUDYING THE CYTOCHROME C OXIDASE PROTON PUMPING MECHANISM USING QUANTUM MECHANICS AND CONSTANT PH MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *Cytochrome c Oxidase, Proton pumping, Computational biophysics.*

ABSTRACT

The Cytochrome c Oxidase (CcO) enzyme reduces molecular oxygen to water while pumping protons against their concentration gradient from the mitochondrial matrix to intermembrane space, maintaining the electrochemical gradient. The directionality of the pumping is postulated as a “gating” mechanism, where changes in the electrostatic environment modulate the proton affinity (pKa value) of certain residues.

We consolidated the literature on the catalytic cycle, and presented an alternative. Constant pH Molecular Dynamics (CpHMD) simulations were used to study the protonation behavior (pKa values) of key residues of the gating mechanism. However, the metal cofactors of CcO and their coordinated residues are not parameterized in standard force fields, and previously published charge sets are not compatible with the catalytic cycle adopted, requiring their parameterization with Quantum Mechanics (QM) methods, coupled with RESP calculations.

The QM-calculated electrostatic potential profile obtained for each state of the catalytic cycle showed convergence and electronic stability. The charge sets obtained with RESP were in agreement with previously published data [paper Antonio]. We build a computational CcO model informed by our charge set calculations, which preliminary CpHMD results will be showcased.

We have validated the stability of the electronic configuration of the catalytic site at each step of our catalytic cycle with QM calculations, and have studied some of them with CpHMD.

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P56. SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERISATION OF PYRANINE DERIVATES AS NEW FLUORESCENT pH SENSORS

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Keywords: *Pyranine derivatives, pH sensitive probe, membrane permeation assay*

ABSTRACT

Fluorescent pH sensors are important probes for the characterization of the pH of biological systems by fluorescence microscopy. For this goal, the pH sensors must be membrane permeable to allow their equilibration within cells and cell organelles. They must also show sensitivity in the physiological pH range, in the neutral and acidic region. Another important application of fluorescent pH sensors is to follow the permeation kinetics of weak acids/bases using the pH variation assay.¹ In this application, the pH sensor must however be membrane impermeable. Pyranine possesses a hydroxyl group with a pK_a of 7.3, and three sulfonic acid groups providing high polarity and low membrane permeability, being used in this method to evaluate permeation kinetics at neutral pH. To increase the applicability of the pH variation assay it is relevant to expand the pH sensitive region. However the pH sensors available, including some pyranine derivatives,² are all membrane permeable.

Synthesis of a new pyranine derivative by its reaction with 4-(2-aminoethyl)benzenesulfonyl fluoride (AEBSF) in aqueous media. Characterization of the product formed, including its spectroscopic properties and pH sensitivity.

The pyranine derivative preserved a pH-dependent fluorescence, with a decrease in the pK_a from 7.3 to near 4. The product maintains a very high polarity, being a promising pH sensor to assess drug permeability in the acidic region using the pH variation assay.

This work is an important contribution in the field of drug development by allowing deep and complementary studies about membrane permeability at acidic conditions.

References: [1] Eyer, K., Paech, F., et al. A liposomal fluorescence assay to study permeation kinetics of drug-like weak bases across the lipid bilayer. *J. Control. Release* 173, 102–109 (2014). [2] Finkler, B., Spies, C., et al. Highly photostable “super”-photoacids for ultrasensitive fluorescence spectroscopy. *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.* 13, 548–562 (2014).

P57. TARGETING THE PROTEASOME B5 SUBUNIT: A COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH TO CANCER DRUG DISCOVERY

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Keywords: Human Proteasome $\beta 5$ Subunit, Pharmacophore Modeling, Proteasome Inhibitors

ABSTRACT

The human proteasome $\beta 5$ subunit (HPB5S) plays a crucial role in protein degradation, characterized by its chymotrypsin-like (CT-L) activity. As such, HPB5S is a key target for proteasome inhibitors, such as bortezomib and carfilzomib, which selectively inhibit its CT-L activity. Inhibition of this activity ultimately triggers cell apoptosis.¹

Initially, key residues responsible for most interactions within all HPB5S PDB structures were identified using the Protein-Ligand Interaction Profiler (PLIP) software, specifically T1, A20, T21, M45, G47, and A49. Then, pharmacophore models were generated using MOE and Schrödinger software. A receptor-based model was generated using the 5LEY² structure, which included two hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA), two hydrogen bond donors (HBD), and one hydrophobic (HYD) feature. This model was then employed to screen HPB5S inhibitors from the ChEMBL34 database. The screening indicated that 88.6% of active compounds passed, along with 69.9% of inactive compounds. Due to the model's low selectivity, a ligand-based approach was also implemented, involving the alignment of 14 crystallographic inhibitors of HPB5S. 89% of actives were retrieved, although 74.7% of inactive passed. Consequently, a combined receptor- and ligand-based model was constructed based on the 8UD9³ structure complexed with the TDI-8304 inhibitor, featuring two HBA, one HYD, and one aromatic feature. This model achieved higher accuracy, retaining 94.4% of actives. However, the high number of inactive compounds retrieved highlights the need for further improvement. Next steps include refining the radii of features and implementing filtering techniques including Machine Learning models. Additionally, databases including DrugBank, will be assessed for repurposing.

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References: 1. Leonardo-Sousa, C & Carvalho, A. N. & Guedes, R. A. & Fernandes, P. M. P. & Aniceto, N. & Salvador, J. A. R. & Gama, M. J. & Guedes, R. C. Revisiting Proteasome Inhibitors: Molecular Underpinnings of Their Development, Mechanisms of Resistance and Strategies to Overcome Anti-Cancer Drug Resistance. *Molecules* **27**, 2201 (2022). 2. Schrader, J. & Henneberg, F. & Mata, R.A. & Tittmann, K. & Schneider, T.R. & Stark, H. & Bourenkov, G. & Chari, A. The inhibition mechanism of human 20S proteasomes enables next-generation inhibitor design. *Science* **353**, 594-598 (2016). 3. Hsu, H.C & Li, D. & Zhan, W. & Ye, J. & Liu, Y.J. & Leung, A. & Qin, J. & Crespo, B. & Gamo, F.J. & Zhang, H. & Cui, L. & Roth, A. & Kirkman, L.A. & Lin, G. Structures revealing mechanisms of resistance and collateral sensitivity of Plasmodium falciparum to proteasome inhibitors. *Nat Commun* **14**, 8302-8302 (2023)

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P58. Targeting the role of 4Fe4S cluster in DNA Glycosylases

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Keywords: DNA glycosylases, FeS cluster proteins, vibrational spectroscopy

ABSTRACT

DNA glycosylases are enzymes that remove damaged bases from DNA by catalysing the hydrolysis of the glycosylic bond, between the base and the sugar phosphate backbone of DNA, at the onset of the base excision repair (BER) pathway [1, 2, 3]. These enzymes are found in bacteria, yeast and humans, and are interesting targets for drug development. Some of the enzymes belonging to the Helix-hairpin-Helix (HhH) superfamily of DNA glycosylases possess a FeS cluster, which raises a fundamental question about the role of the cluster in the BER [2, 3]. Here we address the still disputed role of these clusters by studying two yeast DNA glycosylases, one which carries a cluster (yNTH₂) and one that does not (yNTH₁). After the recombinant production of full-length yNTH₂ and truncated yNTH₂Δ39, we characterized their biophysical and biochemical properties by employing vibrational spectroscopy (resonance Raman and FTIR), electrochemistry and activity assays. We demonstrate that both forms are catalytically active, possess a typical cubane [4Fe4S]²⁺ cluster, and have comparable redox potentials ($E_0=0 \pm 14$ mV). In the next step, we will produce and study the enzyme without the cluster (yNTH₁), which will allow us to understand the influence of the cluster on the structural and functional properties of DNA glycosylases.

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References: [1] Roldán-Arjona, T., & Ariza, R. R. (2009). Repair and tolerance of oxidative DNA damage in plants. *Mutation Research/Reviews in Mutation Research*, 681(2-3), 169-179. [2] Moe E, Silveira CM, Zuccarello L, Rollo F, Stelter M, De Bonis S, Kulka-Peschke C, Katz S, Hildebrandt P, Zebger I, et al. 2022. *Chem Commun.* 58(90):12568–12571. [3] Moe E, Sezer M, Hildebrandt P and Todorovic S. 2015. *Chem Commun.* 51(15): 3255–3257.

P59. THE EFFECT OF LOW-DOSE RADIATION ON THE AGGREGATION OF NKX6-2 MUTANTS ASSOCIATED TO SPASTIC ATAXIA 8 IN LIVING CELLS

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Keywords: NKX6-2; amyloid; neurodegeneration; radiation therapy; SPAX8

ABSTRACT

Spastic ataxia 8 (SPAX8) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by cerebellar dysfunction and white matter loss, linked to loss-of-function mutations in the NKX6-2 gene, encoding for a transcriptional repressor relevant to embryonic development. Our lab recently showed that some of these mutations result in NKX6-2 misfolding and aggregation in the nucleus of living cells. This study investigates whether low-dose ionizing radiation can modulate NKX6-2 aggregation, suggesting its potential as a treatment for SPAX8 and other protein misfolding disorders.

New SPAX8-related NKX6-2 mutants (N188D and Q191*) are being generated using PCR-based site-directed mutagenesis and cloning, to be introduced into a pcDNA3.1 backbone, tagged with the Venus fluorescent reporter, and transfected into HeLa cells. Aggregation will be assessed using filter trap assays, western blotting, and fluorescence microscopy. Cells will be exposed to ionizing radiation (electron, photon, and proton beams), and analyzed once more using the same initial assays.

Our data suggest that NKX6-2 mutants, such as K41* and L163V, exhibit distinct aggregation patterns. We will compare new mutants' phenotypes (N188D and Q191*) with the known phenotypes. Ionizing radiation, through direct molecular damage and reactive oxygen species generation, may influence these patterns. Ongoing analysis will be able to compare irradiated and non-irradiated samples, determining the effects of low-dose radiation on NKX6-2 amyloid load and structural changes.

This study aims to elucidate the aggregation behavior of SPAX8-related NKX6-2 mutants and assess ionizing radiation as a potential therapeutic strategy. Insights from this research may contribute to novel treatments for neurodegenerative diseases associated with protein misfolding.

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P60. THE PHYTOCHEMICAL ACETYL ALEURITOLIC ACID HAS DOUBLE ACTION AGAINST SARS-CoV-2 INFECTION: ANTIVIRAL AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY PROFILE

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Keywords: SARS-CoV-2 infection, Triterpenoid, Antiviral, Anti-inflammatory.

ABSTRACT

Despite the fast development of vaccines, the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) still circulates through variants and escape the humoral immune response [1]. SARS-CoV-2 has provoked over 200,000 deaths/months since its emergence and only a few antiviral drugs showed clinical benefit up to this moment. Thus, chemical structures endowed with anti-SARS-CoV-2 activity are important for continuous antiviral development and natural products represent a fruitful source of substances with biological activity [1-3]. In the present study, acetyl aleuritic acid (AAA), a triterpenoid isolated from the powered stem bark of *Croton cajucara*, was investigated as a candidate anti-SARS-CoV-2 by cell-based assays combined with enzymatic and in silico approaches. In silico and enzymatic analysis indicated that AAA may target the viral main protease (M^{pro}) and not the papain-like protease (PL^{pro}) in a mixed inhibition way. Cell-based assays in type II pneumocytes cell lineage (Calu-3) showed that SARS-CoV-2 is susceptible to AAA with a similar potency compared with the commercial anti-SARS-CoV-2 nirmatrelvir (the covalent M^{pro} inhibitor present in the drug PAXLOVID™) [4] with the corresponding half maximal effective concentration of (1.09 ± 0.13) and (0.882 ± 0.151) μ M. Finally, AAA had the capacity to inhibit the levels of pro-inflammatory mediators [5], configuring this phytochemical as an interesting chemical scaffold for the development of novel semisynthetic compounds against coronavirus disease (COVID-19).

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References: [1] Chaves, et al. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 2022, 222, 1015. [2] Chaves, et al. *Viruses* 2022, 14, 1458. [3] Alqaaf, et al. *Sci Rep* 2025, 15, 200. [4] Moon, et al. *Antiviral Res.* 2024, 225, 105859. [5] Li, et al. *Phytochemistry* 2025, 231, 114344.

BIOPHYSICS FESTIVAL – 5th Meeting of Young Biophysicists

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P61. UNDERSTANDING DRUG-MEMBRANE INTERACTIONS AND RECONCILING RESULTS FROM DIFFERENT METHODS: INSIGHTS FROM A pH-VARIATION ASSAY

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Keywords: Passive permeation, Liposome, pH-variation assay.

ABSTRACT

Unassisted permeation through biomembranes is crucial for the availability of drugs and biological ligands at target sites. Understanding this process and how specific molecular properties influence it is essential to optimize drug delivery and enhance therapeutic efficacy. However, literature data are difficult to interpret and/or reconcile.

The pH-variation assay is a simple methodology useful to evaluate permeation of non-fluorescent compounds with acidic/basic groups. The faster permeation of the neutral form leads to a pH variation inside liposomes and is followed by encapsulated pH-sensitive probes. In this work, we characterized the permeability for a large set of drug-like molecules using a stopped-flow and plate reader.

The observed pH variation is interpreted with our detailed kinetic model for an accurate calculation of compounds' permeability coefficient.[1] Unlike previous approaches using the pH-variation assay, this model explicitly includes several steps: association with the membrane, translocation, changes in the compound ionization when associated with the membrane, the establishment and dissipation of the pH gradient. This helps to rationalize the contribution of different molecular properties to overall permeability.

The results show that compound mass transfer across membranes occurs in different timescales, with discrepancies arising from each methodology's distinct sensitivity. The simplicity and broad applicability of this method make it a valuable tool in early stages of drug development, allowing the identification of compounds most likely to succeed in detailed in vitro and in vivo studies. Our model is also a valuable for understanding results and discrepancies in permeability coefficient from different methodologies.

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References: [1] Cordeiro, M. M., Salvador, A. & Moreno, M. J. *Membranes* 12 (2022) 3: 254

P62. UNRAVELLING THE FUNCTION OF KEY RESIDUES IN THE NON-CLASSICAL BACTERIAL PEROXIDASE FROM *ESCHERICHIA COLI*

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Keywords: *Non-classical bacterial peroxidase, hydrogen peroxide detoxification, kinetics*

ABSTRACT

Pathogenic strains of *E. coli* are responsible for several human diseases. In some cases, the host's cells expose the pathogens to high concentrations of radicals, like hydrogen peroxide as a defence mechanism. Bacterial peroxidase composed of three-domains have been identified in the genome of pathogenic bacteria, but only a few were isolated and characterized to date [1]. They are proposed to be involved in the detoxification of hydrogen peroxide in the periplasm [1] and to confer the ability to use H₂O₂ as a terminal electron acceptor in the absence of oxygen [2]. We have focused our studies on YhjA, a quinol peroxidase from *E. coli* [3]. YhjA is a tri-hemic enzyme with a predicted transmembrane helix. The soluble domain of YhjA presents peroxidase activity *in vitro* using hydroquinone and menadiol as electron donors, and the coordination of the N-terminal heme has been established [3],[4]. We are currently characterizing YhjA variants in key residues involved in intra-electron transfer and involved in the catalytic mechanism. These variants are being characterized using biochemical and biophysical techniques (UV-visible and CD spectroscopy, DSC), and steady-state kinetics.

Inhibition studies have shown the ability of the wild-type enzyme to bind azide and imidazole, with different affinities and binding mechanisms. The variant W250F has similar spectroscopic properties with YhjA WT, but lower activity using ABTS²⁻. The other variants are currently being characterized.

The spectroscopic and kinetic characterization of these variants will contribute to a more complete understanding of the catalytic mechanism of non-classical bacterial peroxidases.

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References: [1] D. S. Barreiro, *et. al.* Elsevier B.V. (2023):485, 215114 ; [2] M. Khademian *et. al.* PNAS (2017):114, 6922; [3] C. S. Nóbrega, *et al.* BBA (2018):1859, 411; [4] R. N. S. Oliveira *et. al.* Molecules (2023):28, 5498

P63. USING ¹H-NMR TO UNCOVER BRONCHOALVEOLAR LAVAGE FLUID BIOMARKERS FOR DETECTING LOWER RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTIONS

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Keywords: Lower Respiratory Tract Infections (LRTIs), Bronchoalveolar Lavages Fluids (BALFs), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), biomarkers, diagnosis.

ABSTRACT

Lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs) are a leading cause of death globally, caused by various bacterial pathogens like *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The complexity of LRTIs makes the treatment more challenging and, therefore, an accurate and timely diagnosis is crucial. However, there is a notable lack of reliable biomarkers to improve LRTI diagnosis.

We performed untargeted ¹H-NMR metabolite profiling of bronchoalveolar lavage fluids (BALFs) to identify biomarkers for LRTI diagnosis. BALFs from outpatients with both infectious and non-infectious LRT diseases were collected at CHUdSA Hospital (Porto, Portugal) and analyzed using standard microbiological diagnostic techniques. The data were then integrated with NMR-based metabolomics of the BALFs.

Microbiological analysis identified Enterobacteriales (~26%), *Haemophilus influenzae* (~18%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (~10%), and *Moraxella catarrhalis* (~10%) as the most frequent bacteria causing LRTI disease. Multivariate analysis (PCA, PLS-DA, OrthoPLS-DA) of the metabolomics data showed partial separation between infectious and non-infectious LRTIs. Further refinement by focusing on samples infected with *Haemophilus influenzae* led to complete differentiation, with improved model fit and predictive performance. However, no significant separation was observed between the major pathogens, suggesting that no exclusive metabolic markers for specific species are present.

Gram-negative bacteria (79%) are a major cause of LRTIs in CHUdSA outpatients. Untargeted ¹H-NMR metabolomics identified potential biomarkers distinguishing infectious from non-infectious LRTIs, but no unique metabolic features were found for specific pathogens. Further analysis is ongoing to identify key metabolites.

P64. YEAST DISPLAY FOR PROTEIN LIBRARIES SCREENING

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Keywords: *Yeast Display, Protein Engineering, Biophysical Assays, SPR, BLI.*

ABSTRACT

Yeast display is a versatile platform to screen protein interactions and engineer novel binders by expressing proteins on *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*'s membrane, enabling selection of high-affinity variants by fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS).

Proteins are fused to the Aga2 anchor protein and displayed on the yeast surface with specific tags for expression and binding detection. High-throughput screening is performed using FACS, after incubation with labeled targets. At ITQB NOVA, yeast display is currently being implemented for the screening of miniproteins and monobody libraries. Two computationally designed libraries targeting SARS-CoV-2 and Zika virus proteins were screened. Yeast display analyses were also deployed to validate surface plasmon resonance (SPR) analyses testing for 53 miniproteins interactions with RBD (thus targeting SARS-CoV-2).

We obtained a high-efficiency library transformation, which was validated through colony PCR and sequencing. The Zika library had very low expression levels, whereas the RBD library showed no detectable expression. The system was successfully applied to individually screen of miniproteins targeting RBD.

Yeast display complements classical biophysical techniques like SPR and biolayer interferometry (BLI) by enabling rapid pre-screening of candidates before detailed kinetic characterization. The integration of these techniques in high throughput pipelines have the potential to accelerate drug discovery and biomolecular interaction studies.

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P65. μ S-LONG DYNAMICS OF H5N1 HEMAGGLUTININ GLOBULAR HEAD: EPIOTOPE STABILITY AND GLYCAN SHIELDING

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Keywords: H5N1, Avian Influenza, Hemagglutinin, Molecular Dynamics, Zoonotic Transmission.

ABSTRACT

Highly pathogenic avian influenza virus (HPAIV) H5N1 poses a significant threat due to its increasing ability to infect mammals. The latest strain (A/cattle/Texas/2024) has caused an outbreak in dairy cattle across the United States, spreading to poultry and humans working in close contact with infected animals. While no human-to-human transmission has been confirmed, the virus' continued spread and adaptation to new mammalian hosts raise concerns about its potential to acquire this capability, potentially leading to human-to-human transmission.

The present study focuses on the globular head domain of the hemagglutinin (HA) protein, responsible for host cell attachment. The X-ray structure of HA (PDB ID: 9DIP), solved in the glycosylated form, was used as a starting point for μ s-long molecular dynamics. The structure was truncated to include only the globular head, with the N-linked glycan at N169 and inserted into a simulation box with water and ions. The simulations were performed with GROMACS 2021.7 using the AMBER14sb force field. Three replicates ensured robust sampling of conformational dynamics.

The simulations provide a detailed characterization of the conformational landscape of the hemagglutinin globular head and enable the assessment of stability in regions critical for receptor binding. The receptor binding site (RBS) remains stable and accessible throughout the simulations, with no evidence of shielding by the glycan at N169.

By enhancing our understanding of H5N1 HA globular head conformational dynamics, a foundation is laid for future targeted interventions to contain the pandemic potential of this evolving virus.

References: Burrough ER, Magstadt DR, Petersen B, Timmermans SJ, Gauger PC, Zhang J, et al. Highly pathogenic Avian influenza A(H5N1) Clade 2.3.4.4b virus infection in domestic dairy cattle and cats, United States, 2024. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* [Internet]. 2024 May 1;30(7). DOI: 10.3201/eid3007.240508 PMID: 38683888.